

A PHONOLOGY OF EMAI

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A PHONOLOGY OF EMAI

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Life is fiction
The mind is the writer

Clouds gather so that there may be rain
The sun sets so that it may rise
Night is that day may be
Sorrow is the mirror of joy.

Francis Oisaghaede Egbokhare.

DEDICATION

To my beloved parents -
Philip Oarhe Egbokhare
and
Magaret Abunovbo Egbokhare
and
My maternal grandmother -
Onokhifa Ilevbare

ABSTRACT

This study sets out to provide a phonological description of Emai.

In Chapter One we discuss the sounds of the language and establish the significant ones.

Chapter Two reviews the autosegmental framework which forms the theoretical orientation adopted in this study. We adopt a version of the theory which holds that distinctive features have an internal hierarchical structure.

Morphological structure and processes come under attention in Chapter Three. Deictics in Emai are found to exhibit an interesting morphological structure in which a regular correspondence between sound and meaning is observed in the VCVV deictic frame. Morphological processes such as Compounding, Prefixation and Reduplication are discussed.

In Chapter Four we discuss the syllable structure processes such as Vowel Elision (V.E.), Glide Formation (G.F.) and Vowel Insertion. V.E. and G.F. are under the control of the grammar. Both processes apply only within primary constituent boundaries prior to the application

of word order rules.

Chapter Five deals with various assimilation processes such as total vowel assimilation, palatalisation and nasalization. Nasalization is captured by an MSC and a left to right spread of nasality. The MSC ensures that elements within a syllable agree in nasality while spreading ensures that nasalization covers the word domain of nasality. Nasality is found to exhibit 'stability' in Emai only if it is underlying. However, such stable nasality is effaced following lexicalisation.

Finally, Chapter Six examines the tonal phenomena in Emai. It examines DS and DD and tonal changes in various syntactic units.

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My uncle, Dr Ilevbare was very helpful in my struggle to get this thesis completed. I am grateful for his encouragement and advice.

The tide tells the strong ship; but no ship is strong without a crew. I rode on rough tide steered

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by
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ABBREVIATIONS AND CONVENTIONS

!	- Downstep
∅	- null or zero
#	- Morpheme or word boundary
∕	- Delinking
Ⓛ	- Floating Low tone
Ⓜ	- Floating High tone
μ	- Morpheme symbol
σ	- Syllable symbol
Asp	- Aspect Morpheme
Cd	- Concord
Cl	- (Noun) Class
Comp	- Comparative
Comp	- Complement Marker
CONT	- Continuous Morpheme
CPA	- Completive Past
CPE	- Completive Present
Def	- Definite Morpheme
DR	- Deictic Root
DX	- Deixis
Fac	- Factative
G.	- Goal
G.F.	- Glide Formation
HAB	- Habitual Morpheme
It.	- Iterative Morpheme
log	- logopheric pronoun
Loc	- Locative
NEG	- Negator
Nom	- Nominal
Pref	- Prefix
n.p	- Noun Prefix

ABBREVIATIONS AND CONVENTIONS

Prep	-	Preposition
Prox	-	Proximity Morpheme
ref	-	Reference
RP	-	Replacive Pronoun
SCM	-	Subject Concord Marker
FUT	-	Future Marker
IFUT	-	Immediate Future
RFUT	-	Remote Future
V ₁	-	First Vowel in a Sequence
V ₂	-	Second Vowel in a sequence
V.E.	-	Vowel Elision
DUB	-	Dubitive
Aux	-	Auxiliary
AM	-	Associative marker

INTRODUCTION

0.1 LANGUAGE AND PEOPLE

Émáì is the name of a community of villages with claims of a common origin and cultural beliefs. The community is located at the eastern part of Owan Local Government Area of Bendel State of Nigeria (See Figs. 1 and 2). Émáì is also the name of the speech variety spoken in this community.

Émáì community is made up of the following villages: Afuze, Uanhumi, Eteye, Okpa, Ogute, Evbiamę, Ojavun and Ovbionwu. It has a population of about 40,000 people.

The name Émáì is said to be derived from Ímā who, according to oral tradition, is the ancestor of the Émáì people. He was said to have fled from the ancient Benin kingdom around the 16th century for an undisclosed reason.

Elugbe (1989) classifies Émáì under the 'Ora-Emai-Iuleha' dialect cluster of the North Central Branch of Edoid. The Edoid group is in turn a branch of New Benue-Congo of Niger-Congo. In Figure (3) we present

FIG 1 Political Map Showing Towns In Owen
Local Government Area.

SOURCE : Ministry Of Information, Atuze.

FIG 2 Map Of Owan Local Govt Area Showing The Division Districts And Position Of Emai District

SOURCE : Ministry Of Information, Afuze.

Elugbe's (1989:26) Classification of Edoid languages

Fig. 3 The Edoid family tree

KEY: PDE - Proto Delta Edoid
 PSWE - Proto South-Western Edoid
 PNCE - Proto North-Central Edoid
 PNWE - Proto North-Western Edoid
 PSNWE - Proto Southern-North-Western Edoid
 PO - Proto Osse.

Ora and Iuleha are mutually intelligible dialects spoken in communities bordering Emai to the Southwest and West up to the River Qsq. Elugbe (1989: 24) notes that in spite of the fact that these dialects are easily recognised as dialects of the same language, political and interethnic rivalry has prevented the adoption of one of them as the standard. This rivalry is probably more pronounced between Ora and Emai as revealed by stereotypes and stories handed down to generations of indigenes of both communities.

0.2 Objective

Our objective is to contribute to linguistic theory while still making the work practically relevant to the language users. To achieve this objective we strive to marry data and theory and thus avoid the fallacy that has characterised a number of linguistic studies over the years - that of practical non-relevance. The need for theoretical contribution stems from a natural desire to uphold the universal objective of all linguistic studies - bringing man closer to a perfect understanding of the nature of

language. The theoretical contributions will not be by way of straightforward proposals or theoretical reforms, but will be in the form of the testing of assumption

The need for practical contributions cannot be overemphasized in an undeveloped language like Emai. It is worthwhile that the study should contribute to the standardization and modernization of the language (especially in the areas of orthography and lexical expansion). This, if it must be adequate, should necessarily await a morpho-phonological statement of the language.

In the area of morphology, we seek to define the 'word' in a principled way so as to solve the orthographic problem of distinguishing between compounds and phrases, since their differences are not readily obvious in the Edoid languages. We take special interest in the role of syntax and morphology in the phonology of the language. Although syntax and morphology have long been recognized as playing significant roles in the phonologies of languages, most phonological studies do not go beyond acknowledging their involvement. Usually, no effort is made to explore

the depths of influence which they exert on the phonology. The result is that useful generalisations are missed and, in fact, the absence of such vital grammatical data complicates the solution to otherwise simple problems. This study therefore seeks to demonstrate the influence of syntax on the phonology of Emai and proceeds to capture this influence in a principled way.

Finally, we hope in the end to contribute to a better understanding of the Edoid languages. With further research, we hope that, in the future, it will be possible to outline the defining characteristics of Edoid languages.

0.3 Previous works

Emai, like its sister (Edoid) languages, has little research to its credit. Linguistic research on the language was started in 1982 by Dr Ronald Schaefer. This research has culminated in the publication of some articles on its grammatical structure. The most notable of his research effort on the language is *An Initial Orthography and Lexicon*

of Emai Dialect of Edoid (I.U.L.C. 1987). No detailed research has been done on the phonology of the language.

x There exists, however, an M.A. dissertation on Vowel Elision in the language (1985) by the present writer. Long essays have also been written on the phonetics and phonology of Emai by students of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan (1987).

0.4 The Data

The quality of a linguistic work is to a large extent determined by the adequacy of its data base. The adequacy of its data depends largely on the scope vis-a-vis the subject of investigation. The scope of a set of linguistic data is determined by the extent to which it represents the geosocial structure of the community under investigation.

Data was collected in different locations from different speakers of different sociocultural dispositions. The advantage of such broad based data is that it unveils the variation in speech in the community thereby showing the nature and direction of

phonological change. This was particularly helpful in our analysis of palatalisation.

A large part of the data collected was oral traditions elicited in traditional settings. This was made up of about sixty-two stories and one hundred and thirty riddles and puzzles. The oral traditions provided us with data free of artificial elements associated with formally elicited data. For instance, we found that some Emai speakers tended to eliminate nasality from vowels under conscious elicitation. Also, through oral traditions, we were able to observe forms and expressions which are not currently in use in the language. This proved invaluable in the analysis of pronouns as older forms surfaced in the stories.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 PHONEMIC STATEMENT OF THE SEGMENTS

1.1 CONSONANTS

These are sounds produced with a degree of constriction of the vocal passage exceeding that found in close vowels. It includes stops, fricatives and approximants.

1.1.1 Phonation

Edoid languages make a selection from three states of the glottis in the production of consonants. These are: the voice state, the voiceless state and the breathy (voice) state. Of these three, all Edoid languages utilise the first two contrastively. Elugbe (1984: 326) notes that Ibilo and Emhalḥ (both Ọkpamheri dialects of NWE), Unḥḥ (of NCE) and Isoko (of SWE) also employ significantly the breathy-voice state of the glottis. Whereas Ibilo displays breathy-voice nasals, fricatives and laterals, Emhalḥ, Unḥḥ and Isoko display breathy-voicing only in fricatives.

Breathy-voice occurs when

the ligamentals are together while the arytenoids are apart. However, following (comparatively turbulent) high rate of

45 802 062015 10

airflow from the lungs, the vocal cords simply flap in the breeze.

(Elugbe 1989:36)

On the origin of breathy-voice sounds in the Edoid languages, Elugbe (1980a) claims that "breathy voicing is a stage in the development of voiceless lenis PE stops into voiced [consonants]".

Emai utilises contrastively the voice and voiceless states of the glottis at every point except at the glottal place of articulation where only the voiceless approximant [h] occurs.

1.1.2 Place and Manner of Articulation

Emai has sounds at the bilabial, labiodental, alveolar, palato-alveolar, palatal, velar and labial-velar places of articulation. Only the palato-alveolar position is not utilised contrastively. All manners of articulation (excluding nasal) are utilised contrastively. In all, there are fifty consonant sounds in the phonetic chart of Emai.

1.1.3 Phonetic Chart of Emai Consonants

	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Alveolar	Palato-alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Labialised Velar	Labial-Velar	[Glottal]
Nasal	m		n		ɲ		ŋw		
Plosive (Postnasalised)	p ^N b ^N p ^N b ^N		t ^N d ^N t ^N d ^N			k ^N g ^N k ^N g ^N		kp gb	
(Prenasalised)	mp mb		nt nd			ŋk ŋg		ŋmkp ŋmgb	
Affricate (Prenasalised)				tʃ dʒ					
Tap				ntʃ ndʒ					
Fricative		f v	s z	ʃ ʒ					
Approximant (Nasalised) (Lateral)	ʋ		r ɻ l		ʝ ɣ	x ɣ ɣ̃		w w̃	h h̃

1.1.4 Stops

Stops are consonant sounds produced by a total obstruction of the vocal tract followed by a sudden release (for plosives) or gradual release (for affricates).

1.1.5 Plosives

Emai has four sets of plosives produced at the bilabial, alveolar, velar and labial-velar places of articulation. In each of these places there is an opposition between voiced and voiceless plosives. Each of the plosives has a prenasalised allophone after nasal vowels. Before nasal vowels the plosives (excluding the labial velars) have postnasalised allophones.

1.1.6 Bilabial

At the bilabial position /p/ and /b/ occur

- | | | | |
|-------------|-----------|----------|----------|
| 1 a) /óplà/ | 'cutlass' | c) /óbò/ | 'hand' |
| b) /pèré/ | 'be flat' | d) /bà/ | 'to sew' |

It must be mentioned that /p/ occurs only in the two lexical items cited above. /b/ carries a heavier

functional load, occurring in a good number of words in the language. The rarity of /p/ in Emai may be as a result of its merger with */f/. Evidence from Proto-Edoid and reflexes in daughter languages show that the sound has merged with /f/ in most languages except in Avbianwu (of Yekhee (NCE)) and Epie (DE). (See Elugbe 1989: 102, Table A).

1.1.7 Alveolar

There is a contrast between /t/ and /d/ in Emai.

- 2 a) /t̃à/ 'say' c) /àt̃à/ 'truth'
 b) /d̃à/ 'drink wine' d) /àd̃à/ 'witches coven'

/t/ and /d/ have palato-alveolar allophones [t̃j] and [d̃j]. These allophones occur in a derived environment, before a palatal glide [j]. The glide is created by the glide formation rule which turns close vowels into glides when they occur before non-identical vowels (see Chapter Four for a discussion of glide formation process).

- 3 a) /ót̃í/ → [ót̃jě] → [ót̃jě̃]
 'cherry'

- b) /òtíàxó/ → [òtʃâxó] ~ [òtʃâxó]
 'day after tomorrow'
- c) /ódiò/ → [ódʒô] ~ [ód₃ô]
 'elder'
- d) /díàré/ → [dʒàré] ~ [d₃àré]
 'come out!'
- e) /étì/ → [étì]
 'power, breath'
- f) /ùtí/ → [ùtí]
 'fetters'
- g) /ídi/ → [ídi]
 'grave'
- h) /òdi/ → [òdi]
 'mute'

1.1.8 Velar

At the velar place of articulation we have /k/ and /g/. Like the alveolar plosives they become [tʃ] and [d₃] before the palatal glide [j].

- a) /ɛkià/ → [ɛkjà] ~ [ɛtʃà]
 'reedbuck'
- b) /kɪà/ → [kjà] ~ [tʃà]
 'become, until'
- c) /ògiè/ → [ògʒè] ~ [òd₃è]
 'king'
- d) /gliè/ → [gʒè] ~ [d₃è]
 'to laugh'
- e) /iki/ → [iki]
 'key'
- f) /ùgi/ → [ùgi]
 'basket'
- g) /ògii/ → [ògii]
 'fermented melon'

1.1.9 Labial-velar

/kp/ and /gb/ contrast at the labial-velar place as the examples below show:

- 5 a) /úkpà/ 'seed' c) /íkpl/ 'python'
 b) /úgbà/ 'fence' d) /ìgbì/ 'seed yam'

The labial-velar stops in Emai are produced with suction at the lips and explosion at the velum. The suction at the lips is the result of a velaric ingressive mechanism, while the explosion at the velum is produced by a pulmonic egressive mechanism. Elugbe (1989:30) notes for Ègèṅṅ that

although some kind of implosion is heard at the lips, the positive pharyngeal pressure (behind the velar closure) indicates the presence of an egressive pulmonic airstream.

He concludes that the implosion at the lips is the result of an ingressive velaric airstream. Also, in his discussion of labial-velars in Èdo (Bini), Ladefoged (1968) noted that three airstreams are involved in their production. These are the pulmonic egressive, the velaric ingressive and the glottalic ingressive. The first airstream alone, a combination with the first and second, or a combination of all

three airstreams can be used in the production of labial-velars in ɛdo (Bini). No instrumental study has been done to determine the exact number and combination of airstreams involved in the production of labial-velar plosives in Emai. Nevertheless, the implosion at the lips and the explosion at the velum are perceptually and articulatorily discernible.

1.2 Prenasalised and Postnasalised Stops

1.2.1 Prenasalised Stops

All stops in Emai are prenasalised when they occur after nasal vowels.

- 6 a) /xĩ̀é ópiá/ → [ʃɔmpja]

sell cutlass 'sell a cutlass'
- b) /kẽ ébè/ → [k^Nɛmbè]

share book 'share books'
- c) /ṭ̃ òtá/ → [t^Nònt^Ná]

roast squirrel 'roast a squirrel'
- d) /ṭ̃ ùdù/ → [t^Nùndù]

roast heart 'roast a heart'

- e) /bɛ́ ókà/ → [b^Nʃɔkà]
 pluck maize 'pluck maize'
- f) /gbàgà/ → [gbàŋg^Nà]
 'to trip, obstruct'
- h) /kɛ́ íkpù/ → [k^Níŋmkpù]
 share clothes 'share clothes'
- i) /ɛ́hà égbè/ → [ɛ́hàŋmgbè]
 make body 'sit properly'
- j) /sɛ́ ògíè/ → [sònd₃è]
 stab king 'stab king'
- k) /sɛ́ èkià/ → [sɛ́ntjà]
 stab reedbuck 'stab reedbuck'

Spectrographic evidence confirms the presence of prenasalisation in Emai. Figs. (4-8) show nasal formant taking up a substantial part of the duration of the stops. Precisely, the nasal formant takes up at least half of the duration of the sound in voiced segments. The plosive sounds in the figures below

— 1 —

Fig 4

K 3 m p j a

t e m b e

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Figs

Mant

Sendo

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fig 6

f z n f a

s o n d e

Fig 7

3 4 3 5

7 1 2 3 4 5

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Fig 8

96 2 99 2

7 394 2

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da

z b a

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Fig 9b

did

t & ind

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last for about 0.1 seconds. The nasal element takes up at least 0.05 seconds of this in voiced segments and about 0.025 seconds in voiceless segments. It would be noted that there is no significant difference between the length of a normal stop and a prenasalised stop as shown by the spectrograms in figures 9(a) and (b) ([àbà] 'type of food'/[ʃəmbà] 'sell eba'; [é:dó] 'termite'/[tè:ndó] 'sell termite'). [b] and [mb] last for about 0.1 seconds in figure (a) whereas in figure (b) [d] lasts for about 0.1 seconds while [nd] lasts for about 0.12 seconds.

The characteristic formant patterns of nasals are well-known. Fry (1979) notes that nasal formant is usually located in the region of the second formant of most vowels. This can easily be observed in the voiced prenasalised stops in figures (A-8).

Prenasalization in Emai is the result of the absence of synchrony in the oral and nasal processes. While the airstream for the preceding nasalised vowel terminates with the abduction of the articulators, the nasal air flow continues for some time as a result of the delay in securing a velic closure for the oral stop.

1.2.2 Postnasalisation (Nasal Plosion)

Emal plosives, with the exception of the labial-velar ones are produced with nasal plosion when they occur before nasal vowels. This plosion is however partial unlike the complete plosion in such words as [bʌtʌ] 'button' and [brɪtʌ] 'brittain' in English. Below are a few examples:

- 7 a) /fɒ̃/ → [fɒ̃^N]
- 'liver'
- b) /sɒ̃/ → [sɒ̃^N]
- 'husband'
- c) /ɒ̃t̃/ → [ɒ̃t̃^N]
- 'squirrel'
- d) /ú'g̃/ → [ú'g̃^N]
- 'velvet tamarine'
- e) /ák̃/ → [ák̃^N]
- 'teeth'

Oscillomink tracings showing nasal plosion in the examples above are presented in figures (10-1^a).

For ease of typing we shall not indicate nasal

Fig 10

Fig 11

Fig 12

s d z

Fig 14

- 9 a) /ɛsɔ̃/ 'poverty, suffering' c) /sà/ 'shoot'
 b) /ɛzɔ̃/ 'litigation, case' d) /zà/ 'from'

The voiceless alveolar fricative /s/ has an allophone in the voiceless palato-alveolar fricative [ʃ] in a derived environment, before a palatal glide [j]. This glide is created by a glide formation rule which turns close vowels into glides when they occur before non-identical vowels.

- 10 a) /ósi ókpó/ → [ósjɔ̃kpó] → [óʃɔ̃kpó] x
 'yellow yam'
- b) /si óbò/ → [sjóbò] → [ʃóbò]
 'move hand'
- c) /fisi/ → [fɛjɛ́] → [fʃɛ́]
 'pepper'
- d) /ɛsi/ → [ɛsi]
 'horse'
- e) /fisi/ → [fisi]
 'pig'

plosion and prenasalisation in our transcription in this work except where it has implications for our analysis.

1.3 Fricatives

Fricatives are sounds produced with a close approximation of the articulators, resulting in turbulence in the outflowing airstream. They are characterised by randomly distributed energy peaks (noise) over the sound spectrogram.

In Emai, fricatives are produced at the labiodental, alveolar and palato-alveolar positions. The palato-alveolar fricatives are allophones of the alveolar fricatives and velar approximants.

1.3.1 Alveolar and Labiodental

Two fricatives /f/ and /v/ occur in contrast at the labiodental place.

- | | | | | | |
|------|------|-------------|------------|-------|-------------------------------|
| 8 a) | /fà/ | 'lose face' | c) | /ifè/ | 'whistle' |
| | b) | /và/ | 'to split' | d) | /i've/ 'pricing,
haggling' |

At the alveolar place /s/ and /z/ occur in contrast.

- 11 a) /vâ/ → [vâ]
'you pl.'
- b) /vê/ → [vê]
'be wide'
- c) /úvêc/ → [úmêc]
'salt'
- d) /éuâ/ → [éná]
'yam'

There are a few instances of [m] occurring before oral vowels in words

- 12 a) [ómòò] 'friend'
- b) [ímè] 'farm'
- c) [ómòhè] 'man'
- d) [émèdó] 'sweet potato'

The only process that can create a nasal consonant plus oral vowel sequence in Emai is the nasality effacement rule. This process affects only compound nouns - deleting nasality from the final vowel of N_1 in an $N_1 + N_2$ sequence. Examples (c) and (d) above have the

derivation in 13(a) and (b).

13 a) óvò + òhè > ómò + òhè > ómòhè
 child male 'man'

b) évà + èdó > émà + èdó > émèdó
 yam Edo(Bini) 'sweet potato'

c) àfè + ú`zé > áfúzè
 home axe 'name of a place'

d) ódò + àfè > ódàfè
 husband home 'head of household'

Although the derivational history of (12a and b) above is lost, we believe that they are from the same source as (c) and (d). For detailed discussion of nasality effacement see Chapter Five.

1.4.3 Palatal Approximant

The voiced palatal approximant /j/ becomes a palatal nasal before a nasal vowel.

- 14 a) /òjà/ → [òjà]
 'hardship'
- b) /jè/ → [jè]
 'send'
- c) /ájè/ → [ájè]
 'to reply'
- d) /jà/ → [jà]
 'to pamper'

A [j] allophone is found occurring in free variation with [ɲ] before nasal vowels in the third person singular and plural logophoric pronouns.

- 15 a) /íjái/ → [íjái] - [íɲái]
 3rd pers. pl. (logophoric)
- b) /íjái/ → [íjái] - [íɲái]
 3rd pers. sg. (logophoric)

1.4.4 Labial-velar Approximant

The voiced labial-velar approximant /w/ has three allophones [w], [w̃] and [ɣw]. [w] occurs before oral vowels while the latter two occur before nasal vowels.

[w̄] occurs only in one lexical item in the language. In spite of its sparse distribution, we must distinguish [w̄] from [ɣw] in the language since we cannot substitute them.

- 16 a) /éwè/ → [éwè]
 'goat'
- b) /áwà/ → [áwà]
 'dog'
- c) /èwáí/ → [èwáí]
 'wisdom'
- d) /wà/ → [ɣwà]
 'take'
- e) /íwá/ → [íɣwá]
 'dirt'

The situation where two separate allophones are found occurring in the same environment (i.e. before nasal vowels) calls for comments. It is possible that [w̄] is a relic of an earlier allophone from which [ɣw] was derived over time.

1.4.5 Velar Approximant

Emai has two approximants at the velar place of articulation. They are the voiceless and voiced approximants, /x/ and /ɣ/. These sounds contrast as shown by the examples below:

- | | | | |
|-------|------------|----|------------|
| 17 a) | /éyè/ | c) | /yàrà/ |
| | 'time' | | 'prop' |
| b) | /xàsè/ | d) | /xàxà/ |
| | 'wait for' | | 'to sieve' |

Uzochukwu (1987) treats the velar approximants as fricatives. He notes that in Emai the phonetic category of fricatives is made up of sounds that comprise solely turbulent noise or hiss, and those that have minimal turbulence. In this latter group are the velar fricatives which he observes have some formant structure which makes them look like approximants. Uzochukwu was probably influenced by the situation in other Edoid languages as regards velar sounds. At the velar position most Edoid languages make a choice between fortis and lenis plosives and velar fricatives. Some languages realise all these sound types. In these

languages, the lenis plosive and the fricative usually occur in free variation (see Elugbe 1989). Spectrographic evidence (Figures 15 and 16) shows clearly that these sounds are approximants. In the absence of glottal noise/ tone, it is the local friction of the point of articulation that is responsible for noise in the fricative. In these cases, there is no local noise, hence the absence of noise in the approximant.

Phonological evidence is in support of our analysis of /x/ and /ɣ/ as approximants. If we analyse them as velar fricatives, they would be the only fricatives that are nasalised in the language. On the other hand, all approximants in Emai have nasalized allophones before nasal vowels. Thus, what would have been a general rule of nasalization would be unnecessarily complicated. Examples (18) below show the nasalization of /x/ and /ɣ/ before nasal vowels.

18 a) /xɔ̃/ → [xɔ̃]

'bathe'

b) /xɔ̃/ → [x̃ɔ̃]

'be content'

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O X a

E 8 E

Fig 15

Fig 16

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3 2 3

3 2 3

c) /ɣàɣà/ → [ɣàɣà]

'to prop, support'

d) /ɣɔ̀ɣò/ → [ɣɔ̀ɣò]

'be happy'

/x/ is also realised as [ɣ] before [j]

19 a) /óxíà/ → [óx̣já] → [ójá]

'walking'

b) /xíé/ → [x̣jé] → [jé]

'sell'

c) /éxi/ → [éxi]

'cripple'

d) /ixi/ → [ixi]

'name of a place'

There is no example of /ɣ/ becoming [ɣ̣] in our data. At the same time there is no instance of /ɣ/ occurring before [j]. As in the case of /z/ we suspect that such change occurred in the past even though we cannot elicit it today.

1.4.6 Glottal Approximant

The voiceless glottal approximant /h/ occurs in

Emai. It is nasalised before nasal vowels.

- 20 a) /óhà/ → [óhà̃]
 'wife'
- b) /ihùè/ → [ihwè̃]
 'nose'
- c) /éhǝ/ → [éhǝ̃]
 'ear'
- d) /óhǝ/ → [óhǝ̃]
 'anger'

1.4.7 r-sounds

Emai has two r-sounds. These are the voiced alveolar tap [ɾ] as in:

- 21 a) [ɛɾèè]
 'blood'
- b) [óɾǝ̃]
 'tree'

and the voiced alveolar central approximant [r] as in

- c) [rèyè]
 'to rock'
- d) [rèrè]
 'be far, long'

The tap is produced by a very brief contact between the blade of the tongue and the alveolar ridge. This is what differentiates it from plosives. The alveolar central approximant is produced by an open approximation of the blade of the tongue and the alveolar ridge. The tap and the approximant are in free variation.

The approximant has a nasalised allophone before nasal vowels.

- 22 a) /rɔ̃/ → [rɔ̃]

 'to rain'
- b) /rãa/ → [rãã]

 'forment'
- c) /ràà/ → [ràà]

 'to plaster'

1.A.8 Lateral Approximant

Emai has only one lateral approximant /l/ produced at the alveolar place with voice phonation. Its production involves total, central occlusion of the vocal tract at the alveolar ridge while still allowing the airstream to escape round the sides of the tongue. It

is realised as a voiced alveolar nasal, [n], before nasal vowels.

- 23 a) /lèlè/ → [lèlè]
 'copulate'
- b) /là/ → [là]
 'run'
- c) /úlâ/ → [únû]
 'mouth'
- d) /ilî/ → [inî]
 'elephant'

1.4.9 The Phonemic Chart of Emai Consonants

	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Labial-velar	Glottal
Plosive	p b		t d		k g	kp gb	
Fricative		f v	s z				
Approximant (Central)	ɔ		r	j	x ɣ	w	h
(Lateral)			l				

The phonemic consonant chart of Emai contains only twenty sounds made up of eight stops, four fricatives and eight approximants.

1.5 Vowel System

There are twelve contrastive vowels in Emai, consisting of seven oral and five nasal vowels. The oral vowels are /i e ε a o o u/, while the nasal ones are /ĩ ē ā õ ũ/. There are no phonemic half-close nasal vowels (i.e. */ə ɔ/) in Emai. Below are examples showing contrast between oral and nasal vowels.

- | | | |
|-------|--------|----------------|
| 24 a) | /úkpù/ | 'cloth' |
| b) | /úkpũ/ | 'coconut' |
| c) | /sà/ | 'shoot' |
| d) | /sã/ | 'be pellucid' |
| e) | /kò/ | 'to plant' |
| f) | /kõ/ | 'snore, stain' |
| g) | /sì/ | 'pull' |
| h) | /sí/ | 'deny' |
| i) | /sè/ | 'get to' |
| j) | /sẽ/ | 'stab' |

In addition to the twelve vowel phonemes, [ẽ] and [õ] occur in the phonetic chart. This is because each of the seven oral vowels may be nasalised when they occur in the environments of nasal vowels. Below, we present an auditory phonetic chart of Emai vowels.

1.5.1 Auditory Phonetic Chart of Oral and Nasal Vowels

Acoustic studies (Uzochukwu 1987; Adeniyi 1987) support the chart. Their investigation showed that nasal vowels are lower than their oral counterparts.

There is a clear height distinction between [e] and [o] in Emai. The latter is very high up as a mid vowel and it is sometimes confused with [u] by non-native speakers of the language.

1.5.2 Vowel Sequences

Vowel sequences are common in Emai. There is, however, a restriction on the types of vowels that may occur in sequence. There are basically two types of sequences. These are the identical vowel sequences and non-identical vowel sequences. The latter type may be broadly divided into the closing and opening sequences. By an opening sequence we mean one in which a close vowel is followed by a non-close vowel; on the other hand, a closing sequence is one in which a non-close vowel is followed by a close vowel. Below are examples of these sequences.

- | | | | | | |
|-------|--------|--------------|----|--------|---------------|
| 25 a) | /hià/ | 'cut' | h) | /òí/ | 'pomade' |
| b) | /hùà/ | 'carry' | i) | /àhòì/ | 'nothingness' |
| c) | /ékùè/ | 'meeting' | j) | /éí/ | 'tortoise' |
| d) | /xùò/ | 'fade' | k) | /èhàí/ | 'forehead' |
| e) | /viè/ | 'be dorn' | l) | /òú/ | 'cotton' |
| f) | /lò/ | 'song' | m) | /èù/ | 'shirt' |
| g) | /úò/ | 'chimpanzee' | | | |

We have only three examples of non-identical sequences which are neither closing nor opening in our data.

They are:

- 26 a) /ɛ̀ò/ 'face'
 b) /áǎ/ 'sign'
 c) /èò/ 'buffalo'

Although vowel sequences mostly contain two vowels, there are examples where three vowels occur in a row:

- 27 a) /óíà/ 'ground squirrel'
 b) /óíà/ 'person'
 c) /úíá/ 'vein'
 d) /òíí/ 'a type of berry'
 e) /òf'é/ 'co-wife'

When we have a CVV or V-V-V sequence one of the vowels must be close; in the case of a V-V-V sequence, the medial vowel must be close.

Finally, sequences of identical vowels are commonplace in Emai. Below are some examples:

- 28 a) /óhòò/ 'dizziness'
 b) /úvǎǎ/ 'salt'
 c) /évvèè/ 'kolanut'
 d) /èè/ 'gain, profit'
 e) /ɣàà/ 'adjudicate'
 f) /hòò/ 'wash clothes'
 g) /hòò/ 'search for'

Schaefer (1987) analyzes these sequences as long vowels. Evidence from vowel elision clearly indicates that what we have are identical vowel sequences. Examples below show vowel elision cutting the length of these sequences by half.

- 29 a) /hòò éwè/ → [hòéwè]
 'search for goat'
- b) /hòò úkpù/ → [hòúkpù]
 'wash clothes'
- c) /hàà ósà/ → [hàósà]
 'pay debt'
- d) /kò èfó/ → [kèfó]
 'plant vegetables'
- e) /dè ófè/ → [dófè]
 'buy rat'

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 AUTOSEGMENTAL PHONOLOGY

The model of Generative Phonology in The Sound Pattern of English (SPE) (Chomsky and Halle 1968) makes the assumption that phonetic representation is composed of discrete segments (phonemes) which define its physical properties. Thus,

a phonetic representation has the form of a two-dimensional matrix in which the rows stand for particular phonetic features, the columns stand for the consecutive segments of the utterance ...
(Chomsky and Halle 1968: 5).

Autosegmental phonology is an attempt to provide a more adequate characterisation of the phonetic and phonological representation. It is a proposal at the same logical level as the SPE proposal that phonetic representation is a sequence of segments' (Goldsmith 1976). It differs however from SPE by proposing explicitly that:

- a) phonetic representation is multilinear or multi-tiered (Goldsmith 1976),
- b) tiers are linked,
- c) feature specifications have an internal hierarchical structure (Steriade 1982, Clements 1985, Sagey 1986),
- d) Some tiers may be morphemes (McCarthy 1979, 1981, Lieber 1987).

2.1.1 Multitier Representation

The concept of a multitier phonetic (and, consequently, phonological) representation was evolved as a result of the conceptual problem generated by feature asynchrony in phonological processes. Although within generative phonology features are bundled together in matrices, it is well known that these features do not always function as a unit. For instance, certain features are often retained in a number of languages despite the deletion of the segment of which they were supposed to be a part. In Emai for example, elision affects vowels without affecting nasality which is supposed to be a feature of the vowel.

- 1 a) /sɛ́ áwà/ --> [sáwà]
 stab dog 'stab dog'
- b) /fá éwèè/ --> [fɛ́wèè]
 pluck kolanut 'pluck kolanut'

According to Akinlabi (1985: 11) "this rule is fundamentally objectionable, for within any phonological theory, no elision rule deletes some features of a segment while leaving others. Elision rules rather delete whole segments". Similarly, glide formation and vowel elision may desyllabify a vowel while allowing its tone to be retained on a following vowel:

- 2 a) /ògìè jé èkó/ --> [òd₃é jékó]
 king go Lagos 'the king has gone to Lagos'
- b) /ófè dé òkpà/ --> [ófè dɔ́kpà]
 rat buy cock 'the rat has bought a cock'
- c) /ò fí òtá/ --> [ò fjótá]
 he/she throw squirrel 'he/she has thrown a squirrel'
- d) /ò xú èsò/ --> [ò xwɛ́sò]
 he/she chase suffering/ 'he/she has chased suffering/
 poverty poverty away'.

The 'stability' of nasality and tone (in examples (1) and (2) above) suggests that these and other vowel features in Emai are independent 'segments'.

In tone languages instances may be found where tones occur without being associated with a vowel segment. Such tones are commonly referred to as floating tones. The notion of floating tone which has been found to be theoretically and empirically desirable is practically impossible in a framework that strictly upholds a unilinear phonetic representation. It is impossible because tones as features of vowels cannot be realised without the vowels bearing them. The reality of floating tones is suggested by the following examples from Isoko. In Isoko, Donwa (1982: 194-5) notes that the associative (noun plus noun qualifier) construction is marked by a floating high tone which occurs between the two nouns as shown below:

3 a) òbò + ' + òbò
 hand native doctor

b) òlé + ' + òví
 yam goat

She notes also that some floating tones function as grammatical formatives. Questions in the language are marked by a final floating tone, while the positive interrogative is marked by final floating high tone. Elugbe (1982) refers to such a tonal morpheme as a 'tomorph'. As we shall see in Chapter Six tonal morphemes or tomorphs occur in Emai as well.

To account for these and other phenomena, autosegmental phonology postulates a multitier phonetic representation in which portions of the bundle of distinctive features are extracted and arrayed on independent tiers or levels (Goldsmith 1976). Such features constitute segments in their own right, hence the term 'autosegment'.

2.1.2 Linking of Tiers

All autosegmental phonologists agree that phonological representation is multitiered and that these tiers must be connected up or coordinated in order to obtain a well-formed phonological representation. But divergent views exist as to how this coordination is implemented. In the paragraphs that

follow, we shall attempt to give a summary of existing views.

As far as linking of the tiers is concerned, two positions exist:

- a) autosegments are linked to consonant and vowel segments or syllables (as in A),

- b) autosegments are linked to a structural (CV) tier (as in B)

The first position was adopted in early autosegmental studies (see Goldsmith 1976, 1979; Clements and Ford 1979). But the obvious problem is that it does not show the actual independence of the tiers since the autosegments are shown to be properties

of the units bearing them (consonants and vowels) after application of association convention. Although Goldsmith (1979) claims that after association the autosegment and the unit bearing it do not become a single unit, such ^arepresentation suggests that they are. In fact, one wonders how they are pronounced together if they are not a single unit.

The notion of a structural (CV) tier is contained in such works as McCarthy (1979, 1981), Halle and Vergnaud (1980), Clements and Keyser (1981), Marantz (1982), etc. They propose that autosegments are indirectly linked via the CV tier. The CV tier determines the timing relation of the autosegmental tiers. The CV tier is not just a descriptive artifact. Morphological and phonological evidence have been offered to confirm its reality. McCarthy (1979, 1981) shows quite convincingly for Semitic, that the CV-skeleton is a morpheme which interpolates the consonant root and vocalic inflections - both of which ¹ constitute different tiers. Phonological evidence ² confirming the presence of the CV tier comes from instances of compensatory lengthening (Clements and Keyser (1981)). According to Clements and Keyser,

"the phonological reality of the CV tier is demonstrated by the fact that it retains its identity in spite of processes which delete elements of the segmental tier" (p. 79). An example of compensatory lengthening comes from Icelandic. Thraisson (1978) (cf Clements and Keyser 1981) analyzes the preaspiration process in Icelandic as a kind of compensatory lengthening. In this language the past tense is formed by suffixing t to a stem (as in example (6) below, cf Clements and Keyser 1981, figure 23).

	<u>Infinitive</u>	<u>Past</u>
6. 'untie'	leys-a	leys-t-i
'stare'	glap-a	glap-t-i
'wake'	vak-a	vak-t-i

The first of a pair of identical voiceless aspirated consonants represented orthographically as p, t and k may be replaced by h. Consequently, the past tense suffix t causes a stem final t to be replaced by [h]:

7. (= Clements and Keyser fig. 24)

	<u>Infinitive</u>	<u>Past</u>
'meet'	mæt-a	mæt-t-i [maihti]
'grant'	veit-a	veit-t-i [veihti]
'utilise'	nyt-a	nyt-t-i [nihti]

Thraisson proposes that laryngeal features [+spread glottis] and [-spread glottis], supra-laryngeal features and CV occupy separate tiers in Icelandic. Preaspiration is the result of the deletion of the set of supralaryngeal features of the first two identical voiceless aspirated stops, followed by a spreading of the preceding vowel *on* to the vacant C-slot. This results in a long vowel with ... aspiration of the second part.

The CV model allows us to sustain the independence of the tiers. This model can be likened to a bicycle wheel with spokes (tiers) radiating from the hub (CV skeleton). This is shown schematically in figure 17 below from Pulleyblank (1983: 38):

Fig. 17

On the principles governing the linking of autosegments, Pulleyblank (1983: 31) offers the following universal association conventions:

Map a sequence of tones onto a sequence of tone-bearing units

- a) from left to right
- b) in a one-to-one relation

Association lines do not cross.

Autosegmentalists disagree on how to handle those situations where there are unequal numbers of autosegments and their bearing units. While Goldsmith (1976) would automatically cluster excess tones on the last syllable, Williams (1971) and Clements and Ford (1979) would allow the grammar of the language to determine whether or not we should have tone clustering. Goldsmith, Williams and Clements and Ford all allow automatic spreading of the last tone onto excess tone bearing units. Halle and Vergnaud (1982) modify this slightly to allow the convention to apply only to floating tones. Pulleyblank (1983) claims that tone clustering and spreading come about by language-specific

rules. We cannot make any contributions here since we have no data that bears on this in Emai.

At this point, we should mention that following recent advances in autosegmental phonology (Clements 1985, Sagey 1986, etc.) tiers are no longer related in the fashion just presented in section (2.1.2). Rather, a hierarchical organisation of features has required that only the root tier (which defines the phoneme concept) be linked to the skeleton. In the following section, we shall discuss this hierarchical organisation of the bundle of distinctive features and effect appropriate modifications of the representation in figure 17.

2.1.3 Feature Geometry

In its early stages, autosegmental phonology was a theory of suprasegmentals (e.g. tone, nasality, harmony, length, etc.). Its concern was primarily to justify the postulated structure of phonetic representation. Three compartments were easily recognised - the autosegment compartment, the structural (CV) compartment and the phonemic melody. The structural compartment

"served to identify the notion of segment with respect to timing phenomena and suprasegmental behaviour" (Anderson et al 1985: 205). The phonemic melody contained the distinctive feature matrix, composed of features that have not been autosegmentalised. This may be illustrated thus:

Autosegmental phonology adopted the SPE matrix model of feature specifications. Implicit in the matrix model is the idea that the bundle of distinctive features have no internal organisation whatsoever. Consequently, the features in a bundle of distinctive features are considered to be equally related. This position has been challenged following recent advances in autosegmental phonology (see Clements 1985, Sagey 1986, Pulleyblank 1988, etc.). It has been proposed that distinctive features have an internal hierarchical

organization which reflects the phonological or phonetic independence found among the features. "Thus, the relative independence of any two features or feature classes is correlated with the number of nodes separating them". Within this dispensation, features need no longer be extracted from the bundle of distinctive features to find autosegmental status.

Every node of the tree represents a set of features designated by the theory as a natural class; every node, terminal and nonterminal, represents a distinct autosegmental tier; and every autosegmental tier can play a role in the formulation of phonological processes.

Pulleyblank (1988: 235-6).

Below is a typical feature hierarchy representation.

At the base of the hierarchy are the terminal nodes which contain the individual features. A higher grouping brings these features under the place and manner nodes. The place and manner nodes are grouped together under a

supralaryngeal node. Finally, the laryngeal and supralaryngeal features are grouped into the root node. This node is the only phonologically motivated constituent in the hierarchy. The entirety of the non-terminal nodes may be referred to as class nodes (Clements 1985).

Feature hierarchies vary along several parameters such as: whether phonetic or phonological patterning of features should serve as the basis for establishing a hierarchy; whether the hierarchy can be manipulated on a language specific basis; whether to include monovalent "privative" features; and finally on the nodes as well as the hierarchical relationship between them.

Hierarchies are established either on the basis of vocal tract anatomy (Sagey 1986) or on the basis of the patterning of features in phonological and phonetic processes (Clements 1985). A feature hierarchy established solely on phonetic considerations makes a claim about the structure of human speech by showing that speech production is componential in nature. It involves the synchronization of simultaneous and partially overlapping gestures which exhibit varying

degrees of mutual independence. For instance, one can vary the vocal tract configuration while holding the laryngeal configuration constant and vice versa. Similarly, one can maintain a certain degree of stricture while changing the points of constriction and vice versa. This observation has led to the postulation of the following independent articulatory parameters as primary nodes of feature hierarchies.

- a) Laryngeal configuration
- b) Supralaryngeal configuration
 - i Degree of nasal cavity stricture
 - ii Degree and type of oral cavity stricture
 - iii A pairing of an active and passive articulators.

Each of these categories subsume a number of phonetic parameters. But these parameters do not exhibit any remarkable independence.

Sagey (1986) proposes a universal hierarchy based on the vocal tract anatomy. "Features are grouped according to the articulator in the vocal tract they are executed by. Articulators are grouped according to their acoustic effects on formants" (p. 12). Below is

a presentation of her hierarchy.

Fig. 20 Sagey 1986 (end view)

Clements' hierarchy, unlike Sagey's, is based on cross-linguistic generalisations concerning phonological and

phonetic processes. Features that pattern together in assimilation processes are grouped together. Thus, according to Clements,

... the study of the interaction among various sets of features, as observed (for example) in the study of assimilation rules provides prime evidence for the nature of simultaneous feature groupings. If we find that certain sets of features consistently behave as a unit with respect to certain types of rule of assimilation or resequencing, we have good reason to suppose that they constitute a unit in phonological representation ...

(1985: 226)

Evidence in support of the multitiered view of feature representation is presented by the spreading account of assimilation. The rule of assimilation has been argued to involve the spreading of an element of one tier onto a new position on an adjacent tier (see Halle and Vergnaud 1980; Goldsmith 1981; Steriade 1982; McCarthy 1982; Clements 1985). This is schematised in figure 21 below:

Fig. 21 (= Clements 1985: 231)

Three common types of assimilation occur. These are total assimilation in which the spreading feature is a root node, partial assimilation in which the spreading feature is a class node and feature assimilation in which the spreading feature is a single feature. The crucial evidence comes from the fact that each of these types of assimilation creates a linked structure as predicted by the hierarchical theory. In Emai, total assimilation, vowel elision or glide formation may apply when vowels occur in sequence across word boundaries. A piece of evidence showing that assimilation creates linked structures comes from the fact that sequences of identical vowels created by total assimilation do not undergo elision; at best they may be contracted (see e.g.s 8(a) and (b) below. In contrast, sequences of identical vowels are often objects of vowel elision (see e.g.s 8(c) and (d) below):

8 a) ɔ́ sáyá ɔ́í → ɔ́ sáyá áí
 he/she rip apart it
 'he/she has ripped it apart'

b) ɔ́ kpéyé é → ɔ́kpéyé é
 he/she shake you
 'he/she has shaken you'

c) ɔ́ gbé éfè → ɔ́ gbéfè
 he/she kill rats
 'he/she has killed rats'

d) ɔ́wèxá dɛ́ éwè → ɔ́wèxá dɛ́wè
 child buy goat
 'the child has bought a goat'

In Kolani, a vowel is normally inserted between consonant clusters when such clusters occur before another consonant or at word boundary. This rule does not apply in two environments - i.e. "between two members of a geminate consonant, or between a nasal-stop sequence in which the nasal has undergone a rule assimilating it to the place features of the following stop". This is because rules of partial assimilation create partly

linked structures. Thus, the nonapplication of vowel insertion in those instances is explainable in terms of the prohibition against crossing association lines. (For further discussions see Clements 1985: 231-3).

Laryngeal processes such as voicing assimilation, aspiration and deaspiration can apply without tampering with their supralaryngeal features (e.g. nasality, place and manner of articulation). An example can be found in Icelandic preaspiration. In Icelandic, aspirated geminate stops /p^h p^h, t^h t^h, k^h k^h/ become [hp, ht, hk] respectively. Thraisson explains this change in terms of the deletion of the supralaryngeal features of the first member of the geminate leaving behind the laryngeal features. This change is captured thus (cf Clements 1985: 233).

Fig. 22 Laryngeal tier:

The rule applies to two consonants which share laryngeal

and supralaryngeal features; i.e. geminate voiceless aspirated stops. The double crossed line shows the delinking of the supralaryngeal features of the first consonant of the geminate. The broken line spreads the supralaryngeal features of the preceding vowel onto the C resulting in an aspirated segment which shares all supralaryngeal features with the preceding vowel (i.e. an [h]).

The lower-level branching into place and manner of articulation also have justification. The rule of palatalisation is a very common rule which involves the addition of the feature [+high, -back]. Segments like [s, z, t, d] usually take [+high] feature whereas only [-back] is needed to express palatalisation of velars. This is particularly the case in Emai where all non-labial consonants (except /h/, /l/ and /r/) undergo palatalisation (becoming palato-alveolars) before a (derived) palatal approximant [j]. It is easy to see that both features [+high, -back] are functioning together here to indicate a change in place of articulation. Palatalisation in Emai could simply be explained in terms of the spreading of the (dorsal)

place features of [j] onto preceding non-labial consonants.

We agree with Clements that a feature hierarchy should not be based on a priori considerations of vocal tract anatomy but on an observation of the patterning of features in phonological and phonetic processes since in the end the hierarchy is intended not for phonetic classifications but for phonological purposes. One may recognize a universal hierarchy based on vocal tract anatomy just as one recognizes a universal phonetic inventory. This will define possible nodes and their phonetic implementation (see Ladefoged 1988 figure 2). But allowance must be made for languages to diverge in their selection of nodes as well as the functional relations of these nodes much in the same way as languages diverge in their selection of sounds from the universal inventory and the use to which such sounds are put.

Our operational hierarchy in this study is presented in figure 23 below:

Fig. 23

This hierarchy is similar to that presented in Pulleyblank (1988) (which is itself based on Sagey 1986). It is markedly different from Clements' by recognizing articulator nodes - Labial, Coronal and Dorsal which refer to the lips, tongue blade ~~and front~~, and tongue body ~~and~~ ^{back as} articulators respectively. Apart from the phonetic reality of the classification of features in terms of the articulators which implement them, phonologically,

such classification is necessary in explaining processes such a palatalisation which simply involves the spreading of dorsal features. Where features are not classified in terms of their articulators the output of palatalisation would depend on the nature of the input to the process - [anterior] segments would involve the addition of [+high] while velars would involve the addition of [-back].

The labial node is necessary for the explanation of processes in several languages. In Emai, for instance, there is an opposition between labial and non-labial segments. Thus, in accounting for palatalisation one must impose a restriction in the structural description that the sound be non-labial. Similarly, this labial/non-labial opposition must be specified in the account of vowel insertion in Emai. Labial segments (both vowels and consonants) spread their labial features onto adjacent vowels which have been inserted.

It would be observed that our hierarchy follows Clements' in postulating a manner node which dominates traditional manner features such as [sonorant], [continuant], [consonantal], [strident], [liquid] and [nasal]. The feature [liquid] is necessary in Emai to

oppose /l/ and /r/ with other consonants in Emai. Both sounds are the only non-labial consonants that do not undergo palatalisation. The feature [lateral] is absent from our hierarchy because it is unmotivated phonologically. The manner node is absent from Sagey's and Pulleyblank's hierarchies. Pulleyblank projects these features from the supralaryngeal node. Sagey projects the features [continuant] and [consonantal] from the root node while a soft palate node (under the supralaryngeal node) dominates the feature [nasal]. Other manner features are left in limbo. The exclusion of a MANNER node from Sagey's hierarchy creates otherwise avoidable problems. She justifies the projection of the features [consonantal] and [continuant] from the root node by the fact that they specify the degree of constriction of the primary articulators. The remaining features (excluding [nasal]) are left because they do not specify the degree of constriction of the primary articulators. It is clear that Sagey does not really know what to do with manner features. The confusion probably comes from the fact that in dealing with these features she abandoned the very (phonetic) basis of her hierarchy. Instead she uses as criterion for classifying

manner features, the domain of the features.

The traditional conception of 'Manner of Articulation' refers to the type of articulation as opposed to place of articulation. Thus, two natural classes of features - 'manner' and 'place' may be established.

Manner features are unique because they act on place features. But this does not suggest any kind of dependency between the two types of features. Just as there are processes which refer to place of articulation features, so also there are processes which refer to manner of articulation features (e.g. frication, spirantization, lateralization, etc.).

We follow Sagey in retaining a soft palate node. Although traditionally defined as manner of articulation, the nasal quality is not a property of constriction, but derived from a diversion of the airstream through the nasal channel. Its independence from manner features is shown by its ability to combine with virtually all constriction types. Phonologically, in Emai, nasality shows some degree of independence from other features.

X
Manner &
Place seem
to be
functionally
independent

For instance, nasality is often found to be retained after the deletion of nasal vowels. Conversely, nasality (but not any other features) may be effaced from a vowel segment following lexicalisation (see Chapter Five). In spite of this, however, supralaryngeal (manner) features exert a measure of influence on nasality. For example, [strident] consonants do not undergo nasalisation in Emai. This supralaryngeal influence has informed our projection of nasality as a supralaryngeal feature rather than projecting it from the skeleton like tone. Its independence from other manner features is expressed in terms of the soft palate node.

We follow Fulleyblank in projecting the tonal node from the skeleton rather than the laryngeal node. Like phonation and aspiration, tone is implemented by the larynx. It shows marked independence from these features phonologically in Emai. This independence is suggested by the fact that no laryngeal/supralaryngeal features need be specified in explaining tonal processes. Moreover, the deletion of a root-node (vowel elision) often leaves the tone floating

or relinked onto a following vowel segment. There is perhaps a strong motivation for specifying tonal features together with other laryngeal features in languages like Chinese and Nama where tones and laryngeal features interact. In these languages, voiced consonants lower the tones of following vowels (Sagey 1986: 49).

Finally, our hierarchy differs from Sagey's and Pulleyblank's in holding that the restriction placed on class nodes (articulator nodes) - that they be monovalent - is unnecessary. We need to be able to oppose labial and nonlabial segments in our specification of the structural description of palatalisation and vowel insertion in Emai. Having monovalent class nodes does not allow us to appropriate this restriction in our specification of these rules, since only the [+] value of the node can be realised (see Chapter Four, vowel insertion and Chapter Five, palatalisation). In fact, one cannot understand the motivation for this restriction on class nodes. If class nodes like terminal nodes constitute autosegmental tiers and are a locus of phonological rules alike, they should exhibit similar properties.

To conclude, it is important to note one marked advantage which the hierarchical organization of features has over previous autosegmental proposals. Previous proposals lacked the means of characterising the phoneme as a phonological unit. According to Clements (1985: 228),

... phonological representations are to a large extent segmentable into phonemes that behave as single units with respect to rules; indeed, this is one of the primary motivations for recognizing the phoneme as a category of linguistic theory. Rules must have access to phoneme-sized units in autosegmental theory as well. For example, they must be able to delete consonants and vowels or spread all the features of a consonant or vowel onto a neighbouring position in the skeleton, as in the case of compensatory lengthening process.

In previous frameworks, such rules referring to phoneme-sized units would have a highly marked status, since they must refer to features located on two or more tiers. Within the hierarchical model, the phoneme is conceptualised in the root node. Consequently, any

rule affecting the root node must be seen as affecting a phoneme-sized unit (e.g. segment deletion and total assimilation rules).

2.2 Autosegmental Morphology

Within autosegmental phonology, individual tiers may constitute independent morphemes. McCarthy (1979, 1981, 1983) contain a number of examples of this phenomenon.

McCarthy (1983, cf Lieber 1987) states that the features [+round] (labialisation) and the features [+high, -back] (palatalisation) are morphological tiers in *Chaha*, a Semitic language. "Among other categories, labialisation marks (with the suffix +n) a third person masculine singular object". The feature attaches to the rightmost labializable consonant in the root.

9. Perfective

- a) 3rd pers. Masc. Sg. Without Object: lanag
 With 3rd pers. Masc. Sg. Object: danag^w

Also, palatalisation "marks the verb for agreement with a second person feminine singular subject". The features [+high, -back] attach to the last root consonant.

b) Imperative

2nd pers. masc. sg. = s^yek^yət

2nd pers. fem. sg. = s^yek^yət^y

Examples 9(a) and (b) are drawn from Lieber (1987: 11).

In his account of Semitic morphology, McCarthy (1979, 1981) shows convincingly that consonantal roots, vocalic inflections and the CV- skeleta are different morphemes and must be placed on separate tiers. The nasal autosegment constitutes an autonomous morpheme in Coatzospan Mixtec. "In Coatzospan the second person singular of the verb is marked by a nasalisation 'prosody'. The word final vowel is nasalized, as are the preceding vowels if no voiceless obstruent intervenes" (Poser 1980a, cf Lieber 1987). In the

examples below, both vowels of the verb kò?ò 'to drink' are nasalized to inflect the verb for the second person singular.

10. kò?ò 'to drink' kò?ò̃ 'you sg. will drink'

To account for such problems of morphological structure, McCarthy (1979, 1981) proposes the following structure for the morpheme.

Fig. 2^a

The morpheme node (root node in McCarthy's terminology) identifies a string as a morpheme. It contains all non-phonological information associated with the morpheme such as rule diacritics, its status as a root or affix, its identity as a morpheme and the structure of the morpheme (i.e. CV combination). McCarthy shows convincingly that this structure is descriptively necessary and theoretically desirable. Our accounts of the morphological structures in Emai will be based on this proposal (see Chapter Three).

CHAPTER THREE

MORPHOLOGY

Morphology may be defined as lower-level syntax. This is because both syntax and morphology involve syntagmatic relations of some kind. Syntax has as its frame of reference the sentence as a unit of relationship involving words. Morphology on the other hand has as its frame of reference the word as a unit of organization involving morphemes. The term 'word' is used here to refer to the unit of lexical insertion. It is often a complex of morphemes. It is exactly this complexity in the structure of words that morphological theories seek to unravel.

This chapter deals with the morphology of Emai. We shall proceed by discussing the structure of the different lexical categories followed by an analysis of word formation processes in the language. For the purpose of this study, we shall recognise the following categories in Emai: (a) Noun, (b) Verb, (c) Deictics, (d) Modifiers, (e) Adjunctive and (e) construction markers.

3.1 Morphological Structure

A tacit distinction is often drawn in morphological literature between two types of morphological structure. These are the concatenative and the non-concatenative or discontinuous structures. The former includes various processes which string morphemes together in sequence (prefixation and suffixation) which are amenable to simple discovery procedures. The latter includes infixation, reduplication, suprafixation, etc. - structures which are not amenable to the methods of recurrent partials (McCarthy 1979, 1981). Both structures are often found occurring together in the same language.

In classical generative grammar (Chomsky 1965), the morpheme is regarded as a complex of phonological, syntactic and semantic features. The morpheme is represented as a sequence of segments bounded on both sides by boundary symbols. The phonological representation of the morpheme is seen as necessarily linear and non-hierarchical. McCarthy (1979, 1981) presents an alternative proposal (grounded in the autosegmental framework) where a separate simultaneous

level of morphological representation is recognised. He notes that this idea is implicit in Zellig Harris' (1951) 'Long Component' approach which he says may be extended to mean that a string of segments is uninterrupted, but morphological analysis is given by another simultaneous level of representation. This level of representation is defined by the root node μ (henceforth morpheme node). The morpheme node according to McCarthy identifies a string as a particular morpheme and contains all the non-phonological information associated with a morpheme. His conception of the phonological representation of the morpheme followed autosegmental traditions of the time (Halle and Vergnaud 1980, Clements and Keyser 1981). It consists of an autonomous prosodic (CV) template which defines an ordered string of feature matrices. In this study we adopt McCarthy's model of morphemic structure (see Figure 22, Chapter Two) with some modifications in the light of our discussions in Chapter Two. The CV node is a structural tier that neither defines nor is characterised by any features. Feature specifications have an internal hierarchical structure. In addition, part of the information which

the morpheme node must provide is the morpheme structure (i.e. CV structure).

3.2 Noun Structure

Welmers (1973: 159) states that "in all branches of the Niger-Kordofanian language family, with the exception of Mande, it is typical that a noun in its simplest form can be analyzed as constituted of a stem and an affix". In a number of West African languages such affixes are prefixes which distinguish number. Elugbe (1973) accounts for PE as having a noun class system in which the initial vowels function as class prefixes. The noun class system is still observable in Dɛgɛma (DE) (Elugbe 1976), and Oloms (NWE) (Elugbe and Schubert 1976). In Emai, traces of this class system can be observed in number formation in nouns and the pattern of vowel selection in nominalisation (see 3.7 and 3.8.3 below).

The noun in Emai can theoretically be of any length. However, nouns are basically bisyllabic or trisyllabic. Longer nouns are easily recognised as complex while a good number of trisyllabic nouns are derived. All nouns whether derived or not have

initial vowels which are historically class markers. This initial V- syllable differentiates nouns from verbs at the underlying level.

- | | |
|---------------|-----------|
| 1 a) /úrùkpà/ | e) /údò/ |
| 'lantern' | 'stone' |
| b) /ágèlè/ | f) /àgbà/ |
| 'young man' | 'jaw' |
| c) /àlèkè/ | g) /ófè/ |
| 'girl' | 'rat' |
| d) /ìkùkù/ | h) /òsè/ |
| 'bullet' | 'beauty' |

Derived Nouns

- | | | |
|----------------------------|---|-------------------|
| 2 a) /ùdèlòbò/ | < | ù + dèlò + óbò |
| 'stick for mashing things' | | np turn hand |
| b) /ùkpàkò/ | < | ù + kpè + àkò |
| 'chew stick' | | np wash teeth |
| c) /áè/ | < | á + èè |
| 'sign, mark' | | np know |
| d) /òzèwáí/ | < | ó + zè + èwáí |
| 'wise man' | | np extract wisdom |

There are examples of nouns of four syllables or more whose derivational history has been lost.

e) /lɔ̃gbɔ̃dɔ̃/

'earthworm'

f) /isɪsɪxùàí/

'wasp'

g) /éviévi/

'lizard'

The segmental structure of these nouns gives them away as derived forms. Example (e) looks like an ideophone - imitating the shape of the earthworm. Vowel repetition is one strategy employed in ideophones. Examples (f) and (g) suggest cases of partial and total reduplication.

In view of the discussions above we may represent the noun with the structure below:

Fig. 25

3.3 Verb Structure

3.3.1 Simple Verbs

The structure of the simple verb in Emai can aptly be captured by the following MSC:

$$V \rightarrow (C) V (((C)V)(V))$$

The structure above states that the verbal category has a maximal trisyllabic structure while the minimal structure is monosyllabic. All consonants are optional (as a result of historical loss and synchronic deletion) which means that we can have any of the following verbal structures.

3 VCV

- a) /ɛ̃yɛ̃/ 'be tasty' *see to*
 b) /ãyã/ 'stroll'

CV

- c) /tã/ 'say'
 d) /bũ/ 'be many'

VV

- e) /ãã/ 'castrate'
 f) /òò/ 'mimic'

CVCV

- g) /tòtò/ 'strong'
 h) /rùrù/ 'foolish'

V

- i) /è/ 'eat'
 j) /ù/ 'die'

CVVV

- k) /vîââ/ 'ask'
 l) /rûââ/ 'happen, occur'
 m) /hùèè/ 'boil'

CVV

- n) /bîâ/ 'work'
 o) /hîò/ 'be proud'
 p) /vîè/ 'cry'

Vocalic sequences within verbs, if not of the opening type (e.g. ia, io, ue), must be identical.

Some interesting facts emerge from the study of sound cooccurrences in Emai verbs. We can identify two verb types. Type A represents verbs which have identical consonants and/or vowel segments as shown below:

4 a)	kàkà	'dried, hard'	e)	èyè	'tasty'
b)	xàxà	'sieve'	f)	ùrù	'crush'
c)	xèxè	'sour'	g)	vèhè	'sleep'
d)	kpèkpè	'sickly'	h)	àà	'castrate'

Type B represents verbs which have unidentical consonants and vowel segments.

5	vià	'bear, give birth'
	ràvè	'swear'
	sùvè	'struggle'
	òhià	'be grown'

We hold the rather strong view that only monosyllabic verbs are simple in Emai (i.e. underived). Bisyllabic and trisyllabic verbs are complex and can be analysed into root plus formative structure, most of which have become fossilized. We shall attempt a reconstruction of some of these formatives.

The complete identity of consonants and vowels in Type A is occasioned by the process of reduplication and assimilation of suffix vowels to root vowels. We can actually observe the process of reduplication in a handful of verbs in the language, although most of the reduplications have been fossilized (i.e. frozen).

6 a)	xù	chase	-->	xùxù	'chase intensively'
b)	bà	stalk	-->	bàbà	'stalk intensively'
c)	jě	suckle	-->	jějě	'suckle intensively'
d)	và	mould sth.	-->	vàvà	'pile sth.'
e)	hà	press	-->	hàhà	'crush'
f)	*kpè		-->	kpèkpè	'sickly'
g)	*rù		-->	rùrù	'foolish'
h)	*dà		-->	dàdà	'wander'
i)	*lè		-->	lèlè	'copulate'

It will be noted that in examples (a-e) we have a general impression of intensification of meaning. This is paralleled in examples (f-i) by the fact that all the forms represent actions which are repeated, processes which are prolonged and states which are enduring.

*anyone of?
ask?
Duration?*

The complete identity of V_1 and V_2 in the non-reduplicated examples (4e-h) is probably the result of the assimilation of suffix vowels to root vowels. The assimilation has probably not been implemented in examples (5a-d). Our position is supported by the fact that we can reconstruct -CV suffixes from such verbs. These reconstructions are based on a comparison

of verbs in the language.

3.3.2 Verbal Suffixes

3.3.2.1 -YV

A look at the following data reveals a certain relationship between the forms which is perhaps a function of the YV syllable.

- | | | | | |
|------|-----------|----------------------------------|---------|---------------------------|
| 7 a) | /v̄àYà/ | 'be tamed' | /v̄àà/ | 'be used to' |
| b) | /r̄àYà/ | 'rub together or rub off' | "/r̄àà/ | 'plaster (as in a house)' |
| c) | /z̄àYà/ | 'scatter' | | |
| d) | /j̄àYà/ | 'rip apart' | /j̄à/ | 'rip off, severe' |
| e) | /s̄àYà/ | 'tear in bits' | | |
| f) | /r̄èYè/ | 'to rock' | | |
| g) | /kp̄èYè/ | 'shake' | | |
| h) | /v̄īàYà/ | 'sprinkle water' | | |
| i) | /r̄ùYù/ | 'unsettle debris in water' | | |
| j) | /s̄ùYù/ | 'wash by stirring' | | |
| k) | /h̄ùYù/ | 'stir for foam or lather' | /h̄ù/ | 'to foam' |
| l) | /l̄ùYù/ | 'to crinkle' | /l̄ù/ | 'to ring, chew' |
| m) | /ù̄Yù/ | 'grate, crush' | | |
| n) | /h̄òYò/ | 'to weaken by repeated movement' | | |

- o) /gùòyò/ 'bend to break' /gùò/ 'shiver'
 p) /wě̀yè/ 'crush to small particles'
 q) /zùvù/ 'turn things upside down'

*In other words give
some kind of process*

From the data above, it would seem that -YV has a causative meaning. It displays a constant meaning which has to do with certain conditions or actions for which there is a cause.

Non-identity of vowels in the type B verbs (e.g. 5) is probably caused by the fact that the assimilation process has not been completely carried through. We have been able to reconstruct some suffixes in these cases.

3.3.2.2 -jV suffix

This suffix assimilates to the stem in height and nasality. The form after /e/ and oral high stem vowels is [je], whereas [je] and [pē] occur after other oral vowels and nasal vowels respectively.

- 8 a) /vèjè/ 'tilt' --> [mèpè]
 b) /tìjè/ 'untie' --> [tìpè]
 c) /kpèjè/ 'wash off' --> [kpèjè] /kpè/ 'wash sth.'

- d) /xùjè/ 'close door' --> [xùjè]
- e) /vùjè/ 'cover a container' --> [vùjè]
- f) /xwèjè/ 'of long objects, break into parts' --> [xwèjè]
- g) /làjè/ 'rinse' --> [làjè]
- h) /ɣàjè/ 'share, separate, cut up' --> [ɣàjè]
- i) /vǎjè/ 'peel off' --> [mǎpè]

We can observe that a particular meaning of "off" or "un-" is recurrent and it involves a change from one state or condition to another.

Other recurrent forms in Emai verbs for which neither a definite meaning nor classification has been found are presented below:

3.3.2.3 -hiV

- 9 a) /vǎhià/ 'mould into a bolus' /vǎ/ 'mould'
- b) /tòhià/ 'be hot' /tò/ 'burn'
- c) /ùhiè/ 'add ingredients to beans'
- d) /òhià/ 'be grown'

3.3.2.4 -vè

- 10 a) /rāvè/ 'swear'
 b) /vīāvè/ 'difficult'
 c) /xōvè/ 'be ill'
 d) /dāvè/ 'test, attempt'
 e) /būvè/ 'to dust'
 f) /hūvè/ 'be good'

3.3.2.5 The Iterative suffix

The iterative suffix is added to a verb to indicate actions which are repeated. The suffix agrees with the verb stem in vowel height and nasality. The examples below are organised to reflect this agreement.

- | <u>A</u> | | | <u>B</u> | | |
|----------|----------|---------------|----------|----------|---------|
| 11 a) | [xùlò] | 'chase' | h) | [dèlò] | 'fall' |
| b) | [tùlò] | 'spit' | i) | [èlò] | 'eat' |
| c) | [filò] | 'throw' | j) | [zèlò] | 'chose' |
| d) | [silò] | 'pull' | k) | [dèlò] | 'buy' |
| e) | [ùlò] | 'die' | l) | [sàlò] | 'sting' |
| f) | [sòlò] | 'punch' | m) | [tàlò] | 'talk' |
| g) | [vòlò] | 'fetch water' | n) | [vòlò] | 'jump' |

	<u>C</u>	
o)	tĩnõ	'fly'
p)	vĩnõ	'write'
q)	vũnõ	'uproot'
r)	ɔwũnõ	'take'
s)	sãnõ	'leap'
t)	bãnõ	'undress'
u)	ʃãnõ	'sell'
v)	kẽnõ	'share'
w)	tõnõ	'dig'

We can summarise the suffix selection rule below:

- i) /-lɔ/ and /-lɔ̃/ are suffixed to stems with close and non-close oral vowels respectively.
- ii) These suffixes become [nõ] and [nõ̃] after nasal stem vowels. [õ̃] further becomes [õ] as a result of a rule that lowers nasalized half-close vowels within word boundaries.
- iii) The half-close rounded vowel /o/ assimilates the suffix vowel /ɔ/ hence we have [-lɔ] as the form occurring after /o/ (see Chapter Five for further discussions).

3.3.3 Complex Verbs

There is a class of 'idiomatic' verbs in Emai which is made up of a verb and a noun. Below are

examples:

- | | |
|---|--|
| 12 a) /rù èò/
roost face
'be blind' | g) /là ófè/
run fear
'be afraid' |
| b) /jí éhò/
pull out ear
'be deaf' | h) /xèxè èvòí/
sour word
'stammer' |
| c) /fí éví/
throw thing
'hit' | i) /sà ávòhà/
shoot a slap
'to slap' |
| d) /hò éhò/
hear ear
'be hear' | j) /vìè úròò/
receive language
'interpret' |
| e) /fí íhùè/
throw nose
'talk through nose' | k) /hò íhùè/
hear nose
'perceive smell' |
| f) /hùvè ósè/
good beauty
'be beautiful' | |

Although both verb and noun in the examples may occur as independent forms and may be separated in a sentence, it is necessary to recognize them as a single unit on

account of the idiomatic nature of the meaning. In addition, the verb incorporates the meaning of the noun to express an action, state, or process. In other words, in such combinations, the noun can no longer be seen as performing a nominal but rather a verbal function.

3.4 Deictics

In this section we seek to show that deictics in Emai exhibit a peculiar structure in which there is a regular correspondence between a unit of sound and a unit of meaning. "Deictics are words used to bring attention to things in the actual spatiotemporal context in which language is being used or in some way embedded in ongoing discourse" (Brown 1985: 283). It includes such categories as the personal pronouns, demonstratives, definite article, spatial and temporal adverbs, etc.

Deictics in Emai are derived from an underlying V_1 - CV_2 -(V_3) structure in which $-CV_2-$ is a deictic root and V_1 is a prefix which determines the class or type of deictic. Within each deictic class various types of semantic/

morphological information (e.g. number, concord, spatial orientation, etc) are expressed by varying the phonological feature composition of one or the other of the CV slots.

3.A.1 Deictic Categories in Emai

Emai has a list of deictic categories which includes personal pronouns, demonstrative pronouns (or adjectives), deictic adverbs (of place) and comparative adverbs. A comparison of these deictics reveals that they express basically three dimensions of existence which are perhaps founded on the locative expressions 'here', 'there', and 'yonder'. This assumption is supported by the localists who believe that spatial expressions are more basic and serve as structural templates for other expressions. 'This follows from the view held by psychologists that spatial organisation is of prime importance in human cognition' (Lyons 1977: 718).

3.A.1.1 Personal Pronouns

The category pronoun is commonly regarded as functioning as a substitute for a noun in discourse, but as Lyons (1977: 636-7) argues, its deictic function is more basic than its anaphoric function. Thus,

following Lyons' position, it would seem that a pronoun expresses basically two inseparable bits of information - deixis and reference. Deixis encompasses three deictic roles; first, second and third persons, although only the first and second persons participate in discourse. As for reference, it is singular or general, depending on whether an expression refers to an individual or classes of individuals. Besides this, a distinction is drawn between pronominal expressions that refer to some specific individual or groups of individuals (definite) and those that do not (indefinite). Finally, a language might draw a distinction between "reference to the individual whose speech, thoughts, or feelings are reported in a given context [logophoric reference], from reference to other individuals" (Clements 1975: 1). An adequate description of the pronominal system of a language entails a specification of the forms which are realised in these environments and where necessary a specification of their relationship.

Table 1: Emai Pronouns

	Object				Emphatic
	Subject	Direct	Indirect	Possessive	
1st person sg. pl.	í	vě	əvè	èvè	(í)věvè
	vá	vái	əvái	ávái	(í)vávái
2nd person sg. pl.	ù	(w)è	à	è(w)è	(ù)wèwè
	và	và	əvà	ávà	(í)vávà
3rd person sg. pl.	ò	òí	ái	òí	íjòí
	jà	íjái	íjái	íjái	íjái
Logophoric sg. pl.	jò	íjòí	íjòí	íjòí	-
	jà	íjái	íjái	íjái	-
Indefinite Pronoun	ə				

A look at the table above reveals some assymetries in pronominal structure. First, only subject and direct object environments have consonant initial forms. In the former environment the singular forms have V structure while the plural forms have CV structure. In the latter environment, 1st and 2nd person forms have a consonant initial structure while the 3rd person forms have vowel initial structures. This situation is caused by segment deletion affecting the pronominal category. For instance, the initial vowel of the emphatic pronoun is optional. Also, it will be observed that although /w/ is absent from the 2nd person subject, and optional in the object and possessive pronoun environments, it is obligatorily present in the emphatic environment. Similarly, although the 3rd person singular forms lack /j/ in subject, object and possessive environments, the consonant shows up in the emphatic environment. It is also obligatorily present in the plural 3rd person forms. It would seem as if the deletion has affected -CV in singular subject pronouns and V- in their plural direct object counterparts as well as in the 1st and 2nd persons (sg. and pl.) and 3rd person (sg.) direct object forms. Our suspicion is confirmed by the fact that the retained forms are

identical with some parts of the indirect object, possessive or even emphatic forms.

3.4.1.2 Demonstrative Pronoun (or Adjective), Place and Comparative Adverbs

Demonstrative pronouns, place adverbs, and comparative adverbs are deictics and they provide us with information in the deictic context. Specifically, demonstrative pronouns locate objects or individuals under reference, while deictic adverbs identify the location under reference. Emai draws a distinction between three demonstrative pronouns, three place adverbs and two comparative adverbs primarily on account of proximity to the deictic zero point. The demonstrative pronouns are further differentiated by number while place adverbs are cross-classified by the dimension of definiteness (see tables 2, 3 and 4 below).

Table 2: Demonstrative Pronouns

			<u>Emphatic</u>
A	sg.	ólà 'this'	ólálà 'this very one'
	pl	èlâ 'these'	élálâ 'these very ones'
B	sg.	ó(1)áí 'that'	
	pl	é(1)áí 'those'	
C	sg.	ólíí 'the other'	
	pl	élíí 'the others'	

Table 3: Adverb of Place

<u>Proximal</u>				<u>Emphatic</u>
A	definite	àlâ 'here'		álálâ 'this very place'
	indefinite	èlâ 'here'		élálâ "
B	definite	á(1)áí 'there'		-
	indefinite	é(1)áí 'there'		-
C	definite			-
	indefinite	èùò 'yonder'		-

Table A: Comparative Adverbs

A	ílá	'like this'
B	-	
C	íjó	'like the other'

Note that the data in tables 1-A are in phonemic transcription.

Before we set out to examine the morpho-phonological structure of deictics, it is important to restate that deictics express basically three dimensions of existence founded on the locative dimensions 'here', 'there', and 'yonder' (represented as A, B, C in the tables above). The personal pronoun category, however, differs in subtle ways in its realisation of these locative dimensions. The actual dimensions of existence in the personal pronoun category are 'here' (participation in discourse) and 'yonder' (non-participation in discourse). First and second persons participate in discourse and the distinction is a function of the roles which the participants in a discourse assume - either as speaker or listener. These roles are not static. This role distinction is realised as 'here' and 'there' locative dimensions. No distinction

is made as regards non-participation in discourse. It is very important that we make these points since our intention to match a unit of meaning with a unit of sound cannot be realised without our first understanding the semantic dimensions involved in all the categories.

3.0.2.0 The Phonological Structure of Deictics

Our aim here is to analyse the relationship between forms within the different subcategories and, where necessary, across the categories. Following this, a structure will be postulated for the deictic categories on the basis of which their segmental composition can be investigated. This will enable us bring out certain regularities and substantiate our claim of phono-semantic correspondence in deictic categories.

3.0.2.1 Segmental Composition of Deictics

The relationship between the deictics of Emal can best be revealed by looking at their segmental composition within the underlying $V_1 CV_2 (V_3)$ structure. Only a highly restricted set of segments can occur in each of these slots across the categories. Later we shall see

that each of these segments coincides with one or the other of the semantic dimensions expressed in the deictic categories. Below is a chart showing the segmental composition of deictics.

Table 5: The Segmental Composition of Deictics

		<u>Personal Pronouns</u>				
		<u>V₁ Possessive pronoun</u>	Others	C	V ₂	V ₃
A	sg	e	i	v	ē	∅
	pl	a	i	v	a	i
B	sg	e	u	w	e	∅
	pl	a	i	v	a	∅
C	sg	-	i	J	o	i
	pl	i	i	J	a	i
Logophoric:						
	sg	i	i	J	ō	i
	pl	i	i	J	ā	i
		<u>Demonstratives</u>				
A	sg		o	l	v̄	∅
	pl		e	l	ā	∅
B	sg		o	l	a	i
	pl		e	l	a	i
C	sg		o	l	o	i
	pl		e	l	o	i
		<u>Place Adverbs</u>				
A	definite		a	l	ā	∅
	indefinite		e	l	a	∅
B	definite		a	l	a	i
	indefinite		e	l	a	i
C	definite		-	-	-	-
	indefinite		e	v	o	∅

Personal Pronouns

<u>V₁ Possessive pronoun</u>	Others	C	V ₂	V ₃
---	--------	---	----------------	----------------

Comparative Adverb

A	ɪ	l	a	ɸ
B	-	-	-	-
C	ɪ	j	ɔ	ɸ

A breakdown of the table shows that only four consonants can fill the C-slot. The consonants are /j/, /l/, /v/ and /w/. /j/ has the widest distribution and occurs as the consonant of the third dimension (yonder) across all the categories except in the demonstrative pronoun category where /l/ occurs and the 3rd dimension place adverb where /v/ shows up. /l/ is restricted to demonstratives and adverbial deictics. It occurs in the 1st and 2nd dimensions of these categories. /v/ is the consonant of the first person environment of the personal pronoun. Although it is found occurring also in the second person plural environment, its occurrence there may have been historically conditioned. In Edo (Bini) (cf Amayo 1976) and Esan /w/ is found to occur

in this environment. /w/ occurs in the second person singular environment in Emai.

Table 6: A breakdown of the distribution of Consonants in Deictics

Consonant	Personal	Adverbs		Demonstrative
	pronoun	Comparative	Place	Pronoun
A	v	1	1	1
B	w ¹	-	1	1
C	j	j	v	1

Only three vowel types are allowed in the V_2 -slot. They are /ɛ/ /ɛ̃/, /a/ /ã/, /ɔ/ /ɔ̃/. /a/² occurs as the plural vowel in the personal pronouns; it is also the indefinite pronoun as well as the vowel realised in the first and second dimensions in demonstrative pronoun and place and comparative adverbs. /ɔ/ occurs as the third person singular vowel in pronouns and as the third dimension vowel in demonstratives, place and comparative adverbs. /ɛ/ is the vowel of the first and second person

1 /w/ is retained as the 2nd person consonant because of the possibility that /v/ in the 2nd person plural position is historically conditioned. In Edo (Bini) Esan (both NCE) /w/ is consistently found as the 2nd person consonant.

2 The oral forms are used here to represent the pair.

singular pronoun environment. Below is a breakdown of the distribution of vowels in V_2 position.

Table 7: A breakdown of distribution of vowels

V_2	Pronoun		Adverbs		Demonstrative
	sg	pl			
A	ē	ā	a	ā	ā
B	e	a	-	a	ā
C	o	ā	o	o	o
Indefinite Pronoun	a				

Only /i/ occurs as the $-V_3$ vowel across all the categories. It is however restricted to the second and third dimensions. It also occurs in the first person plural object environment although completely absent from the second person pronoun, comparative adverb and third dimension demonstrative environments.

In the V_1 position /i/ occurs in the personal pronouns with the exception of /u/ in the second person singular environment. The presence of /u/ rather than

/l/ before /w/ may be due to labial assimilation of the latter sound in that environment. First and second person possessive pronouns have V_1 which are identical with V_2 . Total vowel assimilation may have occurred in these environments.

Demonstratives alternate o-/e- in V_1 position to signify singular and plural numbers whereas place adverb alternates a-/e- to signify definiteness (singularity) and fuzziness (or plurality) of location. /l/ occupies V_1 slot in comparative adverbs.

3.1.2.2 Phono-Semantic Correspondence

Comparing the demonstrative pronoun, place and comparative adverbs, one finds that they are only differentiated by their V_1 - (see Tables 2-4). V_1 is o-/e- for demonstratives, a-/e- for place adverbs and i- for comparative adverb. Other elements are the same except in the third dimension where there is a variation in the c- element which is /l/ for demonstrative, /v/ for place adverb and /j/ for comparative adverb. Also V_2 is /o-/ for the demonstrative pronoun and comparative adverb but /a/ for the place adverb.

o-/e- in demonstrative pronouns mark singular and

plural number, a-/e- in place adverb marks definite and indefinite location and i- is the comparative morpheme. The V_1 of demonstrative pronouns is actually concord prefixes attached to qualifiers. The possessive pronoun also has its initial vowels functioning as concord prefixes. Like other qualifiers, it loses this vowel when it occurs in construction with head nouns.

The $-CV_2-$ is a deictic root in which -C- marks deixis (encompassing three deictic roles, 1st, 2nd and 3rd persons in personal pronouns). V_2 marks reference (anaphoric in pronouns). Differences in person and reference are marked by varying the segmental composition of $-CV_2-$, that of the C-slot for the former and V_2 -slot for the latter. /l/ is the deictic consonant, occurring only in environments where deixis does not involve person. The deictic consonant is realised as /v/, /w/ and /j/ in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd persons pronoun environments (see Table 6).

The occurrence of /j/ in the third dimension comparative adverb (i_jó 'like that') may be due to some semantic feature (which ties it to the 3rd person personal pronoun) which we have been unable to determine.

Reference is marked by /a/. Earlier on we indicated that /a/ is found in V_2 position across all the deictic categories (i.e. in plural environments of personal pronouns, 1st and 2nd dimensions of demonstratives and deictic adverbs) except in the 3rd dimensions where /o/ consistently occurs, and in the 1st and 2nd persons singular environments where /e/ occurs (see table 5 above). Also, the indefinite pronoun is /a/. This pronoun in Emai has a plural connotation. In fact, the plural sense seems to be an inherent component of indefiniteness. Thus, all that is happening here is that we have an indefinite reference form /a/ which manifests the plural meaning in pronoun environment where number distinction is crucial (or not marked in other ways). It simply marks reference in other environments where it would be inappropriate to talk about number (e.g. comparative adverb and adverb of place), or where number is marked by other means (e.g. demonstrative pronouns). In the marked singular environment /e/ is realised as 1st and 2nd persons singular form while /o/ simply occurs across all the deictic categories marking absence from a discourse situation (i.e. marking 3rd dimension or yonder), and

picking up a singular meaning in personal pronoun environment.

It would be observed that the final close vowel ($-V_3$) noticed in some object pronouns is also present in the 2nd and 3rd dimensions in demonstratives and place adverbs. We conclude that this sound in the scheme marks distance from the deictic zero point. Translated into the personal pronoun category, it marks structural distance. Its absence from the 2nd person sg/pl and 1st person sg environments is probably due to the fact that it is just being extended to personal pronouns.

We have already specified the semantic content of V_1 in demonstratives, adverbs of place, comparative adverbs and possessive pronouns (see section 3.2.3 paragraphs one and two). We may as well note that V_1 (i.e. /i/ in other personal pronouns) mark the personal pronoun class. This falls in line with the general situation in the language where initial vowels of nominals are historical class markers and those of modifiers are concord prefixes.

To conclude, we postulate the following deictic structure for Emai.

Fig. 26

The deictic is represented as a word branching into a deixis plus reference root, a class/concord/locative/comparative prefix, and an optional proximity suffix. Variation in reference type (i.e. singular vs plural) and deixis (person) is expressed in terms of variation of the phonemic content of the CV skeleta.

3.5 Modifiers

3.5.1 The category of modifiers is one which embraces numerals, quantifiers, demonstratives, possessive pronouns, determiner, augmentative and diminutive markers, etc. They all share one important morphological characteristic. Like the noun, they all have vowel initial structures and this vowel (except in numerals) marks concord with the head nominal in a noun phrase.

Modifiers have a minimal bisyllabic and maximal trisyllabic structure. Below we present some examples of modifiers showing their alternating concordial vowels.

	<u>sg</u>	<u>pl</u>
13 a)	úvì	í-
	'diminutive	
b)	údù	í-
	'augmentative	
c)	úkpà	í-
	'individuator'	
d)	ólì	é-
	'definite article'	
e)	ósò	é-
	'a certain...'	'some'

features rather than class features are associated with this vowel.

3.5.2. Adjunctives

Adjunctives are a separate class of modifiers in Emai. They are words which function as adjectives and/or adverbs (Samarin 1967, cf Dixon 1977: 5). The existence of this class of words in Emai was first brought to our attention by R. Schaefer (personal communication).

Adjunctives in Emai have bisyllabic structure (when unreduplicated) and consistently carry high tones.

Below are a few examples:

- | | | |
|-------------------|---------|---------------------------|
| 1 ^a a) | /gbíkí/ | 'stocky' (Adjective) |
| b) | /dúgbú/ | 'pod-like' (Adjective) |
| c) | /kpúdú/ | 'pellet-like' (Adjective) |
| d) | /lógó/ | 'tall and thin' (Adverb) |

- e) /kpótótó/ 'heavy-like iron' (Adverb)
 f) /gbóó/ 'long and straight' (Adverb)

3.6 Construction Markers

Emai has the following construction markers: ési/ísi 'possessive associative marker', xi 'complement marker', òlì 'descriptive associative marker'/relative introducer/focus marker, vî 'locativizer', etc. Aspect markers are not included in the list above because we are yet to determine the exact number and range of information which they convey.

The possessive associative marker has é- or í- in the initial position depending on whether the preceding noun is a place noun or not. Below are some examples:

- 15 a) iwè ési ògìè
 home AM king
 'king's home'
- b) èvòò ési ófè
 town AM rat
 'rat's town'
- c) ébè ísi éwè
 leaf/book AM goat
 'goat's leaf/book'

- d) *ibè fai òhí*
 band AM name of person
 'Oli's band'

The same form *ólí* is postulated as the relative introducer, descriptive associative marker and focus marker (see appendix for discussions of these constructions). *ólí* is actually a definite article in Emai which is utilised to mark the constructions cited above. It is no coincidence that these constructions utilise this form. One would be missing an obvious generalisation if one postulated different morphemes in each instance of the occurrence of the form instead of recognizing a single morphemic form which is used in the different constructions. Looking at the basic semantic nature of these constructions one would find a similarity in them which may explain the presence of the *ólí* form in all of them. There is the idea of 'definiteness' contained in all of these constructions which shows up as some form of restriction on the constructions. The definite article cannot modify a proper noun in normal usage because of the fact that

proper nouns are inherently [+definite]. In a discourse context, however, the use of a definite article with a proper noun presupposes prior information about the individual represented by the proper noun. Also, a proper noun cannot serve as the head of a relative clause or descriptive associative construction for the same reason, as seen in examples 15 below:

15 a)* ólì òhíò
 the name of person
 'the Òhíò'

b)* òhíò ólì ògiè
 'Òhíò the king'

c)* òhíò ólì ń gbé ófè lá `lé
 Òhíò who RP kill rat run away
 'Òhíò, who killed a rat, ran away'

The descriptive qualifier and relative clause perform a definitive function by identifying a specific referent within a class of possible referents. Although this definitive feature also occurs in the focus construction, it is in a slightly different sense and so, the restriction does not apply.

- d) òhíò (lí) ǒ gbé ǒfè
 " Def RP kill rat
 'it is Ohíò who killed a rat'

/lí/ is not a focus marker; it merely makes definite the subject, or verb under focus. When absent, focus is still retained but this definitive meaning (it is ...) is lost. In concluding, one would like to mention that at the surface level, the initial vowel of ǒlí is not realised except when it occurs as definite article. The absence of this vowel in descriptive associative and relative constructions is due to its deletion. We shall not discuss other construction markers listed above because there is really nothing interesting about them.

3.7 Number Formation

For the purposes of number formation, Emai vowels can be divided into two sets - a singular and a plural set. The singular set is made up of the following vowels: /e-/, /o-/, /u-/, /ɔ-/ and /a-/. The plural set is made up of /i-/ and /e-/. Plurality is marked by replacing one or the other of the singular vowel

prefixes with a plural prefix. Below are a few examples:

	<u>sg</u>		<u>pl</u>
16 a)	/ófè/	'rat'	é-
b)	/órá/	'tree'	é-
c)	/óuìò/	'relative'	f-
d)	/óhùà/	'hunter'	f-
e)	/òkposò/	'woman'	i-
f)	/óyòóyò/	'sheep'	f-
g)	/óbò/	'native doctor'	é-
h)	/shà/	'wife'	é-
i)	/ódò/	'husband'	é-
j)	/sósò/	'chicken'	é-
k)	/sègiè/	'chief'	f-
l)	/spià/	'matchet'	f-
m)	/éwè/	'goat'	é-
n)	/éuèlá/	'cow'	f-
o)	/áxè/	'pot'	é-
p)	/áwà/	'dog'	f-
q)	/ávéi/	'weaverbird'	f-

	<u>sg</u>		<u>pl</u>
r)	/áfiávi/	'bird'	f-
s)	/úkpù/	'cloth'	f-
t)	/úí/	'rope'	f-
u)	/ùgf/	'basket'	i-
v)	/úddò/	'stone'	f-
w)	/ú`zó/	'antelope'	f-
x)	/ú`gò/	'beetle'	f-

Elugbe (1986: 60) notes that "in the typical Edoid language, singular/plural prefix changes are phonologically determined and do not indicate any noun class semantic demarcation". He notes, however, the existence of a curious plural form in /a-/ which seems to have some kind of semantic content referred to as (paired) body parts (including 'teeth'). This plural form also occurs in Emai in such paired body parts as hands and legs.

	<u>sg</u>		<u>pl</u>
17 a)	òè	'leg'	àwè 'legs'
b)	óbò	'hand'	ábò 'hands'

Other paired body parts like 'eyes' and teeth have lost the singular/plural distinction in Emai.

- c) èò 'eye'
àkò 'teeth'

In Emai, nouns with the singular prefix /u-/ take the /i-/ plural form without exception. This is a case of phonological conditioning.

3.8 Lexicalisation

This subsection focusses on the lexicalisation or word formation processes. Lexicalisation processes can involve a simple change of lexical categories through affixation. It also involves the derivation of complex words via compounding, and phrase reduction. A discussion of lexicalisation processes should be preceded by a definition of the 'word' if we are to know exactly what phenomena qualify as lexicalisation processes. Any such definition of the word must provide us with a direct or indirect means of formally distinguishing complex words from their phrasal copies. Otherwise, one stands the risk of mistakenly including in the lexicon phrasal materials. Phrases like complex lexical

items (compounds) are made up of lexical sequences. Phrases and compounds are sometimes not formally distinguished and where they are formally distinguished, the distinction may not be readily obvious. For instance, the process of compounding in English has constituted a problem as a result of this formal ambiguity (Jespersen 1942). In Emai, one has to be able to determine when a lexical sequence constitutes an associative noun phrase (i.e. $N_1 + N_2$) or a word. Apart from the need to observe the pattern of lexicalisation, it has a crucial implication for the orthography of the language because it is necessary for one to know the morphological relationship between two words to determine if they should be separated in the orthography or not.

Although a morphological word is best seen as a semantic unit, a definition based on purely semantic considerations is bound to run into problems with complex words. We define the word simply as an atomic unit which constitutes the unit of lexical insertion. Atomicity is defined primarily in formal syntactic terms. Thus, although a word may have internal

structure, its components cannot be separated by any syntactic movement rules (Aronoff 1976). Consequently, a word admits of no medial variables.

3.8.1.1 Nominalisation

The morphology of Emai is centred around processes of nominalisation. Nominalisation processes are processes which derive nominals from other lexical categories or phrasal entities. There are basically two types of nominalisation in Emai. These are the gerundive and non-gerundive nominalisations.

3.8.1.1.1 Gerundive Nominalisation

Gerundivisation is a process which turns verbs into gerunds. It is marked by the affixation of a discontinuous morpheme /ú-ví/ as well as a high tone on the third syllable of a gerundive nominal. Below are some examples:

- | | | | | | |
|-------|------|---------------|-----|-----------------------|------------|
| 18 a) | /á/ | 'run' | --> | [úlà [́] mí] | 'running' |
| b) | /ṣ/ | 'drink water' | --> | [úṣ [́] mí] | 'drinking' |
| c) | /è/ | 'eat' | --> | [úè [́] mí] | 'eating' |
| d) | /fi/ | 'throw' | --> | [úfì [́] mí] | 'throwing' |

- e) /tòtò/ 'strong' --> [útòtó!mĩ́] 'strength'
 f) /vàè/ 'red' --> [úvàé!mĩ́] 'redness'
 g) /gbàlò/ 'big' --> [úgbàlò!mĩ́] 'bigness'

It would be observed that the /-vĩ/ suffixal part of the gerundive morpheme is realised phonetically as [-mĩ́] in line with the rule of nasalisation in Emai.

The gerundive morpheme in Emai is very close to the PE gerundive morpheme represented as U...Amhr by Elugbe (1984). 'A' (for ə or a) represents a vowel between the verb stem and the nasal. In Emai, the only indication that such vowel might have existed in that position is the downstepping of the low tone on [-mĩ́] in four-syllable gerunds. However, this could also have been due to the high tone assigned to the third syllable of the gerund which sets a low tone on the vowel floating. What perhaps offers strong evidence for the occurrence of a vowel in that position comes from Dẹgẹma and Uvbiẹ (see Elugbe 1984). "Dẹgẹma has a vowel there in environments after a stem final consonant; Uvbiẹ has it all the time ... In Dẹgẹma, it is A, realised as ə or a. In Uvbiẹ and other SWE languages, it is o or ɔ". The occurrence of downstep

phenomenon in gerunds in Edo (Bini) and Ora (both NCE) languages further confirms Elugbe's postulation of a V-nasal-V structure for the gerundive affix.

		<u>Edo</u>	<u>Ora</u>
19 a)	bi 'open'	ùbí!pè	-
	b) de 'fall'	ùdé!pè	ídé!mí
	c) ds 'buy'	ùdé!pè	ídé!mí
	d) bí	-	íbí!mí

Elugbe (1984: 87) raises the possibility of functionally separating the prefix from the suffix. According to him "since PE is assumed to have employed only prefixes to mark noun classes, the possibility that the class marking U- prefix was originally different from the suffix ...Amhi cannot be discarded. In that case, the function of Amhi would probably have been to derive noun stems from verb stems. Thus while Amhi was used after the verb stem to de-verbalize it, U- was prefixed to the stem to mark it for a particular class". We agree with Elugbe in functionally separating the prefix and suffix. There are actually examples where U- is prefixed to verb stems and in such cases this prefix identifies the result of the action or

	<u>Noun Prefix</u>	<u>V</u>		
20 a)	ò -	xòò 'be-bad'	-->	òxòò 'badness'
b)	ó -	hòò 'be dizzy'	-->	óhòó 'dizziness'
c)	è -	xùsvì 'thank'	-->	èxwémì 'thanks'
d)	é -	kpà 'to vomit'	-->	ékpà 'vomit'
e)	è -	fè 'be rich'	-->	éfè 'riches'
f)	é -	kòò 'enclose'	-->	ékoó 'nest/parcel'
g)	à -	si 'inhale, pull'	-->	ásí 'snuff'
h)	á -	èè 'know'	-->	áèè 'sign, mark'
i)	ó -	rèè 'to visit'	-->	ó!ré 'visitor, stranger'
j)	ò -	xòò 'be bad'	-->	òxòó 'bad act, sin'
k)	ù -	kòkò 'gather, contain'	-->	ùkòkò 'container, vagina'

process of doing (see non-gerundive nominalisation, 38.1.2). Thus, the gerundiveness is the result of the suffixation of Amhr. The addition of U- follows the process of deverbalization which requires that the resultant noun be allocated to a class.

Elugbe again raises the possibility of 'A' serving as concord element. We have no way of confirming this. But it looks unlikely that a concord element would occur in that position. Generally, in Edoïd languages, the concord element occurs as the initial vowel of a qualifier. Apart from the fact that the gerund is not a qualifier, one cannot easily discern the kind of concord which would be expressed in the gerund - certainly not number. It is probably just a linker connecting both members of the discontinuous gerundive morpheme.

3.84.2 Non-Gerundive Nominalisation

In Emai nouns can be derived by prefixing one or the other of the seven oral vowels to a verb or verb phrase. Below are examples:

	<u>Noun prefix</u>		<u>V</u>		
1)	ú -		gbà 'tie'	-->	úgbà 'fence'

	<u>Noun prefix</u>			<u>VP</u>	
21 a)	ò -		è + gbé eat excessive	-->	òègbé 'overfeeding'
b)	ó -		sì + ré pull arrive	-->	ósiré 'charm for attracting customers'
c)	à -		là + ífò run sweat	-->	àlòfò 'manual fan'
d)	á -		wù + èhè catch fish	-->	áwéhè 'fish trap'
e)	ò -		fò + ré cold arrive	-->	òfòré 'dampness'
f)	ù -		kpè + ábò wash hand	-->	ùkpàbò 'bowl for washing hands'
g)	ú -		kpè + àkò wash teeth	-->	ùkpàkò 'chewstick'
h)	ì -		rè + só 'cause to end'	-->	ìrèsó 'end of time'

Noun prefix

1)	f	-	hǎà	+	èò	-->	fnjèò
			cut		face		'stinginess'

From the examples above we can observe that /i-/ does not nominalise a verb in Emai. Similarly, /e-/ and /o-/ do not nominalise verb phrases.

The segmental composition of a prefix coincides with certain meanings in Emai. We shall now attempt to postulate the semantic dimensions which the different vowel prefixes represent.

3.8.1.3 Meaning of Vowel Prefixes in Nominalisation

One can most generally identify the prefixes as having the following semantic implications.

/u-/, The prefix is here analysed as an instrument prefix. Instrument is understood in a loose sense as some object or condition which plays a role in bringing a process about but which is not the motivating force, the cause or instigator. This meaning comes out clearly in verb phrase nominalisation where objects are involved in the process.

- 22 a) $\acute{u}$ - kpè + àkò --> ùkpàkò
 np wash teeth 'chewstick'
- b) $\grave{u}$ - kpè + ábò --> ùkpàbò
 np wash hands 'bowl for washing hands'
- c) $\grave{u}$ - gbè + éwè --> ùgbàwè
 np kill goat 'plague/disease that kills goats'
- d) $\grave{u}$ - dèlò + óbò --> ùdelòbò
 np turn hand 'implement for marshing and stirring food'

However, with verb stems alone, the prefix identifies or expresses the result of the action of doing.

- e) $\acute{u}$ - xùèè --> ùxwèè
 np 'to insult' 'insult'
- f) $\acute{u}$ - là --> ùlà
 np run 'race'
- g) $\grave{u}$ - ròò --> ùròò
 np quarrel 'a quarrel'

/i-/, This is the prefix that derives abstract nouns from verbs and verb phrases. Examples are:

- 23 a) i - hía bá --> ihjábá
 np cut add 'blessing'

- b) i - là ófě́ --> ilòfě́
 np run fear 'fear'
 'be afraid'
- c) í - xòò èhài --> íxòèhài
 np bad forehead 'ill-luck'
 'be lucky'
- d) í - hùvè èhài --> íhùmèhài
 np good forehead 'good luck'
 'be lucky'

/ɔ-/ and /a-/

These are two prefixes which are not very different from each other. However, while /ɔ-/ has a definite reference which can be translated as 'something/'somebody', /a-/ has an indefinite or generic reference translatable as anything/anybody.

- 24 a) ɔ - xòvè --> ɔxòmè
 np be sick 'sick person'
- b) ɔ - kpè àò --> ɔkpàò
 np be front 'first person, thing'
- c) à - yài --> àyáí
 np be costly 'costly thing'

- d) ɔ̌ - tòhià --> òtòhjá
 np hot 'hot climate'
- e) á - tàlò --> átàlò
 np talk repeatedly 'any talkative person'
- f) á - wù èhě --> ágwěhě
 np catch fish 'any fish trap'
- g) à - si --> àsí
 np inhale, pull 'anything sniffed, inhaled'
- h) á - s̄s̄ --> ás̄s̄
 np know 'sign, mark'

/o-/ and /e-/

We have been unable to draw a distinction between these two prefixes. The relationship between the derivand and operand (for both) is 'resultative' - in which case, when everything else is filtered out, the prefixes can be said to express the result of the action, process or state expressed by the verb. Examples are presented below:

- 25 a) é - tà --> étà
 np talk 'talk'
- b) é - kpà --> ékpà
 np vomit 'vomit'
- c) é - viè --> évjè
 np cry 'crying'
- d) é - uèuè --> émèné
 np be mad 'madness'
- e) ó - hòò --> óhòó
 np dizzy 'dizziness'
- f) ò - kpòkpò --> òkpòkpò
 np worry 'worrying'
- g) ò - yèè --> òyèè
 np flirt 'flirtation'
- h) ò - xòò --> òxòò
 np be bad 'badness'

/e-/ occurs in only a few examples. We cannot make any generalizations as regards its meaning.

- 26 a) è - hiò --> èhjò
 np 'be arrogant' 'arrogance'
- b) è - bò --> èbò
 np 'to divine' 'shrine'

- c) è - hi --> èhi
 np 'be destined'

3.8.2 Compounding

A compound word is one whose stem is formed by combining two or more stems (with or without morphological modification) (Lyons 1977: 535). The term compound is often used in a loose sense to refer to phrasal compounds (i.e. lexical sequences) and lexicalised compounds. The distinction between the two is not one that can easily be drawn.

Jerspersen (1942, cf. Awoyale 1974) postulates a lexical combination as a compound word if the meaning of the whole cannot be logically deduced from the meaning of the elements separately. As he rightly observed, it is difficult to find a satisfactory classification of all logical relations that may be encountered in compounds. Wolf (1984: 61), still attempting to define the compound word semantically, states that "lexicalised compounds may be morphologically analysable, they may even be semantically compositional but they have a fixed sense". The problem with this definition is that it is difficult to specify the point at which an

expression has acquired a fixed sense. Our strategy for identifying a compound word follows from our definition of the 'word' as an atomic unit. Thus, any lexical combination that does not exhibit this property cannot qualify as a compound word. If a lexical combination can be separated by movement rules, or if one member of the sequence can be pronominalised, such^a combination cannot qualify as a compound word. Atomicity does not only involve structural immobility, it also has some semantic implications. Thus, a movement of a member of a compound word must either render the construction semantically anomalous or destroy the lexical meaning expressed by the compound. For example, the separation of *émédó* 'sweet potato' into its components *éṁá ísì èdó* 'yam of Edo' renders the structure anomalous.

There are only compound nouns in Emai and it is our belief that they are all derived from the associative construction. Our claim is semantically and phonologically substantiated. Compounding involves two stages illustrated below:

Fig. 28 $[_{NP} N_1 - \text{isi} - N_2 NP] \rangle [_{NP} N_1 \emptyset N_2 NP] \rangle [_{N} N_1 + N_2 N]$
 alienable inalienable compound
 associative associative noun
 construction construction

In other words, underlying all compound nouns in Emai is the alienable associative phrase. To arrive at the compound noun, the alienable phrase is first converted into the inalienable phrase through a deletion of the associative marker, and through a process of 'petrification' (Lyons 1977), the alienable associative phrase acquires a specialised or fixed meaning. Below in examples (27) are compound words and their derivations. Examples (28) contain phrasal sequence. The examples in (27) exhibit atomic structure whereas examples in (28) do not.

	by VE.&NE.		by AM deletion	
27 a)	ámé! ó 'cowrie, coin money'	<	ámé é!yó	< àuè (ísi) é'yó water of money
b)	ékóà 'room'	<	ékéí óà	< ékēi (ísi) óà belly of house
c)	ódàfè 'head of household'	<	ódò àfè	< ódò (ísi) àfè husband of home

- | | | | | | |
|----|---------------------|---|-------------------|---|-----------------------|
| | by V.E. and
N.E. | | by AM
deletion | | |
| d) | áfúłzé | < | áfě úłzé | < | áfě (ísi) ú`zé |
| | 'name of a
town' | | | | home of axe |
| e) | úziní | < | úzá iní | < | úzà (fisi) ilí |
| | 'tse-
tsefly' | | | | tsetsefly of elephant |

- | | | | | | |
|-------|--------------------------|---|-------------------|---|-------------------|
| | by V.E. | | by AM
deletion | | |
| 28 a) | éáméwè | < | éámí éwè | < | éáví ísi éwè |
| | 'goat meat' | | | | meat of goat |
| b) | óruńdí | < | órà údí | < | órà ísi údí |
| | 'palmtree' | | | | tree of palm |
| c) | épedà | < | épé édá | < | éjè ísi édá |
| | 'eel' | | | | snake of river |
| d) | ébéfó | < | ébé éfó | < | ébé ísi éfó |
| | 'vegetable
leaf' | | | | leaf of vegetable |
| e) | ógahè | < | ógó àhé | < | ógó ísi àhé |
| | 'bottle of
local gum' | | | | bottle of gum |

It will be observed that both the compound words and the phrasal compounds are logically derivable from underlying associative constructions. The only difference

is that the compound words have a specialised sense as well as an atomic structure.

Apart from the logical relation between the underlying associative phrases and their compound derivations, tonal evidence supports our derivation. It would be observed in the examples above, (27) and (28), that N_1 always has high tones in both the compound nouns and phrases. This is because the associative construction is characterised by the spreading of the initial high tone of the associative marker onto low tone slots of the preceding noun. Let us now examine a sample derivation of (27a) and (28a):

	AM high tone spread		AM deletion and V.E.		
29 a)	àwè ísì é'Yó	-->	ámé ísì é!Yó	-->	ámé!Yó
	L L H L HL H		H H H L HL!H		H H! H
b)	éàwí ísì éwè	-->	éámí ísì éwè	-->	éáméwè
	HL L H L H L		HH H H L H L		HH H L

If high tone spread, a strictly phrasal rule, is found affecting a supposedly lexical entity, it means that the entity is either not lexical or, if lexical, is phrasally derived.

Phrases and compound words are distinguished phonologically in Emai by the application of the 'Nasality Erasure' rule in the latter. The rule erases the nasality of the final vowel of N_1 following compounding. Contrasting examples are contained in examples (27a-d) and (28a-c). Nasality Erasure also applies in full morpheme reduplication.

Residue

Our view of a compound as an atomic unit seems challenged by the incidence of split verbs and the class of idiomatic verbs which we noted in section (3.3.3). Only four split verbs occur in the language. They are $m\grave{i}-d\acute{a}$ 'to swallow', $f\grave{a}-k\acute{u}n\acute{o}$ 'embrace', $g\grave{a}-z\acute{e}$ 'meet' and $f\grave{a}n-z\acute{e}$ 'to cross'. It is our belief that these so-called split verbs are derived from serial verbs that have lost their independent identities. For one reason the split verbs share the same tonal structure as serial verbs. Whereas verbs in Emai have low tones, serial verbs have low tone on the first verb and high tone on the second verb when they are rendered outside of construction. Below are examples:

30 a) sà - láló
fetch lick

b) gbè - xíé
kill sell

c) xù - wú
close catch

d) dè - áá
fall seal

Secondly, there is evidence that certain members of the serial verbs are losing their independent identities. In the examples below, the underlined members of the series can no longer occur alone.

31 a) là - oáá
run ?
'seek refuge'

b) dò - wú
? take
'steal'

c) gà - wú
? take
'to grip'

d) dá - múzá
 ? stop
 'stand up'

e) fi - gáló
 throw ?
 'entangle'

Thus, where both members of a serial verb lose their independent identities they become split verbs.

The 'idiomatic verbs' have a verb plus noun structure. The verb incorporates the meaning of the noun to express the verbal meaning. We present a few examples below:

32 a) kpá - úrú
 peel neck
 'have goitre'

b) ji - éhò
 extract ear
 'be deaf'

c) rú - èò
 roost face
 'be blind'

d) là - ófè
 run fear
 'be afraid'

The split verbs, the serial verbs with one member decomposed and these idiomatic verbs have no atomic structure yet on the semantic front there is the need to see them as some kind of word. We do not need to modify our definition of the compound word here, rather we should recognize them as phrasal verbs. The fact that they are not atomic is caused by the fact that they have not been fully lexicalised.

3.8.3 Descriptive Associative Noun Phrase Reduction

Descriptive associative noun phrase reduction involves essentially the same process as compounding. It involves the lexicalisation of a descriptive noun phrase. Like other words, they exhibit an atomic structure. This, in addition to their tonal structure, differentiates them from their phrasal counterparts. Examples (33) below show the derived words while examples (34) show the phrases.

			N ₁	Def.	N ₂
33 a)	òrèlêdé	<	óré	íli	édé
	'ancestors'		makes	which	?

		N ₁	Def.		N ₂
b)	idèlôfá 'crayfish'	< idé lobster	ólí 3 which scm		fá white
c)	ininámè 'hippopotamus'	< flí elephant	ólí which		àvè water
d)	àwàlùhòbò 'hyena'	< áwà dog	ólí which		ùhòbò urhobo
e)	édjólíkè 'aged people'	< édíò elders	éíí which		iké ?
f)	óbòlòkpòsò 'witch'	< óbò doctor	ólí which		òkpòsò woman

*òkpòsò
adult female
as opposed to
young female*

	N ₁	Def.	N ₂		
34 a)	ófè rat	ólí which	òxúá 'big	-->	ófèlòxwá 'giant rat'
b)	àláví swallow	ólí which	óbò doctor	-->	ánámí lóbò 'a species of swallow'
c)	óvívié cobra	ólí which	òkpà cock	-->	óvívié lòkpà 'crested cobra'
d)	àrè woodpecker	ólí which	Igbégbè velvet	-->	áréligbégbè 'a species of woodpecker'

Quite apart from the atomicity exhibited by the descriptive words both forms are differentiated tonally. The descriptive words have low tones on the first member of the underlying phrase. The initial vowel of N_2 has a High-falling tone. The descriptive phrase on the other hand has high tones on N_1 (with a few phonologically explainable exceptions). This high tone is created by the spreading of the high tone of the definite morpheme (i.e. 611)

3.84 Reduplication

One can identify two views of reduplication. The first view sees reduplication as a process of 'binary fission' while the second view sees it as an affixation process. Coming under the first view are those works that (implicitly or explicitly) view reduplication as a process of repetition (McCarthy 1979, 1981). The strongest position within this disposition is held by those who see reduplication as a transformational process (see Lieber 1981).

The second view of reduplication is held by Marantz (1982). He defines reduplication most generally

as a process relating a base form of a morpheme or stem to a derived form that may be analysed as being constructed from the base via affixation of phonemic material which is necessarily identical in whole or in part to the phonemic content of the base form.

It is this latter view of reduplication that we are adopting in this study. This is because it will enable us to express the correct generalisation about reduplication as a morphological process. All morphological processes are essentially meaning-based processes which involve the combination of two or more morphemes in different functional relations (e.g. stem + formative). Defining reduplication simply as a process of repetition or 'fission' ignores this fact about morphology. It reduces reduplication to a mere formal strategy rather than the morphological process which it is.

Reduplication may be total or partial depending on whether all the phonemic materials of the stem or part of it are affixed. Emai displays both types to signify different meanings. Partial reduplication is aggregative while total reduplication is intensive/emphatic in nouns,

verbs, adverbs, and pronouns but distributive in numerals and adjunctives. Below we present examples of both types of reduplication applying across various lexical categories.

	<u>Noun</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>Partial</u>
35 a)	ítíhíà 'buttock'	-	ítítíhíà 'both buttocks'
b)	ìkpòsò 'women'	ìkpósìkpósó 'only-women'	ìkpíkpósó 'all women'
c)	ídò 'stones'	ídídò 'only stone'	-
d)	ímòhè 'men'	ímòhímòhè 'only men'	ímímòhè 'all men'
e)	èwáí 'wisdom'	èwéwáí 'wisely'	-
f)	ékè 'sand'	ékèké 'only sand'	-

	<u>Pronoun</u>	<u>Total (emphatic)</u>
36 a)	mě 'me'	mēmē
b)	wè 'you(sg)'	wèwè
c)	và 'you(pl)'	vàvà
d)	mǎǐ 'us/we'	mǎmǎǐ

	<u>Adverb</u>	<u>Total</u>
37 a)	éyè 'time'	élyéyè 'always'
b)	édè 'day'	édédédè 'daily'
c)	àgàlà 'on the spot'	àgàlàgàlà 'right away'
d)	isòkpá 'once'	isòkpáísòkpá 'at once'

	<u>Verbs</u>	<u>Total</u>
38 a)	há 'press'	háhá 'crush'
b)	xù 'chase'	xùxù chase (intensive)
c)	ně suckle	ŋěŋě suckle (intensive)
d)	búmě 'to dust'	búměbúmě 'be haggard'
e)	mátá 'be sticky'	mátámátá 'be very sticky'
f)	sěně 'be ugly'	sěněsěně 'be very ugly'
g)	gǒŋǒ 'be bent'	gǒŋǒgǒŋǒ 'be crooked'

Examples (d-g) do not simply involve intensification. Reduplication in these examples also involve a change from the verb category to the adjective category. This is marked formally by the high tone on the duplicate.

	<u>Adjunctives</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>Partial</u>
h)	kéré 'small'	kérékééré 'many small...'	kékéré 'all small'
i)	héyé 'be light'	héyéhéyé 'many light...'	héhéyé 'all light'
j)	gbíkí 'be stocky'	gbíkígbíkí 'many stocky...'	gbígbíkí 'all very stocky'
k)	kpéké 'be petite'	kpékékpéké 'many petite...'	kpékpéké 'all petite'
l)	kpúdú 'be pelletlike'	kpúdúkpúdú 'many pellet- like ...'	kpúkpúdú 'all pelletlike'
m)	dúgbú 'podlike'	dúgbúdúgbú 'many podlike...'	dúdúgbú 'all podlike'

Numerals

39 a)	èvá 'two'	èvé [^] vá 'two by two'	èvév [^] á 'both'
b)	éélè 'four'	éélèéélè 'four by four'	èlèéélè 'all four'
c)	isí 'nine'	isí [^] isí 'nine by nine'	isisí 'all nine'
d)	igbé 'ten'	igbígbé 'ten by ten'	igbigbé 'all ten'

3.8.4.1 Formal Accounts of Reduplication Marantz 1982

Marantz (1982) is a modification of McCarthy (1979, 1981) which is an autosegmental version of the traditional view of reduplication as a process of repetition. The only other significant difference between McCarthy (1979, 1981) and Marantz (1982) relates to the nature of reduplicated units. While McCarthy allows only constituents (e.g. syllable, foot, morpheme, etc.) to undergo reduplication, Marantz allows in addition units of consonants and vowels that do not constitute phonological constituents to undergo reduplication as well. He advances evidence from Tagalog to support his claim. Marantz anchors his proposal on the view (McCarthy 1979, 1981 and others) that the structure of the morpheme is hierarchical and involves the levels shown below:

Fig. 29

Reduplication in his view involves the affixation of one or the other of the skeletons above to a stem. Such a skeleton is itself a morpheme and is fixed for reduplication. The stem lends the reduplicated affix its phonemic melody by copying "over" the affix its entire phonemic melody. Association conventions ensure that the right melody is associated with the right slot. Below are sample derivations of the various types of reduplication.

40 (= Marantz (36)) CV reduplication

= barbari

41 (- Marantz (37a)) Syllabic reduplication

= dimudimuru

42 (= Marantz (39))

= kurdukurdu

There are two problems with Marantz' framework. First, we can observe that the distinction between CV, σ , μ reduplication is superficial and arises from his purely phonological approach to a primarily morphological problem. He merely typologises reduplication in terms of the nature of additional phonological material involved - when it coincides with a syllable, it is syllabic reduplication, when it violates syllabic structure, it is CV reduplication, and when it coincides with a whole stem it is μ -reduplication. Thus, he gives the impression that reduplication does not always involve a morpheme even though he did mention that the affixed

elements are morphemes in their own right and are fixed for reduplication. Following his approach it would not be odd for one to analyse other affixation processes as CV, σ , or μ depending on the phonological units involved vis-a-vis the stem.

The second problem is raised by the concept of copying "over". We noted earlier that identity of stem and affix is achieved by copying "over" the entire phonemic melody of the stem followed by the application of conventions. Copying "over" is done solely to prevent the violation of the WFC (association lines do not cross). Thus instead of having

43 (= Marantz (19))

a)

become

b)

we have

c) (= Marantz (20))

= taktakki

We believe that this method of copying "over" is too powerful, uneconomical and therefore undesirable. The mechanism itself is fundamentally objectionable and motivated strictly by considerations of theoretical convenience. It is too powerful in the sense that it does not define any stage in standard autosegmental association. Autosegments are supposed to be linked always to CV skeletons in some fashion. What copying "over" implies is that there is a stage or level of representation at which autosegments are unassociated to CV slots. Second, copying as we understand it depends upon the availability of slots. Thus, it seems unlikely that a melody would be copied irrespective of the non-availability of a slot. Perhaps a way out of this problem would be to pile up the affix above the stem as shown below:

Fig. 30

Morphological readjustment rules working on the relational specifications (stem, affix, prefix, suffix, etc.) will linearise the stem and affix.

There is still a basic problem with the requirement that the melodies of the whole stem be copied each time we have reduplication regardless of whether we have just a CV or syllable unit reduplicated (i.e. partial reduplication). Excess melodies are left unattached. This is a basic weakness in the framework. An account of reduplication should have a way of ensuring that only the right number of melodies and no more are copied.

of reduplication should have a way of ensuring that only the right number of melodies and no more are copied.

3.8.4.2 Our Proposal

The problems associated with Marantz' framework can be solved by accepting that reduplication is a bonafide affixation process and proceeding to analyse it as such. Consequently, the duplicate, like every affix, would be associated with a morpheme symbol. This morpheme symbol would provide us all relevant morphological information such as its status as a duplicate, prefix, suffix, infix, etc. It would also give us information about the morpheme structure (i.e. CV combination) in form of a convention CVx. x is a variable property whose precise expansion in total reduplication is done

once affixation has been implemented. For partial reduplication it would prevent the duplicate from exceeding a certain fixed structure. By following this procedure we are able to eliminate the incidence of excess melodies in reduplication. Reduplication would simply involve the affixation of a morpheme unspecified for phonological features. This automatically triggers the application of conventions.

It should be noted that having the CVx convention is not the same thing as copying CV skeleta of stems onto the duplicate as in Marantz (1982). Our approach assumes that all morphemes have skeletal elements whereas Marantz' suggests that duplicates do not and only borrow the skeleta of their stems. There is really no justification for this position. The concept of borrowing of skeleta of the stem

arises from the problem of capturing differences in morpheme length in total reduplication. In partial reduplications no such problem arises because there is always a fixed structure associated with a particular kind of partial reduplication. Thus, what we have done here is to recognise that all affixes have defined morpheme structures, but we allow the stem to exert some influence on the final realisation of morpheme structure in total reduplication. In other words, the expansion of CVx is done once affixation has been done. We shall now use a couple of examples to illustrate.

45

Total
ReduplicationBy affixationBy convention

a) i

ii

iii

= [ímɔ̀hímɔ̀hè]
'only male'

The surface form is arrived at after morphological linearisation, and vowel elision in the case of words that display vowel sequences across boundary (see examples 35 and 37 above).

b) i $\mu(\text{aff})$

[sè̀nè̀sè̀nè̀]

'very ugly, repulsive'

c) i $\mu(\text{aff})$

= [è̀vè̀vá]

'two by two'

Partial Reduplication

Partial reduplication will only differ from total reduplication on the CVx expansion. In total reduplication the upper limit is allowed to vary with the stem, in partial reduplication the x is held constant (fixed).

46

By affixationBy conventiona) i $\mu(\text{aff})$ ii

k é r é

C V C V

 $\mu(\text{stem})$

k e r e

C V C V

 $\mu(\text{stem})$

k e r e

C V C V

 $\mu(\text{stem})$

= [kékééré]

'all small'

examples:

47	<u>Input</u>		<u>By reduplication</u>		<u>By vowel Elision</u>
a)	ikpòsò 'women'	-->	ikpòsòikpòsò	-->	ikpòsikpòsò 'only women'
b)	èkè 'sand'	-->	èkèèkè	-->	èkèkè 'only sand'
c)	àgàlà 'on the spot'	-->	àgàlààgàlà	-->	àgàlàgàlà 'right away'
d)	sènè 'ugly'	-->	sènè [́] sènè [́] 'very ugly, repulsive'		
e)	bùmè 'to dust'	-->	bùmè [́] bùmè [́] 'be haggard'		

Stems which have high tones are unaffected by this tonal change. Below are some examples:

48 a)	éyè 'time'	-->	éyèéyè	-->	éiyéyè 'always'
b)	édè 'day'	-->	édèédè	-->	é!dédè 'daily'
c)	òkpá 'one'	-->	òkpáòkpá	-->	òkpòkpá 'one by one'

= /imɔ́imɔ́hè/ --> [í!mí!mɔ́hè]

'all male'

3.8.4.3 Tonal Changes in Reduplication

Following total reduplication, a reduplicated morpheme may have tones different from the tones on its input. In nominals non-initial low tones of stem and duplicate become high, whereas in certain verbs (see e.g. 38 d-g) only the duplicate realise the high tones. As we indicated earlier, reduplication in these instances is derivational. It involves a shift from the verbal category to the adjectival category. Below are a few

- d) kéré --> kérékéré
'small' 'many small...'
- e) héyé --> héyéhéyé
'be light' 'many light'

Generally, it seems as if monosyllabic words are not involved in this change. Hence monosyllabic verbs and pronouns do not involve any tonal changes when they undergo reduplication.

- f) hà --> hàhà
'press' 'crush'
- g) xù --> xùxù
'chase' 'chase (intensive)'
- h) wè --> wèwè
'you(sg)'
- i) vâ --> vâvâ
'you(pl)'

We shall simply postulate a H-tone reduplication suprafix which attaches to the second syllable of low tone nominal prior to reduplication. This tone spreads onto subsequent syllables. Following reduplication the duplicate copies both segmental and tonal features of the

stem. Bisyllabic verbs on the other hand only get this high tone after reduplication has been effected. The tone is assigned on the duplicate.

Downstep and contour tones are created as a result of the elision of low tone and high tone vowels respectively. The low tone of a deleted vowel remains floating and causes subsequent tones to be realised as DS. The high tone of a deleted vowel is relinked on a following vowel segment thus causing a falling contour.

coda. Below is a schematic representation of the hierarchy.

Fig. 32

An analysis of the syllable of any language must involve a specification of the universal and language specific 'Basic Syllable Composition (BSC)' and principles of resyllabification. According to Selkirk (1982: 257) BSC takes the form of a template and an accompanying set of collocational restrictions. It specifies a well-formed phonological representation. Principles of resyllabification carry out operations on underlying phonological representation modifying it in specific ways to derive surface structure.

Universally, the following conditions must be met

CHAPTER FOUR

THE SYLLABLE AND SYLLABLE STRUCTURE PROCESS

4.0 The Syllable

The advent of autosegmental phonology witnessed increased concern about such units as the syllable. Hitherto, a formulation of the role of the syllable in phonological processes, its structure and relationship to other units in the phonological component had proved intractable. Following studies on the syllable (Kahn 1980, Clements and Keyser 1981, Selkirk 1982, etc.) the status of the syllable in phonological organisation has come into sharp focus. For instance, it is now well known that a proper characterisation of phonotactic constraints and suprasegmental phenomena previously adhocly represented in terms of boundaries can only be done via the syllable (see Kahn 1980, Selkirk 1982).

Selkirk (1982) proposes a three template structure for the syllable. These are the syllable, CV and feature templates. The syllable template (σ) is a binary branching node dominating an onset and a rhyme. The rhyme dominates a nucleus (the only obligatory part of a syllable) and a

before a syllable can be ruled as well formed.

- a) The onset and coda must be filled by C- elements while the nucleus must be a V- element.
- b) Each V must define a syllable. Thus, apart from the fact that there cannot be a syllable without a V, the number of syllables in a string coincides with the number of Vs in the string.

The number of C- elements in the coda and onset are decided language specifically. Where there is more than one C- element, an auxiliary node will specify the collocational restrictions on the combinations of C allowed.

4.1 The Syllable Structure of Emai

The following template specifies the gross features of BSC in Emai.

Fig. 33

Thus, at the underlying level, Emai has a simple syllable structure with a non-branching onset and rhyme. The onset is optional as a result of the existence of vowel prefixes. Below are a few lexical examples of the syllable types represented in figure (33) above.

- 1 a) /é-wè/ 'goat'
 b) /ú-là/ 'race'
 c) /ó-ká/ 'deformity'
 d) / tǎ/ 'say'
 e) / bǝ/ 'to divine'

4.1.2 Phonetic Syllable Structure

The phonetic structure is arrived at after resyllabi-

fication. Resyllabification is motivated by syllable structure processes of deletion, glide formation and insertion which destroy or create syllables.

At the phonetic level in Emai we recognize the existence of a complex onset and a complex rhyme - producing a consonant cluster in the former and a closed syllable in the latter (see figure 3Aa and b).

Fig. 3Aa

b

Examples of words displaying these structures are:

2 a) /bià/ → [bjà]
'to work'

b) /hiò/ → [hjò]
'be arrogant'

c) /ihùè/ → [ihwè]
'nose'

- d) /xùò/ → [xwò]
'fade'
- e) /étò àgbà/ → [étwàgbà]
hair jaw
'beard'
- f) /àhòl/ → [àhòj]
'null, nothingness'
- g) /èhàl/ → [èhàj]
'forehead'

There are, however, certain restrictions on the realisation of these syllable types. The first restriction has to do with the structure of combining onsets and rhyme.

i Principle of minimal onset and maximal rhyme or vice versa.

This principle states that both onset and rhyme cannot be simultaneously complex in a morpheme in Emai. In other words a complex onset presupposes a simple rhyme and vice versa. This explains why figure 3^{bc} below is ungrammatical.

The syllable node cannot simultaneously dominate a branching onset and a branching rhyme.

ii No Onset no Coda

This principle states that without an onset there can be no coda, but not vice versa. Thus, there are no structures like the type in figure (35) below in Emai morphemes.

Fig. 35

For example, the following are not possible in Emai:

- 3 a) /ði/ --> *[ðj]
'thief'
- b) /ðú/ --> *[ðw]
'cotton'
- c) /šũ/ --> *[šw̃]
'shirt'
- d) /éi/ --> *[éj]
'tortoise'

iii Only glides can occur as the second member of the onset cluster, and as coda in the language. These glides are created by a glide formation rule which affects the

following vowels /i, u, o/ when they occur in sequence with unidentical vowels and when such sequence is preceded by a consonant. Examples (2) above illustrate this change. For a detailed discussion of glide formation, see section (4.5).

4.2 Vowel Insertion

Vowel insertion in Emai is motivated by the asymmetry between the morpheme and syllable structures of Emai and English (the major source of loan words in Emai). Whereas the morpheme structure of Emai makes it obligatory for all non-verbal categories to begin with a vowel, in English non-verbal categories need not begin with a vowel. Similarly, whereas Emai syllable structure permits no consonant clusters at the underlying level, English permits clusters of up to three consonants. Consequently, vowel insertion takes place to rectify unacceptable morpheme and/or syllable structures presented by loan words. Prothesis, insertion at the beginning of words, is motivated strictly by morpheme structure considerations while epenthesis, insertion elsewhere, is motivated by a violation of syllabic structure.

4.2.1 The Inserted Vowel

[u] occurs as the epenthetic vowel after labial consonants, and after other consonants if a rounded vowel occurs in an adjacent syllable. We may simply say that /u/ occurs as the epenthetic vowel in labial environments. [i] occurs as the prothetic vowel and as the epenthetic vowel in non-labial environment.

Below are a few examples:

4 a	i)	isílêti	'slate'
	ii)	isílípà	'slippers'
	iii)	ikílâsi	'class'
	iv)	igílâsi	'glass'
	v)	igírêsi	'grace'
	vi)	itírênî	'train'
	vii)	idíráívà	'driver'
b	i)	isúkú	'school'
	ii)	ibùlú	'blue'
	iii)	ibúrêdi	'bread'
	iv)	ipólù	'pole'
	v)	ipùlù	'pool'
	vi)	ibólù	'ball'
	vii)	ifônù	'phone'

viii)	ifúláwà	'flower'
ix)	itúrǎzǎ	'trousers'
x)	itúrǎkǐ	'truck'
xi)	ikǎkù	'cook'
xii)	ìkǎmù	'comb'
xiii)	isùtù	'suit'
xiv)	ifǎbù	'shop'

A similar situation is observed in Yoruba (Awobuluyi (1967, 1978); Pulleyblank (1988)). Pulleyblank accounts for the phenomenon in Yoruba in terms of the application of redundancy rules and labial harmony rule. Redundancy rules account for the occurrence of /i/ being the underspecified vowel while labial harmony ensures that /i/ becomes [u] in labial context. According to Pulleyblank "since consonants can only occur in onset position, any unsyllabified consonant must be assigned a rhyme. And since there would be no motivation for any particular vowel quality to be present on that rhyme, the unmarked expectation would be for redundancy rules to fill in feature values for such an epenthetic vowel" (p 247). He illustrates epenthesis in Yoruba as involving the following:

5 (= Pulleyblank (28))

a)

Allowable
syllabification

b)

Syllabification of
stray consonants

c)

Redundancy rules

While there are strong motivations for recognizing /i/ as supplied by redundancy rules in Yoruba, in Emai one finds no compelling phonological evidence to uphold such an analysis. Nevertheless we agree with Pulleyblank that "a vowel whose sole rationale for existence is considerations of syllable structure ought to exhibit no feature specifications other than those supplied redundantly" (p 249). On the strength of this alone we hold

that vowel insertion in Emai exhibits the stages reflected in (5) above.

Following from the above, we postulate /ɪ/ as the inserted vowel in Emai. The occurrence of [u] in a labial environment is due to the application of the labial harmony (assimilation) rule which spreads the labial feature of a tautosyllabic consonant or a vowel occurring in an adjacent syllable onto the inserted vowel (/ɪ/). Thus, an accurate picture of the insertion process in Emai can aptly be captured by the derivations below:

6	ø	----->	ɪ	----->	u
	by insertion			by labial harmony	

The labial harmony process can be captured schematically in the figure below:

Fig. 36

Figure (36) is two structures fused into one. The upper part shows the process applying progressively while the lower part shows it applying regressively. These structures are illustrated with the following derivations.

	by insertion		by labial harmony		
7 a) 'school':	skul	-->	isikû	-->	isúkû
b) 'suit' :	sut	-->	isûti	-->	isûtù
c) 'flower':	flawa	-->	ifílâwà	-->	ifúlâwà
d) 'crook' :	kruk	-->	ikírûki	-->	ikúrûkù
e) 'blue' :	blu	-->	ibilú	-->	ibùlú

Prothetic vowels are not affected by the labial harmony process.

4.3 Vowel Elision

Vowel elision is a common feature in Kwa and Benue Congo languages. Its pervasiveness is reflected in the following statement by Welmers (1973: 43) on Edo:

In a vast number of Edo utterances containing transitive verbs, the final vowel of the verb simply does not appear. After a considerable amount of elicitation, an investigator may well wonder how even a native speaker of Edo knows what the final vowel of a given verb actually is.

Elision applies in both deliberate and quick speech in Emai. This means that at any point in time listeners are presented with a highly phonetically reduced but natural stream of speech. Since in spite of this, communication is sustained, it means that vowel elision is systematic and represented in the grammar of the language in some way.

Vowel elision deletes either of two vowels occurring across morpheme boundary in Emai. Sometimes it is the vowel before the boundary (V_1) that is elided (as in 8 below); at other times it is the vowel across the boundary (V_2) that is elided (see 9 below).

8 V₁ Elision

- a) gbè ófè --> gbófè
'kill rat 'kill a rat'
- b) fi ídò --> fídò
throw stones 'throw stones'
- c) vè éwè --> véwè
to price goat 'price a goat'
- d) tà étà --> tétà
say word 'talk'
- e) ísi òtá --> ísòtá
am squirrel squirrels
- f) ólì àkàkà --> ólákàkà
the grasshopper 'the grasshopper'
- g) úhùvì évà --> úhùvémà
head yam 'head of yam'
- h) ófè óà --> ófóà
rat house 'house rat'

9 V₂ Elision

- a) éwè òlā --> éwénà
goat this 'this goat'
- b) ífì àvè --> ífímè
trap mine 'my trap'

- c) ékù àvà --> ékùvà
 waist yours 'your waist'
- d) ívèxà ésò --> ívèxàsò
 children some 'some children'
- e) èkpà ísì ògìè --> èkpàsòd₃è
 bag am king 'king's bag'
- f) ́kà ́lì ́gbò --> ́kálògbò
 maize Def. new 'new maize'

4.3.1 The Eliding Vowel

The choice of the eliding vowel is determined by the morphosyntactic relations between the lexical sequence bearing the vowels. The morphology of Emai is such that Nouns begin with (historical) class prefixes, while Qualifiers (i.e. adjectives, quantifiers, demonstratives, possessive pronouns) and construction markers begin with concord prefixes. These concord prefixes ^(all vowels) typically express number concord with their head nouns. Verbs may begin with vowels, but such vowels have no grammatical significance - they are not prefixes. Since Emai has an open syllable system lexical items always end with vowels. Consequently, whenever two lexical items are in sequence,

they make vowels available at their boundaries. The choice of the eliding vowel follows the procedure outlined below:

a) Grammatically functional vowels (prefixes) are retained in preference to grammatically vacuous vowels. This means that vowels of verbs would be elided anytime they are in juxtaposition with vowels of other lexical categories, since such vowels of verbs carry no grammatical information. Also, it suggests that final vowels of nouns, demonstratives, possessive pronouns, quantifiers, construction markers for the same reason would be elided when these words occur in sequence (i.e. N+N; N+Dem; N+Adj; N+Poss. Pron; N+Cm; Cm+Nom, etc.).

b) This principle is overridden if the morphosyntactic relations between two lexical items render one of the vowels in juxtaposition redundant. The redundant vowel is elided. Thus, since qualifiers and construction markers begin with initial concord prefixes, the prefixes become redundant when these words occur immediately preceded by their head noun; hence they

become objects of elision (see examples 9 above).

c) Where two vowels in contact are grammatically functional or vacuous (i.e. equally salient) and where there are no overriding morphosyntactic factors, vowel elision is blocked, so that at best assimilation and/or contraction sets in (see section 4.4 for a discussion of assimilation and contraction).

Following from (a) and (b) above, a correct reflection of the elision pattern in Emai shows that V_1 elision takes place in the following lexical sequences. Cm+Nominal (object) and N+N sequences. V_2 elision applies in a N+Cm and N+Qualifier (Possessive Pronoun, Demonstrative, Adjective, etc.) sequences. See examples (8) and (9) above for a few examples illustrating this pattern of elision.

4.3.2 Blocking of Elision

Vowel elision may apply only within primary constituent boundaries such as Np, Aux, Vp and Ap but never across their boundaries. Hence we find that elision does not apply in the following lexical sequences: Noun-Aux, Aux-Verb, Noun-Verb, Noun-Adverb,

Verb-Adverb. Below are illustrations of some of these sequences:

- 10
- | | N | Aux | V | N | Adv |
|----|--|-----------|-------------|-------------|----------------------|
| a) | <u>ófè</u> | | <u>ú</u> | | <u>òdè</u> |
| | rat | | die | | yesterday |
| | 'the rat died yesterday' | | | | |
| b) | <u>ókó</u> | <u>lǎ</u> | <u>ùwè</u> | | |
| | mortar | will | lost | | |
| | 'the mortar will be lost' | | | | |
| c) | <u>èdó</u> | <u>lǎ</u> | <u>vàré</u> | | <u>áxò</u> |
| | name of
person | will | come | | tomorrow |
| | 'Edó will come tomorrow' | | | | |
| d) | <u>i</u> | | <u>gbé</u> | <u>ákpè</u> | <u>éxèdèá</u> |
| | I | | kill | leopard | day before yesterday |
| | 'I killed a leopard the day before yesterday'. | | | | |

In the examples above, the relevant sequences are underlined. Examples in (11), (12), (13) and (14) below show elision applying within primary constituent boundaries.

- | | N | V | Nom | | | |
|------|------------------------------|--------|----------|-----|---|-------|
| 11a) | ò | sá | éwè | --> | ò | séwè |
| | he/she | shoot | goat | | - | - |
| | 'he/she has shot a goat' | | | | | |
| b) | ò | gbé | òlǎ | --> | ò | gbónǎ |
| | he/she | kill | this one | | - | - |
| | 'he/she has killed this one' | | | | | |
| c) | ò | dé | ùgí | --> | ò | dúgí |
| | he/she | buy | basket | | - | - |
| | 'he/she has bought a basket' | | | | | |
| d) | ò | sá | íjǎi | --> | ò | síjǎi |
| | he/she | shoot | them | | - | - |
| | 'he/she has shot them' | | | | | |
| e) | ò | zé | àvǎ | --> | ò | zévǎ |
| | he/she | choose | two | | - | - |
| | 'he/she has chosen two' | | | | | |

- | | N | am | Qualifier | | |
|------|----------------|-----|-----------|-----|-----------------------|
| 12a) | àgá | ísi | ògiè | --> | àgásòd ₃ è |
| | chair | of | king | | - |
| | 'king's chair' | | | | |

b) éwè ísì èvè --> éwé'sèmé
 goat of mine
 'my goat'

c) ókà ólì òbè --> ókálòbè
 maize which bad
 'bad maize'

d) éwà élì ògbò --> éwálògbò
 mats which new
 'new mats'

- | | | | | |
|-------|-------------|------------|-----|-------|
| | Noun | Qualifier | | |
| 13 a) | ébè | èvè | --> | ébémè |
| | book | mine | | |
| | 'my book' | | | |
| b) | ábò | àvà | --> | ábóvà |
| | hands | yours (pl) | | |
| | 'your hand' | | | |
| c) | èvá | éáì | --> | évááì |
| | two | those | | |
| | 'these two' | | | |

	N	N(Qualifier)		
14a)	ékpà	ókà	-->	ékpókà
	bag	maize		
	'bag of maize'			
b)	úbèlè	évii	-->	úbélévii
	gourd	oil		
	'gourd of oil'			
c)	úhūvi	évā	-->	úhūmémā
	head	yam		
	'head of yam'			

Within primary constituents vowel elision is blocked by the application of word order rules. Consequently, elision does not apply at the boundaries of such words that have undergone movement. Some examples of word order rules in Emai are 'Focus Movement', 'Head-Qualifier Inversion (HQI), etc.

'Focus Movement' foregrounds the morpheme under focus (usually content words) to sentence initial position. Examples below illustrate this:

- | | FOC | N | AUX | V | N | ADV |
|------|--|-----------------------------------|-----|------|-----|-----------|
| 15a) | | éwè | | gbé | ófé | òdè |
| | | goat | | kill | rat | yesterday |
| | | 'the goat killed a rat yesterday' | | | | |
| b) | ófè | éwè | | gbé | | òdè |
| | 'it is a rat that the goat killed yesterday' | | | | | |
| c) | òdè | éwè | | gbé | ófè | |
| | 'it is yesterday that the goat killed a rat' | | | | | |
| d) | éwè | ó | | gbé | ófé | òdè |
| | 'it is the goat that killed a rat yesterday' | | | | | |

It will be observed that even though a vowel sequence occurs across the boundary of the focussed word and the subject of the sentence no elision takes place.

The Head-Qualifier Inversion rule inverts the order of the Head and Qualifier in an alienable associative construction (to Qualifier-Head) and deletes the associative marker. In example (16) for instance, the order of ósà (Head) and òisà (Qualifier) is reversed after the application of the ^{HQI} rule. Observe also that no elision applies across the boundaries of the inverted words.

Input

16

H am Q

By HQI

- a) ǒ hǐ́ ǒsà ísì òísà --> ǒ hǐ́ǒfǐsá ǒsà
 he/she cut soap of- òísà
 'he/she has cut òísà's soap
- b) ǒ gbé ǒrè ísì òlǎ --> ǒ gbóná ǒrè
 he/she kill rat of this one
 'he/she has killed this one's rat'
- c) ǒ kpé ákò ísì òhí --> ǒ kpòhí àkò
 he/she wash teeth of chi
 'he/she has washed òhí's teeth'
- d) ǒ é ǒkà ísì àvà --> ǒ évá ǒkà
 he/she eat maize of yours
 'he/she has eaten your maize'
- e) ǒ dé ǒwè ísì òút --> ǒ démǔ ǒwè
 'he/she buy goat of mine
 'he/she has bought my goat'

Another instance of word order rule concerns the group of complex (idiomatic) verbs which we noted in section (3.3.3). These verbs have the following structure:

$$V \rightarrow V + N$$

The noun component of these verbs may be moved after a nominal object in a transitive sentence. The Nominal+Noun sequence so created does not condition elision. Below are a few examples:

17 Input By movement By Elision/Glide rule

a) ò jí + éhò èkpè --> ò jí ékpè éhò --> ò jékpé éhò
 he/she deafen leopard
 'he/she has deafened the leopard'

b) ò fí + éví ògiè --> ò fí ód₂é émí --> ò fjód₂é émí
 he/she hit king
 'he/she hit the king'

c) ò sá + áwòhà òhí --> ò sá òhí áwòhà --> ò sòhí áwòhà
 he/she slap òhí
 'he/she has slapped òhí'

d) ò rú + èò ílì --> ò rú íní èò --> ò rwíní èò
 he/she blind elephant
 'he/she has blinded the elephant'

The underlined vowels are the relevant vowel sequences.

At this point it is necessary to mention that in addition to the blocking of elision in the cases of movements in examples (15), (16) and (17) above, a pause is observed to occur between the word that has undergone movement and an adjacent word.

We have observed two types of blocking situations. The first coincides with primary constituent boundaries while the second results from the distortion of the structural relations between morphemes by word order rules. It is understandable why elision does not apply under these conditions. From the point of view of sentence processing the initial division of a sentence into its primary constituents is indispensable. Vowel elision as a boundary process fuses lexical sequences together. If elision were allowed to apply at all boundaries, whole sentences would be reduced to single unbroken strings so that constituents could not be identified.

At the boundaries of two lexical sequences that have been transposed or at the boundary of a focussed nominal we observed earlier on that there is a pause in Emai. This pause is a delay element needed for

processing. Thus for reasons of sentence processing, elision is blocked after word order rules.

One would like to state that it is not surprising that syntactic information is playing such a crucial role in vowel elision. Elision is a boundary eliminating process, hence it imposes a sentence processing task on the listener. To enable him to accomplish this task, adequate provisions must be made to facilitate his interpretation of the phonetic string.

Apart from the grammatical constraints on elision discussed above, other constraints of a morpho-phonological nature pertain to those instances where glide formation, assimilation and contraction apply. These processes are discussed in sections (4.4) and (4.5).

4.4 Assimilation and Contraction

As we noted earlier on (section 4.3.1 condition (c)), sometimes the morphosyntax may fail to resolve which of two vowels occurring across morpheme boundary should elide. This happens where the two vowels in contact are grammatically vacuous or functional. Assimilation and contraction may apply in this and other environments.

We use the term contraction here to refer to the compression of adjacent vowels into one. In Emai it is preceded by total assimilation of the vowels in contact. Like vowel elision, there is a measure of grammatical influence in assimilation and contraction.

A verb plus 2nd/3rd person singular object pronoun sequence presents a sequence of 'grammatically vacuous' vowels. These object pronouns (together with subject pronouns) represent the only nominals that lack vowel prefixes (see section 3.4.1.1). Vowels of verbs are also not functional. Following this situation, a sequence of vowels presented by these lexical sequences may be retained, undergo total assimilation or even contract afterwards. But elision never affects these sequences since both vowels are equal in saliency. However, morphosyntactic factors determine which of the situations above should prevail.

When a monosyllabic verb occurs in sequence with these pronouns in a sentence without an auxiliary morpheme or verbal sequence, neither elision nor assimilation nor contraction applies.

- 18 a) ò sá sí
 he/she shoot him
 'he/she has shot him'
- b) ò sá é
 he/she shoot you
 'he/she has shot you'
- c) ò gbé sí
 he/she beat him
 'he/she has beaten you'
- d) ò gbé é
 he/she beat you
 'he/she has beaten you'
- e) ò aé sí
 he/she stab it
 'he/she has stabbed it'
- f) ò aé é
 he/she stab you
 'he/she has stabbed you'

A bisyllabic verb conditions total assimilation. The direction of assimilation is determined primarily by vowel height. Lower vowels assimilate higher vowels

and where two vowels are equal in height, the rounded vowel assimilates the unrounded counterpart.

- 19 a) ò sává sí --> ò sáyá áí
 he/she rip apart it
 'he/she has ripped it apart'
- b) ò uáyá é --> ò máyá á
 it be used to you
 'it is used to you'
- c) ò réyé sí --> ò réyó sí
 he/she rock it
 'he/she has rocked it'
- d) ò kpáyé é --> ò kpáyé é
 he/she shake you
 'he/she has shaken you'
- e) ò kpókpó sí --> ò kpókpó sí
 it worry him/her
 'it has worried him/her'
- f) ò kpókpó é --> ò kpókpé é
 it worry you
 'it has worried you'

g) ò úúú sí --> ò úúú sí
 he/she crush it
 'he/she has crushed it'

h) ò ájé é --> ò ájé é
 he/she reply you
 'he/she has replied you'

i) ò kúló sí --> ò kúnó sí
 it slip him/her
 'he/she has slipped'

j) ò kúló é --> ò kúnó é
 it slip you
 'you have slipped'

Contraction ^{optionally} applies when an auxiliary morpheme or verbal sequence occurs in the sentence. In this case the structure of the verb is irrelevant. It is important to note here that contraction does not produce an intermediate vowel but applies after total assimilation has applied to make the vowels in contact identical. Contraction simply compresses both vowels making them shorter although still significantly longer than single short vowels.

- 20 a) ɔ̌ i sà ɔ̌i --> ɔ̌ i sáí
 he/she not shoot it
 'he/she did not shoot it'
- b) ɔ̌ xà sà é --> ɔ̌ sà sǎ
 'he/she won't shoot you'
- c) ɔ̌ i sǎ́ ɔ̌i --> ɔ̌ i sǎ́í
 he/she not stab it
 'he/she did not stab it'
- d) ɔ̌ i sǎ́ é --> ɔ̌ i sǎ́ǎ
 he/she not stab you
 'he/she did not stab you'
- e) ɔ̌ à kpòkpò ɔ̌i --> ɔ̌ ò kpòkpóí
 he/she Hab. worry him/her
 'he/she worries him/her'
- f) ɔ̌ à kpòkpò é --> ɔ̌ ò kpòkpě
 he/she Hab. worry you
 'he/she worries you'
- g) ò á kùlò ɔ̌i --> ò ɔ̌ kùńóí
 it cont. slip him/her
 'he/she is slipping'

h) ɔ́ á kũlɔ́ é --> ɔ́ ɔ́ kũnɔ́
 it cont. slip you
 'you are slipping'

Three factors necessitated our choice of contraction rather than elision as the process taking place in the examples in (20) above. The first is that an assimilatory stage is an acceptable stage in the speech of Emai speakers. Thus even though we have not indicated this stage in our derivation, it represents an acceptable alternative pronunciation in the speech of Emai speakers. In contrast, there is no acceptable intermediate assimilatory stage in the derivation of vowel elision in Emai - not even in deliberate speech. Second, the derived vowels are perceived to be longer than their normal short counterparts. Finally, in examples (20 b, d, f and h) rising contours are found on the derived sound. Vowel elision does not create rising tones in Emai. When a low tone vowel is elided, the tone remains floating causing subsequent tones to be downstepped:

21 a) ɔ́ lɔ́ gbè ɔ́fè --> ɔ́ lɔ́ !gbɔ́fè
 'he/she will kill a rat'

- b) ò ló tà étà --> ò ló Itétà
 'he/she about talk word 'he/she is about to talk'

Total assimilation also applies in the following sequences: subject pronoun + Neg/Aspect (Habitual/Continuous). The assimilated sequences could be contracted as well. Below are a few examples:

- 22 a) é i là --> é è là --> ê là
 they(indef.)Neg run 'they didn't drink'
- b) ú i là --> ú ù là --> û là
 you Neg. run 'you didn't run'
- c) í i là --> í ì là --> î là
 I Neg run 'I didn't run'
- d) v́á i là --> v́á ì là
 you(pl) Neg. run 'you didn't run'
- e) ś i là --> ś ì là
 he/she Neg. run 'he/she didn't run'
- f) ò á gbé --> ò ś gbé --> ǒ gbé
 he/she Cont. dance 'he/she is dancing'
- g) ś à gbé --> ś ò gbé --> ŝ gbé
 he/she Hab. dance 'he/she dances'

h) v^á à lá --> v^á à lá --> v^â lá
 you(pl) Hab. run 'you run

i) ù á sié --> w^ă sié
 you Cont. play 'you are playing'

j) í à sié --> j^â sié
 I Hab play 'I play'

The assimilation is in one direction. Only subject pronouns assimilate the following Neg/Aspectual morpheme. The phonological condition there is that only vowels of similar height assimilate. In the Pronoun + Neg. sequences, since the negator is a close vowel, only close and half-close pronoun vowels assimilate it. The continuous/habitual aspect is /a/. Consequently, in Pronoun + Aspect sequences only half-open and open pronoun vowels assimilate the aspectual morpheme.

Looking at all instances of assimilation which we have seen so far, one really cannot make a conclusive statement on the direction of assimilation in the language since only a highly restricted number of vowel sequences is provided by the lexical combinations in each instance. Later on, in the concluding part of

this chapter, we shall present schematic representations of all the processes that are discussed in the chapter.

4.5 Glide Formation

Glide formation and vowel elision are complementary processes. In their application both processes come under the same grammatical constraints. Like vowel elision, glide formation may not apply across the boundaries of primary constituents as well as the boundaries of lexical sequences involved in syntactic movement. In Emai, glide formation may apply within or across morpheme boundaries once the following conditions are satisfied:

- a) a close vowel occurs before boundary followed by a non-identical vowel, with the proviso that the word bearing the close vowel has the minimal structure of its lexical category;
- b) the vowel occurring across boundary is not a grammatically redundant vowel; such a redundant vowel is elided before a close vowel has a chance of forming a glide;

c) within morpheme boundaries, the condition is that the close vowel occurs adjacent to a non-identical vowel in the following frames: C-V, V-V, CV-. Below are examples illustrating the conditions above:

23 Glide Formation within Morpheme Boundaries

- a) /éhié/ --> [éhié̃]
'toe/fingernail'
- b) /ódíò/ --> [ódíò̃]
'elder'
- c) /xùò/ --> [xwò]
'fade'
- d) /égbúà/ --> [égbwá]
'backyard'
- e) /àhòì/ --> [àhòj]
'null, nothingness'
- f) /èxòì/ --> [èxòj]
'shame'
- g) /èhàì/ --> [èhàj]
'forehead'
- n) /ègèì/ --> [ègè̃j]
'crutch'

- i) /òtòì/ --> [òtòj]
'ground'
- j) /ójà/ --> [ójà]
'giant ground squirrel'
- k) /síà/ --> [sɔ̀jà] compare [éèà]
'person' 'persons'

Examples (a-d), (e-i) and (j-k) illustrate glide formation in the following frames respectively: C-V, CV- and V-V. There are no examples of /u/ forming a glide in V-V and CV- frames because it cannot occur in those frames.

24 Glide Formation Across Morpheme Boundaries

- a) ùdù éèxò --> údwéèxò
big garden egg 'big garden egg'
- b) flù áxè --> únwáxè
mouth pot 'mouth of pot'
- c) xù fùèè --> xwífuèè
chase monkeys 'chase monkeys'
- d) fi údò --> fjúdò
throw stone 'throw a stone'

- e) isi ògò --> ísjògò
 pig bush' 'bush pig'
- f) vǐ ébè --> vjǐbè
 write book 'write a letter'
- g) étò àgbà --> étwàgbà
 hair jaw 'beard'
- h) sò fò --> swíò
 sing song 'sing'
- i) rò òkpòsò --> rwòkpòsò
 take woman 'marry'

Even though /o/ also forms a glide in examples (g), (h) and (i) above, it must necessarily be raised to /u/ before it can undergo the process, since glides are transitional sounds which characteristically begin with a close tongue position.

Even though a sequence of a close vowel and a non-identical vowel may occur across morpheme boundary, a glide may be formed only when the word bearing the close vowel displays the minimal structure of its lexical category, otherwise elision prevails. Thus,

since the minimal structures for verbs and nominals in Emai are monosyllabic and bisyllabic respectively, it means that only these structures would condition glide formation. As examples below show, bisyllabic verbs and trisyllabic nouns do not condition glide formation. The same vowel sequence is presented in each pair of examples.

	<u>Input</u>		<u>Output</u>
25 a i	isi ògò pig bush	-->	ísjògò 'bush pig'
ii	òísi òxùbí gun firmament	-->	òísòxùmí 'thunder'
b i	éví ékù thing waist	-->	émjékù 'waist bead'
ii	úhùvi évà head yam	-->	úhúmémà 'head of yam'
c i	xù éwè chase goat	-->	xwéwè 'chase a goat'
ii	xùxù éwè chase goat (intensive)	-->	xùxéwè 'chase a goat'

d i	údù	éèxò	-->	údwéèxò
	big	garden egg		'big garden egg'
ii	íkùkù	éuà	-->	íkúkémà
	dirt	yam		'yam peelings'
e i	étò	àgbà	-->	étwàgbà
	hair	jaw		'beard'
ii	úkòkò	àsí	-->	úkókàsí
	container	snuff		'snuff container'
f i	vò	érà	-->	vwérà
	fetch	wood		'fetch wood'
ii	kòkò	èkpà	-->	kòkèkpà
	gather	punch		'make a fist'

The examples above show morpheme structure playing a role in determining whether glide formation should apply or not.

Glide formation never applies in Noun + Qualifier and Noun + Associative Marker sequences because of the elision of the redundant initial concord prefixes (i.e. V_2) of the qualifiers and AM. Examples in (26) below illustrate this situation:

- 26 a) ùgí òlǎ --> ùgínǎ
basket this 'this basket'
- b) èkò éǎi --> ékóǎi
corncake those 'those corncakes'
- c) údò èvè --> údóvè
stone mine 'my stone'
- d) údù àvǎ --> údúvǎ
heart yours 'your heart'
- e) òdù ísì ògìè --> òdú!sòd₃è
bitter kola AM king 'king's bitter'
- f) étò ísì ófè --> étó!sófè
hair AM rat 'rat's hair'
- g) ífí òlì òdè --> ífí!lòdè
trap am yesterday 'the trap of yesterday'

Finally, like vowel elision glide formation does not apply across primary constituent boundaries as at the boundaries of morphemes that have undergone movement. The only instance where glide formation seems to apply across constituent boundaries is when the 1st and 2nd person singular object pronouns occur in sequence with a following Habitual/Continuous aspect morpheme.

- 27 a) ú à gbé --> wá gbé
 you Hab. dance 'you dance'
- b) ù á víé --> wǎ vjé
 you Cont. cry 'you are crying'
- c) í à lá --> já lá
 I Hab. run 'I run'
- d) ì á lá --> jǎ lá
 I Cont. run 'I am running'
- e) ó à gbé --> ó ò gbé
 he/she Hab. dance 'he/she dances'
- f) vǎ á lá --> vǎ á lá
 you(pl) Cont. run 'you are running'

It is clear why glide formation does not apply across the boundaries of primary constituents as well as after word order rules. As we observed for vowel elision, this is as a result of the need to preserve the vital constituent structure information needed for sentence processing.

4.6 To sum up this chapter, we shall present schematic representations as well as a discussion of the structural effect of the processes we have discussed so far. We

shall begin with vowel elision.

Sometimes vowel elision may result in the distortion of the syllable structure of a language. For instance, when the vowel of a CV syllable is elided we are left with a stray consonant. The string undergoes resyllabification to get the stray consonant attached to a syllable. This may be exemplified thus:

Fig. 37

Vowel elision creates an unacceptable syllable

dominating only a C- element. It is this that triggers resyllabification; reassociating the C- element with an adjacent syllable in line with the universal and language specific 'Basic Syllable Composition (BSC)'.

Glide formation in another fashion creates syllables dominating only C- elements as shown below:

[xwéwè] 'chase a goat'

Universal BSC requires that every syllable dominates a nucleus (i.e. vowel). Glide formation

creates syllables dominating only C- elements, hence resyllabification takes place to reassociate these C- elements with an adjacent syllable dominating a nucleus. Total assimilation can be captured in terms of the spreading of a root node as shown in (c) below:

The reality of the spreading account of assimilation in Emai is suggested by the fact that once a sequence of vowels undergoes assimilation elision cannot affect it. This is because assimilation creates linked structures. Thus, the assimilated segment and the assimilating segment are dominated by one and the same root node. Following this vowel elision can no longer apply, since the Structural Description of vowel elision requires that two root nodes (hence two vowel phonemes) occur across morpheme boundary. However, such a sequence may be contracted. But a sequence of identical vowels in Emai conditions elision and not contraction if such identity is not created by assimilation. Contraction

in Emai may be represented schematically as in (d) below:

The structure in the middle (ii) shows the structural description of contraction. The broken line shows the spreading of the root node, while the double crossed line shows the delinking of the syllable dominating the assimilated vowel. The structural change shows two V slots linked to one syllable and one root node. Having one root node dominating two V slots follows from the 'Shared Features Convention' (Steriade 1982). This convention merges identical features of two root nodes together if such identity comes about as a result of a rule. We believe that the delinking of the syllable dominating the assimilated vowel and consequent resyllabification is due to a restriction which prevents a single

syllabic segment from being dominated by more than one syllable node. In simple language, total assimilation in a way turns two segments into one; vowels define the syllable, hence one vowel cannot be dominated by two syllables.

The difference between contraction and elision then is that in the former case it is a syllable node that is deleted, whereas in the latter case it is a V. Having two Vs in one syllable has its phonetic implication; there is a considerable reduction in duration to accommodate them within the timing span that defines the syllable. But the contracted sequence is still considerably longer than a single vowel.

CHAPTER FIVE

PALATALISATION AND NASALITY

5.1 Palatalisation

We observed in the preceding section (4.5) that a sequence of a consonant and a palatal glide may be created at the surface level by the glide formation-rule. A consonant preceding the palatal glide, if it is a velar plosive or approximant, or an alveolar plosive or fricative, may become a palato-alveolar affricate (for the plosives) or fricative (for fricatives and approximants). In the data below, the palato-alveolar affricate and alveolar + glide sequence occur in free variation. In the neighbouring Cra dialect this also extends to the velar consonant + glide sequences.

The velar consonants /k/, /g/, /x/ and /ɣ/ may become [tʃ], [dʒ], [ʃ] and [ʒ] respectively.

1 A	/x/		<u>Emai</u>	<u>Ora</u>
i)	xl̩à	'walk'	ʃ̩à	xʃ̩à/ʃ̩à
ii)	íxiàùò	'okra'	íʃ̩àùò	íxʃ̩àùò/íʃ̩àùò
iii)	íxìè	'a fly'	íʃ̩è	íxʃ̩è/íʃ̩è
iv)	xìè	'sell'	ʃ̩è	xʃ̩è/ʃ̩è
v)	úxiòvì	'half'	úʃ̩òmí	úxʃ̩òmò/úʃ̩òmò
vi)	óxià	'walking'	óʃ̩à	óxʃ̩à/óʃ̩à
vii)	xlèrè	'coil'	ʃ̩jèré	xʃ̩jèré/ʃ̩jèré

B	/k/	<u>Emai</u>	<u>Ora</u>
i)	èkià 'reedbuck'	ètʃà	ètʃà
ii)	kiè 'go back'	tʃjè	tʃjè
iii)	ékéíóxò 'egg'	ékjǒxò/étʃǒxò	ékjǒxò/étʃǒxò
iv)	kiàà 'be quick'	kjàà	kjàà
v)	kiàà 'become, vanish'	kjàà/tʃjàà	kjǎǎ/tʃǎǎ

C	/g/		
i)	òglè 'king'	òd ₃ è	òd ₃ è
ii)	ògíó 'name of person'	òd ₃ ó	òd ₃ ó
iii)	ógìè 'laughter'	ód ₃ è	ógjè/ód ₃ è
iv)	èglè 'at once, quickly'	èd ₃ è	èd ₃ è
v)	òglàglà 'smartness'	òd ₃ àd ₃ à	òd ₃ àd ₃ à
vi)	gièè 'pierce'	d ₃ jèè	d ₃ èè

D	/t/		
i)	ótíé 'cherry'	ótjě/ótʃě	ótjě
ii)	òtíàxùè 'day after tomorrow'	òtjâxó/òtʃâxó	òtjâxwè
iii)	tiè 'call, summon'	tʃjè	tjè/tʃjè

E	/d/	<u>Enai</u>	<u>Ora</u>
i)	dìarè 'come out'	djǎré/d ₃ ǎré	djǎré/d ₃ ǎré
ii)	ódíáwì 'noon'	ódjámì/ód ₃ ámì	ódámì
iii)	ódíò 'elder'	ódjò/ód ₃ ò	ódjò
iv)	dìá 'sit down'	djǎ/d ₃ ǎ	dèhá
v)	òdíàgbá 'metal bowl for holding roof to beam'	òd ₃ ágbá	òd ₃ ágbá
vi)	édíéìbò 'pineapple'	édjéìbò/éd ₃ éìbò	édjéìbò
F	/s/		
i)	ésíéì 'pepper'	ísjéì/íjéì	ésì
ii)	sìèrè 'bring load down from head'	sjèré/ǰèré	sjèrè
iii)	sìòbò 'remove hand from'	sjòbò/ǰòbò	sjòbò
iv)	ósìókpò 'yellow yam'	ósjòkpò/ósǰòkpò	ósjòkpò
v)	ìsìé 'nail'	ìsjé/ìjé	ìsê
vi)	ìsì ògò 'bush pig'	ìsjògò/ìǰògò	ìsjògò

Even though we have no examples of /ɣ/ and /z/ becoming [ʒ], we believe that such a change must have taken place in the past. Today, /ɣ/ and /z/ are not found before [j], while [ʒ] has been attested in only one item in our

data.

The environment for palatalisation is not before a close front vowel. Rather the close front vowel must first become a palatal glide ([j]) to palatalise a preceding consonant. Examples in (2) below when compared with (1) above shows this fact clearly.

2 a)	/əkí/	-->	[əkí]	'market'
b)	/ígí/	-->	[ígí]	'baskets'
c)	/ùtí/	-->	[ùtí]	'fettors'
d)	/òsí'é/	-->	[òsí'é]	'play'
e)	/óyíà/	-->	[óyíà]	'enemy'
f)	/fkió/	-->	[fkió]	'mascara'
g)	/zié/	-->	[zié]	'to endure'

In addition, examples (d-g) show that the environment of palatalisation is not before a sequence of a close front a non-identical vowel.

It would be observed from the examples in (1) that the conditioning palatal glide [j] may be absent from the output of palatalisation. It is absent in all examples with the exception of 1A(vii), B(v) and C(vi).

The term 'palatalisation' can be defined most

generally as a process whereby a segment acquires palatality. Bhat (1974) postulates three components of palatalisation which may occur jointly or severally. These are fronting, raising, and spirantization. However, each of these must result in the sound acquiring palatality. Seen in this light, palatalisation simply derives from an economization of articulatory effort. It typically raises or fronts the tongue position before front vowels and the palatal glide. 'Since a raised or fronted tongue position is an intrinsic characteristic of the following vowel or glide, it is reasonable to assume that palatalisation is an assimilatory process'.

Palatalisation in Emai involves the spreading of the place features (i.e. Dorsal) of the palatal glide onto a preceding non-labial consonant. The Dorsal features of [j] are [+high, -back]. The process is illustrated schematically in figure 38 below:

Fig. 38 a)

/h/, /r/ and /l/ are the only non-labial consonants that do not undergo palatalisation in Emai. It is very clear why /h/ may not undergo palatalisation - because it has no supralaryngeal features. Palatalisation of liquids on the other hand is not a well attested phenomenon. Since there is no single feature that contrasts /l/ and /r/ with others within the SPE framework, we have proposed a feature [liquid] in this work to enable us ^{to} impose a restriction on palatalisation in Emai. Thus, palatalisation affects non-labial sounds if they are also non-liquid. Thus (38a) can be modified as in (38b) to reflect this restriction.

Fig. 38 b)

An analysis of palatalisation that suggests itself to us is one that sees palatalisation as a form of coalescence whereby the consonant + glide sequence become a palatal consonant (cf Foley 1970, assibilation, e.g. $k + j \rightarrow tʃ$). This analysis is effectively blocked by examples 1A(vii), B(v) and C(vi). These examples show a stage where the palatalising glide environment is still present after palatalisation. This suggests a deletion of the environment in those examples where it is absent. Phonetically, palatalisation in Emal involves a movement to the palate-alveolar, rather than strictly palatal, position. Universal redundancy

rules ensure that plosives occurring in palato-alveolar position are realised as affricates.

Finally, it would be observed that the class nodes have binary values in our representation above as against the monovalent "privative" value assigned them by Sagey (1986). One would like to stress here that such binary values [+ , -] do not only characterise the phonetic properties of a sound, they help us to establish phonological oppositions. Thus, a minus value does not always only imply the absence of a particular phonetic property, it helps to express phonological oppositions in language. In our account of palatalisation above, one would be unable to express the restrictions on palatalisation, that only non-labial and non-liquid segments undergo the process, if we hold that class nodes are monovalent.

5.2 Nasality

5.2.1 Preliminaries

At the phonetic level, Emai displays an array of nasal sounds made up of seven nasalized vowels; six postnasalised or nasally released plosives; ten prenasalised stops; six nasalised approximants and four nasal stops. These sounds are listed below:

Vowels [ĩ ē ē̃ ā ǝ õ ũ]

Prenasalised stops [mp mb nt nd ŋk ŋg ɱmkp ɱmgb ntʃ ndʒ]

Postnasalised plosives [p^N b^N t^N d^N k^N g^N]

Nasalised approximants [w̃ r̃ ʒ̃ x̃ ɣ̃ h̃]

Nasal stops [m n ŋ ɱ]

These sounds are derived from their respective oral counterparts when they occur in the environment of nasalization. Only fricatives /f v s z/ are not nasalized in Emai.

At the phonemic level only five nasal vowels are realised. They are: /ĩ ē ũ ǝ ā/. There are no half-close nasal vowel phonemes in the language (i.e. no */ē/ and */ō/).

5.2.2 Nasalization

The relevant facts about nasalization can be summarised thus:

5.2.2.1 Nasality in Lexical Morphemes

There are three types of lexical morphemes,

- i) those with nasal segments only,
- ii) those with oral segments only,
- iii) those with oral and nasal segments.

Below we present data illustrating the three situations.

- | | | |
|------|----------------------|-----------------|
| 3 a) | [m]ǎǎǎ] | 'sprinkle' |
| b) | [rǎrǎ] | 'soak' |
| c) | [mǎhǎ] | 'sleep' |
| d) | [yǎyǎ] | 'happy' |
| e) | [ǎyǎ] | 'tasty' |
| f) | [k ^N ǎhǎ] | 'to cough' |
| 4 a) | [kpǎkpǎ] | 'sickly' |
| b) | [jǎjǎ] | 'tease' |
| c) | [tǎlǎ] | 'itch, scratch' |
| d) | [hǎrǎ] | 'wet' |
| e) | [kpǎyǎ] | 'shake' |

- f) [òhò] 'escort, blow'
 g) [bàbà] 'stalk'
- 5 a) [sàŋk^Ná] 'messy'
 b) [sùné] 'to struggle sth'
 c) [fà] 'pluck'
 d) [vé] 'disperse'
 e) [ááŋjé] 'urine'
 f) [àkásá] 'solid maize custard'
 g) [sùvèxá] 'junior, child'
 h) [ìbèg^Nù] 'shin'
 i) [òxùnì] 'firmament'
 j) [úfúnì] 'head'
 k) [úméxé] 'pumpkin'
 l) [éámì] 'meat'
 m) [ááŋjémì] 'cockroach'
 n) [ùáhá] 'shutter'
 o) [ànámì] 'swallow (bird)'

The third type of lexical morphemes illustrated in example (5) may occur as a result of the presence in a word of strident segments (fricatives [s z f v]) which are opaque to nasality. Also, noun class vowel

Prefixes of nouns in Emai are never nasalised. It follows therefore that since verbs have no prefixes in Emai, barring the presence of an opaque segment in a word, a verb or noun is either nasal or oral. However, neither reason explains why the second syllables are not nasalised in examples (5 (e-1)). Nonetheless, the following observation in (iv) helps to clarify the situation.

iv) In trisyllabic nouns, a nasalized vowel in the second syllable presupposes a nasalized vowel in the third syllable but not vice versa.

The situation in (iv) above may be seen as suggesting that nasality of the third syllable (or V_3) is derived from the second syllable (or V_2) where both syllables (or vowels) are nasalized in trisyllabic nouns. This does not in any way preclude the possibility that the two syllables (or vowels) may both have underlying nasality.

5.2.2.2 Stability of Nasality

1) When a final nasalised vowel of monosyllabic verbs and bisyllabic nouns (minimal structures) is deleted, the nasality is retained on a following vowel occurring across morpheme boundary; but such nasality is effaced following lexicalisation.

		<u>by Elision</u>		<u>by Lexicalisation</u>
6 a)	tò ófè roast rat	--> t ^N ófè		'roast a rat'
b)	sè áwà stab dog	--> sáwà		'stab a dog'
c)	kpè àò be posi- tioned front	--> kpào	-->	kpào 'be first'
d)	àfè èrà home father	--> áfèrà		'father's family'
e)	àfè ú`zé home axe	--> áfù!zé	-->	áfú!zé 'name of a town'
f)	èfè òkpá side one	--> èfòṅmkpá	-->	èfòkpá 'a portion'
g)	ódò àfè husband home	--> ód ^N áfè	-->	ódáfè 'head of household'

ii) In contrast, the deletion of a final nasalized vowel in bisyllabic verbs and trisyllabic nouns does not result in the nasalization of a following vowel (occurring across boundary), if the preceding vowel is also nasalized.

- 7 a) ɛ̃yɛ́ ɔ́lɔ́bá --> ɛ̃yɔ́bá
tasty king 'interest the king'
- b) ɛ̃hɛ́ ɔ́bò --> ɛ̃hɔ́bò
make hand 'place hand properly'
- c) ɛ̃rãrã́ ɔ́kà --> ɛ̃rãrɔ́kà
soak maize 'soak maize'
- d) ɔ́yṹ ɪbòbòdɪ́ --> ɔ́yɪbòbòdɪ́
crush cassava 'grate cassava'
- e) k^Nɛ̃hɛ́ ɪkɔ̀pɛ̀jɛ̀ --> k^Nɛ̃hɪkɔ̀pɛ̀jɛ̀
cough beans 'cough out beans'
- f) ɔ́mɛ̃hɛ́ ɔ́bè --> ɔ́mɛ̃hɔ́bè
sheep bad 'bad sheep'
- g) ɔ́vɛ̀xã́ àlèkè --> ɔ́vɛ̀xã́lèkè
junior girl 'pubescent girl'
- h) àkàsá́ ɪjòòbá --> àkàsá́jòòbá
solid custard Yoruba 'Yoruba type of solid custard'

In addition to our observations above, a preceding

consonant tautosyllabic with the deleted vowel is denasalised. See examples (a-f) above.

5.2.2.3 Domain of Nasalization

Nasalization extends from stem to suffixes.

8 Stem + Iterative Suffix

- | | | | |
|----|-----------|-----|--------------------|
| a) | dè + lò | --> | dèlò |
| | fall It. | | |
| b) | dè + lò | --> | dɛ̃lò |
| | buy It. | | |
| c) | sà + lò | --> | sàlò |
| | shoot It. | | |
| d) | vò + lò | --> | vòlò |
| | jump It. | | |
| e) | vò + lò | --> | vòlò |
| | fetch It. | | |
| f) | xù + lò | --> | xùlò |
| | chase It. | | |
| g) | fi + lò | --> | filò |
| | throw It. | | |
| h) | kḗ + lò | --> | k ^N ḗnò |
| | share It. | | |

- i) sà + lò --> sǎnǎ
 leap It.
- j) tǎ + lò --> t^Nǎnǎ
 dig It.
- k) vǔ + lò --> vǔnǎ
 uproot It.
- l) vǐ + lò --> vǐnǎ
 write It.

9 stem + jv suffix

- a) là + jè --> làjè
 run, flow rinse
- b) *sà + jè --> sàjè
 hatch
- c) *yà + jè --> yàjè
 'share, adjudicate'
- d) kpè + jè --> kpèjè
 wash 'wash'
- e) xù + jè --> xùjè
 chase 'close door'
- f) *vù + jè --> vùjè
 'cover sth'
- g) *vè + jè --> mǎnǎ
 'tilt'

- h) *vā̀ + jè --> mā̀nḕ
'peel off'
- i) *tī̀ + jè --> tī̀nḕ
'untie'

We are unable to show examples involving all the vowels in the language because the /jv/ suffix has been fossilized. Our examples here are drawn from section (3.3.2.2). See this section for discussions of this suffix.

10 Stem + (Iterative Suffix) + Change of State Suffix

- a) ̀ò gbè̀ + á --> ̀ò gbé!á
it break CS 'it is broken'
- b) ̀è vā̀ + ló + á --> ̀è vá!lólà
they split It. CS 'they are split'
- c) ̀ò bí̀ + á --> ̀ò b^{N'}í!á
it black CS 'it has blackened'
- d) ̀ò fū̀ + lò + á --> ̀ò fū̀nó!à
it quench It. CS 'it has quenched'
- e) ̀ò kḕ + lò + á --> ̀ò k^{N'}é!nólà̀
it share It. CS 'it is in bits'

- h) *vǎ + jě --> mǎǎě
'peel off'
- i) *tǐ + jě --> tǐǐě
'untie'

We are unable to show examples involving all the vowels in the language because the /jv/ suffix has been fossilized. Our examples here are drawn from section (3.3.2.2). See this section for discussions of this suffix.

10 Stem + (Iterative Suffix) + Change of State Suffix

- a) ǒ gbè + á --> ǒ gbé!á
it break CS 'it is broken'
- b) è vǎ + lǒ + á --> è vá!lǒ!á
they split It. CS 'they are split'
- c) ǒ bǐ + á --> ǒ b^Nǐ!á
it black CS 'it has blackened'
- d) ǒ fǔ + lǒ + á --> ǒ fǔ!nǒ!á
it quench It. CS 'it has quenched'
- e) ǒ kě + lǒ + á --> ǒ k^Ně!nǒ!á
it share It. CS 'it is in bits'

11 Stem + (Iterative Suffix) + Factative

- a) è là + lò + ì --> è lálólì
 they run It. Fac. 'they have run'
- b) è dè + lò + ì --> è délólì
 they fall It. Fac. 'they have fallen'
- c) è tì + lò + ì --> è t^Nínólì
 they fly It. Fac. 'they have flown'
- d) ò vâ + lò + ì --> è mánólì
 it mould It. Fac. 'it has moulded'

5.2.3 Analysis of Nasalization

Following autosegmental traditions, we establish the following parameters for nasalization in Emai:

- a) The class of nasality bearing units (NBU) defined here as those segments which are underlyingly associated with nasality. These are the five nasal vowel phonemes.
- b) The class of opaque segments which are those that cannot be nasalized - fricatives [s z f v].
- c) The class of transparent segments which are those segments that can acquire nasality at surface representation - all approximants, stops and oral vowels.
- d) The domain of Nasalization - the word (stem plus suffix).

Following our postulation of the five nasal vowel phonemes as the NBUs in Emai, we are faced with the task of locating the NBU in a stem that has more than one nasalized vowel (e.g. $\text{ɛ̃} \text{y} \text{ɛ̃}$ 'tasty', $\text{u} \text{ã} \text{h} \text{á}$ 'shutter'). We assume, following our observation in 5.2.2.1 (iv) that the first nasalized vowel is the NBU. Thus, the next task is to derive the nasality on other segments in the word.

Three analyses suggest themselves. First, we may locate the Nasality on the NBU and have a bidirectional spreading as illustrated below:

12 a)

b) (=lle)

Alternatively, we can see nasalization as involving two ordered processes: copying, whereby an NBU passes over intervening consonants and makes its nasality available to subsequent vowels and, regressive spreading, whereby transparent consonants get nasalized afterward by tautosyllabic nasal or nasalized vowels. This may be illustrated thus:

- 13
- | | <u>by Copying</u> | | <u>by Spreading</u> |
|----------------------------|---|-----|--|
| a) t ^h í+lò | --> t ^h í ^h lò | --> | t ^N í ^h nò |
| 'fly repeatedly' | | | |
| b) v ^h á+lò | --> v ^h á ^h lò | --> | má ^h nò |
| 'mould repeatedly' | | | |
| c) è f ^h ú+lò+á | --> è f ^h ú l ^h ó á | --> | è f ^h ú ^h nó ^h l ^h á |
| 'they have quenched' | | | |

Finally, we may postulate nasality as a feature of the morpheme (or word) rather than the segment, and simply spread the nasality from left to right, beginning with the left-most transparent segment as in 14 below:

14 a)

b)

This last alternative is completely out of the question, since transparent oral segments may cooccur with nasal segments in a stem without getting nasalised (see examples 5e-1). Where nasality is a suprasegment one would expect all transparent segments within the domain of nasalization to be nasalized. Moreover, it fails to draw a distinction between underlying and derived nasality; a distinction that is necessary for an account of the stability of nasality in Emai. Underlying nasality is stable while derived nasality is not (see section 5.2.4 for a discussion of stability).

The first alternative runs into problems by proposing a bidirectional spreading of nasality. As Hyman (1982) observes for Gokana, "the need for two rules to capture the automatic spreading of nasality is unfortunate and due to our decision to 'segmentalise' the nasal feature ..." (cf Chumbow 1986:17). As we have already indicated, postulating a nasality suprasegment does not account for the facts of Emai.

Perhaps more convincing evidence for rejecting this approach in its present form is the incidence of denasalization which we observed in section (5.2.2.2 (ii)). A few examples are repeated below:

- 15 a) k^Nsh̄ɛ̀ ikpɛ̀jɛ̀ --> k^Nch̄ikpɛ̀jɛ̀
 cough beans 'cough out beans'
- b) r̄ar̄à ókà --> r̄ar̄ókà
 soak maize 'soak maize'
- c) ũȳũ̀ ìbòbòdí --> ũȳìbòbòdí
 crush cassava 'grate cassava'

The denasalization of the consonant preceding the deleted nasalized vowel may be taken as showing that the source of nasality of the consonant is the deleted vowel and not any preceding segment. In addition, the restrictiveness of the regressive component as opposed to the progressive component of the bidirectional spreading makes this analysis highly suspect. As the examples below show, regressive spreading only nasalizes the consonant tautosyllabic with the nasal vowel, whereas progressive spreading nasalizes all transparent segments up to word boundary.

16 a)

b)

c)

d)

These taken together suggest the second alternative.

The only process that could have made nasality

available from one vowel to another one at an arbitrary distance without passing through an intervening consonant is copying. In support of this is the fact that the occurrence of nasalised vowels after prenasalized and/or postnasalized stops cannot be explained phonetically through spreading, since there is a fairly long break of orality between the two phases (i.e. prenasalized and nasal released of nasalization of the stops).

- 17 a) [sãŋk^Nã] 'be messy'
 b) [gbãŋg^Nã] 'trip, obstruct'
 c) [mãnt^Nã] 'sticky'
 d) [b^Nĩ] 'be black'
 e) [t^Nɔ] 'roast'

However, adopting this solution (i.e. the second alternative) would be at great cost to simplicity and economy. Moreover, the analysis breaks down with prenasalized segments which clearly derive their nasality from preceding and not from any following nasal vowel.

What seems to be the crucial point in the language

is that nasality is a syllabic property. Consequently, members of a syllable, both consonants and vowels, must agree in nasality (in so far as they are transparent to nasality). This agreement or harmony may be expressed in terms of a Morpheme Structure Condition (MSC) presented schematically below:

Fig. 39

The figure above states that any elements dominated by a syllable node must agree in nasality. Thus, once one element of the syllable gets nasality the other automatically gets it. The MSC together with the figure below are able to explain the facts of nasalization in Emai in a simple way.

a consonant follows the deletion of a tautosyllabic nasalized vowel. This stems from the fact that vowels are the syllabic elements. The loss of the vowel inadvertently means the loss of the syllable, hence the loss of nasality.

Prenasalization and postnasalization are simply the phonetic consequence of the asynchrony of the oro-nasal process. In the case of prenasalization, the nasal cavity configuration for the preceding nasalised vowel is maintained at the inception of the oral stop closure of the following stop. For postnasalization, there is an anticipation of the nasal cavity configuration for a following nasalized vowel.

5.2.4 Stability of Nasality

'Stability' is a technical autosegmental term used to refer to the retention of certain features like tone or nasality after the deletion of segments which appeared to be bearing them. In Emai, when a nasal vowel has been elided at morpheme boundary, its nasality is retained on a following vowel occurring across the boundary.

- 18 a) sɛ́ ófè --> sófè
stab rat 'stab a rat'
- b) fã́ éso --> fésò
pluck some 'pluck some'
- c) kɛ́ isi --> k^Nisi
share pig 'share a pig'
- d) isò áwà --> ísáwà
faeces dog 'dog's faeces'
- e) àkò ílì --> ák^Ninì
teeth elephant 'elephant tusk'

There are two possible explanations of 'stability' in Emai. First, one may assume that the soft-palate feature [+nasal] spreads onto a following segment occurring across boundary prior to the deletion of the segment bearing it. This may be illustrated thus:

Fig. 41

The double crossed lines show deletion of the root node (segment); the broken line shows spreading of [+nasal] across word boundary.

This analysis would erroneously suggest that nasality may spread across word boundary in Emai. Moreover, it fails to recognize the fact that feature specifications are segments in their own right and may behave independently of other features. The better analysis is therefore to propose a straightforward deletion of the nasal vowel leaving only the soft-palate feature [+nasal], which is then reassociated with the following segment.

Fig. 42

The broken line shows that only [+nas] remains among the vowel features. This feature reassociates with

a following vowel occurring across boundary.

Only underlying nasality may exhibit stability. Derived nasality does not. Hence we find the assymetry noted in (5.2.2.2.(i and ii)). That is, that the nasality of deleted final nasal vowels of monosyllabic verbs and bisyllabic nouns is stable, whereas that of final vowels of bisyllabic verbs and trisyllabic nouns which have nasalised vowels in the final syllable is not stable. This is because such vowels derive their nasality from the preceding syllable.

5.2.5 Nasality Effacement

Nasality effacement is a rule which deletes the nasality on vowels occurring at morpheme boundaries in compound and complex words. Since compound and complex words are derived from phrases in Emai (see section 3.8.3 and 3.8.5), it means that vowel elision would have applied resulting in the relocation of the nasality of the deleted vowel on a following vowel occurring across morpheme boundary. In other words, while stability is a phrasal property, effacement is a lexical property. Let us see a few examples below:

19	<u>by Vowel Elision</u>	<u>by Lexicalisation</u>
a) àfě́ ú`zě́ home axe	--> áfú!zě́	--> áfú!zě́ 'name of a town'
b) kpě́ àò be positioned front	--> kpǎǎ	--> ìkpǎǎ 'first time'
c) àgbǎ́ ìdì jaw, edge grave	--> ágbǎ̀ndì	--> ágbǎ̀dì 'be in the throes of death'
d) éhǎ́ úkpódě́ ear road	--> éhú̀m̀kpódě́	'sides of road'
e) ìsǎ́ ófě́ faeces rat	--> ìsǎ́fě́	'rat's faeces'

Also, nasality effacement is extended to instances of total reduplication in Emai. Nasality on the final vowel of the stem is not retained on the initial vowel of the following duplicate after its deletion.

20	<u>by Reduplication</u>	<u>by Vowel Elision</u>
a) ásǎ́ 'night'	--> ásǎ́ásǎ́	--> á!sásǎ́ 'nightly'
b) ìsǎ́ 'faeces'	--> ìsǎ́ìsǎ́	--> ìsǎ́! 'only faeces'
c) ǎ̀dǎ́ 'different...'	--> ǎ̀d ^N ǎ́ǎ̀d ^N ǎ́	--> ǎ̀dǎ́ǎ̀d ^N ǎ́ 'several diferent...'

Since reduplication as a lexical process is not phrasally based, it is understandable why stability is not exhibited at any stage in 20 above. For phrasally derived words nasality effacement is a signal of lexicalisation.

5.2.6 Nasalization of /e/ and /o/

Although /e/ and /o/ can be nasalized in Emai, */ẽ/ and */õ/ are absent from our nasal phoneme inventory. Their phonetic actualisation for nasalization vary from environment to environment. In phrases oral vowels (including /e/ and /o/) may get nasalized as a result of the elision of a preceding nasal vowel occurring across morpheme boundary (see 5.2.4, stability). However, as suffix vowels /e/ and /o/ are lowered to [ẽ] and [õ] respectively by nasalization. Examples are presented by the iterative suffix. The iterative suffix has two phonologically conditioned allomorphs lo and lo. The former occurs after close vowels and /o/ while the latter occurs after other vowels. After nasal vowels both allomorphs are realised as [nõ] (see section 3.3.2.5 and section 5.2.2.3 for examples illustrating this behaviour.

Apart from this example of lowering of [ē] and [ō] one never finds these vowels in stems in Emai. This, of course, can find explanation in the fact that like in suffixes they are lowered by nasalization. Conversely, we find that these vowels may be nasalised in phrase due to the 'stability' of the nasality of deleted preceding nasal vowels occurring across morpheme boundary.

- 21 a) fā̃ ésõ --> fésõ
 pluck some 'pluck some'
- b) s̃s̃ ófè̃ --> sófè̃
 stab rat 'stab a rat'

In such instances these vowels are not lowered to their half-open counterparts. It is clear from the situation above that half-close vowels are lowered if they derive their nasality from a preceding nasalised consonant (see examples 8 and 9); whereas they are not lowered if the source of nasality is a preceding nasal vowel occurring across boundary (see example 21 above). We can summarise these situations below with the following rules:

$$a) \begin{bmatrix} c & e \\ & o \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} N & \begin{matrix} \bar{e} \\ \bar{o} \end{matrix} \end{bmatrix} \quad N \text{ —}$$

$$b) \nabla \neq \begin{bmatrix} e \\ o \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e} \\ \bar{o} \end{bmatrix}$$

The absence of */ē/ and */ō/ from our phonemic chart may have been caused by their merger with /ē/ and /ō/ following the application of rule (a) above.

CHAPTER SIX

ASPECTS OF EMAI TONOLOGY

6.0 INTRODUCTION

Tone systems are bifurcated into the contour and register systems (Pike 1948). The register system to which most African languages belong is further subdivided into the discrete and terraced level types (Welmers 1973). The difference between the two subsystems lies in the operation of downstep in the latter which creates a pitch terrace by lowering successive tone units in steps. The result is that while the different tone units are kept separate in a discrete level system, in a terraced level language there is an intersection between the phonetic realisation of the different tones.

Emai is a terraced level tone language with two basic tones, high (H) and low (L). These tones contrast as shown in the examples below:

- 1 a) ̀kpá 'one'
- b) ̀kpà 'cock'
- c) òí 'pomade'
- d) óì 'thief'

- e) ékpà 'vomit'
- f) èkpà 'punch'
- g) údò 'stone'
- h) ùdó 'name of a place'

Ensi exhibits downstep (both automatic and non-automatic) in both lexical items and in constructions - affecting both high and low tones. The effect of downstep and other tonal phenomena is reflected in the varieties of tonetic forms in the language (see section 6.2 for a discussion of DS).

6.1 Systematic Phonetic Tones

At the systematic phonetic level Ensi has the following tones: high, low, downstep high, downstep low, downglide, rising and falling tones. The following symbols are used to represent the tones listed above ($\acute{V}$, $\grave{V}$, $!\acute{V}$, $!\grave{V}$, $\check{V}$, $\vee$, $\hat{V}$).

6.1.2 The High Tone

The high tone is realised phonetically as a high in word initial position or after another high tone in a high tone sequence as shown by the following examples:

- 2 a) $\acute{u}d\acute{o}$ / / $\rightarrow$ [- ~]
 'stone'
- b) $\acute{i}g\acute{u}\acute{e}$ / / $\rightarrow$ [- - ~]
 'a camp'
- c) $k\acute{i}s\acute{i}$ / / $\rightarrow$ [- -]
 'diminutive'
- d) $gb\acute{i}gb\acute{i}gb\acute{i}$ / / $\rightarrow$ [- - -]
 '(of heat)
 very hot'

A high tone is realised as downstep after a low tone; such a low tone may not be 'visible' (i.e. not phonetically realised). Downdrift (automatic DS) and downstep (non-automatic DS) are terms used to refer respectively to the lowering of tones after low tones that are phonetically realised and after low tones that are not phonetically realised. Downstep is discussed in detail in section (6.2). Below are a few examples illustrating the lowering of high tones after low tones:

- 3 a) $\grave{i}k\grave{o}k\acute{o}$ / - - / $\rightarrow$ [- -]
 'cocoa'

b) ódòdó / - - / → [- -]
 'flower'

c) ògídìgá / - - / → [- -]
 'a type of
 matchet'

d) àgá / - / → [-]
 'chair'

e) ú`zó / - / → [-]
 'antelope'

f) é`yó / - / → [-]
 'money'

g) ìwó`wó / - - / → [- -]
 'peer'

6.1.3 The Low Tone

The low tone is realised phonetically as a low tone in word initial position or as the non-final tone in a tone sequence. In word final position, the low tone downglides.

4 a) ígbàlàkà / - - - / → [- - -]
 'ladder'

b) igbégbè / - - / → [- -]
 'velvet'

c) údò / - / → [- ~]
 'stone'

The downgliding of final low tones could create the false impression that there is downdrifting of low tones in Emai. In a LLⁿ sequence all the low tones are realised on the same level but the final tone downglides as shown by the examples below:

d) àkàkà / - - / → [- - ~]
 'grasshopper'

e) ògbèlè / - - / → [- - ~]
 'belt'

(See also example 4a above).

A low tone may be downstepped following the deletion of a preceding low tone vowel or the delinking of a preceding low tone from the vowel bearing it. Such a low tone is perceived to be lower than a normal low. A tone may be delinked from the vowel bearing it following the application of morphological and syntactic processes which assign tonal melodies (fixed tonal patterns) to morphemes or sentences (see section 6.4). Below are a few examples:

5 a) ̀̀ 1́ gbè ̀̀sà --> ̀̀ 1́!gb̀̀sà
 'he/she Fut. kill chim- 'he/she is about to kill a
 panzee chimpanzee'

b) ̀̀ 1́ dè ̀̀gí --> ̀̀ 1́!d̀̀gí
 he/she Fut buy basket 'he/she is about to buy a
 basket'

by gerundi-
 vization

c) ̀̀lèlè --> ̀̀lèlè`ví --> ̀̀lèlè!m̀̀í
 'to copulate' 'copulating'

d) ̀̀bàbà --> ̀̀bàbà`ví --> ̀̀bàbà!m̀̀í
 'to stalk' 'stalking'

6.1.4 Falling and Rising Tones

When syllable structure processes (e.g. vowel elision and glide formation) desyllabify the first of two adjacent vowels bearing non-identical tones, contour tones may be formed. A falling contour is formed when the tones on the vowel sequence are HL while a rising contour is formed when the sequence bears LH tones.

- 6 a) ò gbé òsà --> ò gbòsà
 he/she kill gorilla
 'he/she has killed a gorilla'
- b) ò dé ùgí --> ò dúgí
 he/she buy basket
 'he/she has bought a basket'
- c) ò kó ìbàyò --> ò kíbàyò
 he/she plant bean(specie)
 'he/she has planted beans'
- d) ògó ùdē --> ògúdē
 bottle palmkernel oil'
 'a bottle of palmkernel oil'
- e) òkpáòkpá --> òkpòkpá
 'one by one'
- f) èváèvá --> èvêvá
 'two by two'

Usually, for some unknown reasons, rising tones are not created by vowel elision in Emai. The low tones of deleted vowels are not reassociated with a following vowel.

Both rising and falling tones are created by the glide formation rule when it applies within morpheme boundary.

7 a)	/égbíà/	-->	[égbjá]
	'morning'		
b)	/sáíò/	-->	[sájó]
	'elder'		
c)	/ihíagùè/	-->	[ihjágwè]
	'groundnuts'		
d)	/éhíé/	-->	[éhǐě]
	'finger/toe nail'		
e)	/úhíó/	-->	[úhjǒ]
	'deep water'		
f)	/átuí/	-->	[átwí]
	'anus'		

6.2 Downstep

Downstep is a phenomenon that is associated with terraced level tone languages. It is in fact what gives the terracing effect that defines these languages. The term 'downstep' is often used with

systematic ambiguity to refer to both downdrift (DD) and downstep (DS). Downdrift occurs when low tones pull down the pitch of succeeding high and low tones. Downstep refers to the lowering of highs or lows where no low tone exists phonetically.

6.2.1 Downdrift

Before we start to discuss downdrift in Emai, it is important that we draw a distinction between declination and downdrift. Very often when people claim to be discussing downdrift it is the former phenomenon rather than DD that is given prominence. Declination refers to the global tendency of the pitch (or more appropriately FO curve) of an utterance to decline progressively with time. Although DD also involves declination of pitch, such declination is far from being global or universal. According to Elugbe (1985: 45),

purely phonetic explanations in terms of the mechanism of FO adjustment do not in themselves account for DD: one must add to that the linguistic purpose, the fact that some languages use it for a variety of reasons. Moreover, the questions of relationship between different (basic) tone levels in a downdrift stream appear to be irrelevant in the ... discussion of declination in nontone languages Declination may be seen as a rather gentle (if undulating) gradient.

Downdrift would be a succession of clearly marked hills and valleys in a terraced decline.

Downdrift, unlike declination, is not simply a function of the speech process, it is under the active control of the speakers. In support of this is the fact that the distance between Lows and Highs is greater in short utterances than in long utterances (Stewart 1971).

Our analysis of DD in Emai is constrained by two factors. First, the application of vowel elision across morpheme boundaries causes the tone of the elided vowel to float and be deleted if such a tone is low. Thus, the terracing which may be observed in this situation is better analysed from the point of view of downstep. Consequently we are restricted only to intransitive sentences where no elision is recorded. Second, tense and aspectual information in Emai are characterised by tonal melodies and tone spreading (see section 6.4.3). The consequence is that lexical tones are set floating (and deleted) creating downstep. Spreading of high tone obliterates the conditioning low tone environment for downdrift. As a result of

these factors, we are only able to discuss DD in the word and in intransitive sentences rendered in the immediate future tense. This is the only environment where no elision and tone spreading take place. Below are examples illustrating DD in words and sentences in Emai.

8 a) ódùdú
'shadow' / $\overset{\wedge}{-} \text{ - } \text{ - } / \rightarrow [\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - }]$

b) íkèké
'bicycle' / $\overset{\wedge}{-} \text{ - } \text{ - } / \rightarrow [\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - }]$

c) ífòtó
'photograph' / $\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - } / \rightarrow [\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - }]$

d) ígbégbè ló dèré ènàá
velvet Fut. fall down now
'the velvet is about to fall down'

/ $\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - } /$
→ [$\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - }]$

e) ókà ló bí á
maize Fut. black cs
'the maize is about to/get blackened'

/ $\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - } / \rightarrow [\text{ - } \text{ - } \text{ - }]$

Like in Yoruba and Igbo, consecutive high tones do not downdrift in Emai. In the following words, successive high tones are realised on the same level.

f) dúdúdí / - - - / → [- - -]
 'very dark'

g) rírírí / - - - / → [- - -]
 'very bright'

h) ígùè / - - - / → [- - -]
 'a camp'

In contrast, consecutive high tones downdrift in Shona. (Hombert 1974:175). Although in Yoruba and Igbo consecutive low tones downdrift, they do not downdrift in Emai. In this way Emai behaves like Ghotuo, a sister language of the NCE branch where no DD is recorded for any sequences whether high, mid, or low (Elugbe 1985). Perhaps what may give the impression of downdrift of low tones in Emai is the tendency for final low tones to downglide. In an all low sequence, the falling of the final low tone creates the impression of a tonal terrace. In actual fact no such terrace exists; but the low tone falls from

the level of preceding low tones to an extra-low level.

- 9 a) àkàkà / - - - / → [- - -]
 'grasshopper'
- b) ùkù / - - / → [- -]
 'inheritance'
- c) ígbàlàkà / - - - - / [- - - -]
 'ladder'

6.2.2 Downstep

Apart from the issue of the formal representation of DS, a lot has been done in terms of its analysis. Winston (1960) was the first to recognize that DS "is not just a third (mid) tone in a three-tone system". He defined it as an intersyllabic feature which occurs arbitrarily and normally distinguishes or helps to distinguish some particular meanings or syntactic relationship or both (cf Elugbe 1985). Since Winston, a widely held position on the origin of DS is that it is from a floating low tone preceding a higher or identical tone. This derivation of DS from a floating low tone came with Stewart (1965) and it has remained

in vogue ever since. Although Fulleyblank (1983: 62) claims that the existence of phonetic DS may be attributable to ^{/aspectual} tense/factors, syntactic factors, lexical factors, etc, according to him such factors condition the existence of a floating tone in the phonological representation. Thus, DS is an indirect result of such factors. In section (6.4.3) we can see how grammatical factors may create DS.

Ways have been suggested in which floating low tone may cause DS. Hyman (1979) suggests that it is derived through contour simplification rules as below:

$$HLH > H(\underline{L})H > H\bar{L}H > H:H$$

Clements (1979) advocates an insertion of the DS. He suggests that the disappearing low tone and the DS be viewed as a sequence. Thus, DS is inserted before a low tone which may then be deleted. This approach has been adopted by Stewart (1983) and Elugbe (1985). They, however, insert DS after the disappearing low tone. Clements and Ford (1979) simply see DS as the result of having a floating low tone in the phonological representation. Each of the approaches above has its usefulness in relevant

languages end in specific environments, thus one cannot make any universal qualitative judgement about them. Nevertheless, it seems more expedient for us to adopt the analysis that inserts DS (in the way suggested by Stewart (1983) and Elugbe (1985)) in our accounts of Emai. Hyman's contour simplification rule is rather too clumsy in its derivation of DS. Moreover, contour tones (HĪ and ĪH) formed by syllable structure processes in Emai are never simplified to DS. Below we present a few examples showing the derivation of contour tones in the language.

- 10 a) ódǐò → ódǐǒ
 'elder'
- b) òdǐàgbá → òdǐàgbá → òdǐàgbá
 'metal for holding roof to beam'
- c) òtǐàxó → òtǐàxó → òtǐàxó
 'day after tomorrow'
- d) éhǐé → éhǐé
 'finger/toe nail'
- e) átùí → átùí
 'anus'

The problem with Clements and Ford's analysis of DS is that it does not sufficiently reflect the phonetic fact, that is, that it is not the low tone but its effect that is phonetically realised. By proposing the insertion of DS after a low tone which is ultimately deleted, one is able to express this phonetic fact.

Downstep occurs in both lexical items and sentences in Emai. In both cases DS occurs as a result of vowel elision and the assignment of aspectual melodies which set lexical tones of the affected vowels afloat.

We shall only discuss DS in lexical items in full, and, in the sentence, we shall only give examples of how vowel elision may cause DS. The whole of section 6.2.3 contains examples of how melody assignment may lead to DS.

6.2.3 DS in Morphemes

Downstep high tone may be created in Emai morphemes when a low tone vowel preceding another high tone vowel is deleted following total reduplication.

A number of CVV bisyllabic verbs realise H:H tonal combination when they undergo nominalisation. In addition, the verb stems become monosyllabic after a nominalisation process has applied. Below are a few examples:

- 12 a) vèè → fivé
 'to bargain' 'bargaining'
- b) tòò → á!tó
 'burn' 'grassland'
- c) rèè → ó!ré
 'visit' 'visitor, stranger'
- d) gèè → ú!gé
 'branch, spread' 'velvet tamarine'
- e) kòò → ú!kó
 'to parcel' 'cup'

Downstep in these examples is derived thus: Nominalisation attaches a high tone vowel prefix to the verb stem. Also a high tone is assigned to the second syllable of the verb stem, thus setting its tone afloat, the vowel of the second syllable is deleted leaving its tone floating, and finally, downstep is inserted after this floating low tone before it is deleted'. These stages are captured in the derivations below:

13 (= 12)

11) $\begin{array}{ccc} H & & LL \\ | & & || \\ i \neq & & vee \end{array} \quad (H)^2$

by nominalisation

111) $\begin{array}{ccccccc} H & & & & L & (H) & L \\ | & & & & | & / & \backslash \\ i & \neq & v & e & e & & \end{array}$

by floating H linking

iv) $\begin{array}{ccccccc} H & & (L) & & H & & (L) \\ | & & & & | & & \\ i & \neq & v\emptyset & & e & & \end{array}$

by vowel elision

v) $\begin{array}{ccccccc} H & & (L) & ! & H \\ | & & & & | \\ i & \neq & v\emptyset & & e \end{array}$

by DS insertion

vi) $\begin{array}{ccccccc} H & & & & :H \\ | & & & & | \\ i & \neq & v\emptyset e & & \end{array}$
 [i:vé]
 'bargaining'

by floating low deletion

b 1) $\begin{array}{c} LL \\ || \\ \text{too} \end{array}$

Input

ii) $\begin{array}{c} H \\ | \\ a \end{array} \# \begin{array}{c} LL \\ || \\ too \end{array} \textcircled{H}$ by nominalisation

iii) $\begin{array}{c} H \\ | \\ a \end{array} \# \begin{array}{c} L \textcircled{H} L \\ | \quad | \quad / \\ to \quad o \end{array}$ by floating H linking

iv) $\begin{array}{c} H \\ | \\ a \end{array} \# \begin{array}{c} \textcircled{L} H \textcircled{L} \\ | \\ t \quad \phi \quad o \end{array}$ by vowel elision

v) $\begin{array}{c} H \\ | \\ a \end{array} \# \begin{array}{c} \textcircled{L} :H \\ | \\ t \quad \phi \quad o \end{array}$ by DG insertion

vi) $\begin{array}{c} H \\ | \\ a \end{array} \# \begin{array}{c} :H \\ | \\ t\phi o \end{array}$ by floating low deletion
 [á:tól]
 'grassland'

c 1) $\begin{array}{c} LL \\ || \\ ree \end{array}$ Input

by nominalisation

by floating H linking

by vowel elision

by DS insertion

by floating low deletion

[s:r]

'stranger, visitor'

DS is inserted only after a floating low tone preceding another tone. Hence DS is not inserted after final floating low tones in the examples above.

We believe that other morphemes exhibiting DS in Emai have similar derivations even though their derivational history has been lost. This position is supported by the fact that DS can only occur in nouns in Emai and only as a final tone no matter the length of the noun. Examples of such morphemes whose derivational history has been lost are:

- | | | |
|-------------------|---------|----------------|
| 1 ^h a) | ú!gbó | 'forest' |
| b) | í!ké | 'horn' |
| c) | ú!gó | 'beetle' |
| d) | ú!ó | 'chimpanzee' |
| e) | íwó!wó | 'peers, mates' |
| f) | àgá!gá | 'a festival' |
| g) | úkél!ké | 'door lock' |

Downstep low tone is also created by gerundive nominalisation. Gerundive nominalisation affixes a discontinuous affix (/í-uf/) to the verb stem. It also assigns a high tone to the third syllable of the derived noun. By this token, ^{the} underlying lexical tone of the third syllable is set afloat. The derivations below show how DS may result following gerundive nominalisation.

15 a

'copulate'

Input

by nominalisation

by floating H linking
(and low tone delinking)

by DS insertion

by floating L deletion

[úlélé!mí]

'copulating'

b 1)

'hard, dry'

Input

11)

by nominalisation

111)

by floating H linking (and
low tone delinking)

1v)

by DS insertion

v)

by floating L deletion

[úkàká:mĩ]

'hardness, dryness'

c 1)

'eat'

Input

by nominalisation

by floating H linking (and low tone delinking)

[úèmf]
'eating'

Input

by nominalisation

by floating H linking (and low tone delinking).

[úlàmɪ]
'running'

It will be observed in examples (a and b) above that DS insertion follows immediately after floating H

linking and low tone delinking. This is because the delinking of the low tone automatically sets it afloat. Also, in examples (c and d) involving monosyllabic stems there is no DS. This is because the floating H links only to the third syllable of a gerund. This syllable in the examples is supplied by the suffixal part of the discontinuous gerundive morpheme.

6.2.4 DS in Sentences

In sentences, the principal cause of DS is the assignment of tense/aspectual tones (see 6.2.3). But both high and low tones may be downstepped when a low tone preceding another tone across a morpheme boundary is desyllabified. Below are a few examples:

16 a 1) L H L H L
 | | | | |
 ɔ ɔ gbe ofe Input string
 he/she Fut. kill rat
 'he/she is about to kill a rat'

11) L H (L) H L
 / | | |
 ɔ ɔ gbɔ ofe by elision

111) L H (L) : H L
 | | | |
 ɔ lɔ gbɔ ofe by DS insertion

iv) L H : H L
 | | | |
 ɔ lɔ gbɔ ofe by floating L deletion
 [ɔ lɔ :gbɔfɛ]

b 1) L H L L L
 | | | | |
 ɔ lɔ ɔ avɛ Input string

he/she Fut. drink water
 'he/she is about to drink water'

11) L H (L) L L
 | | | | |
 ɔ lɔ ɔ avɛ by elision

111) L H (L) : L L
 | | | | |
 ɔ lɔ ɔ avɛ by DS insertion

iv) $\begin{array}{ccc} L & L & : L L \\ | & | & | | \\ \text{ɔ} & \text{lɔ} & \emptyset \text{ au} \end{array}$ by floating L deletion
 [ɔ lɔ : am̩ə]

c 1) $\begin{array}{cccc} L & H & L & H L \\ | & | & | & | | \\ \text{ɔ} & \text{lɔ} & \text{xu} & \text{ofe} \end{array}$ Input string
 he/she Fut. chase rat
 'he/she is about to chase a rat'

ii) $\begin{array}{cccc} L & H & \textcircled{L} & H L \\ | & | & & | | \\ \text{ɔ} & \text{lɔ} & \text{xw} & \text{ofe} \end{array}$ by glide formation

iii) $\begin{array}{cccc} L & H & \textcircled{L} : & H L \\ | & | & & | | \\ \text{ɔ} & \text{lɔ} & \text{xw} & \text{ofe} \end{array}$ by DS insertion

iv) $\begin{array}{ccc} L & H & : H L \\ | & | & | | \\ \text{ɔ} & \text{lɔ} & \text{xw ofe} \end{array}$ by floating L deletion
 [ɔ lɔ : xwɔfə]

d 1) L H L H L
 | | | | |
 ukutu swe Input string
 'whole goat'

ii) L H (L) H L
 | | | |
 ukut $\emptyset$ swe by elision

iii) L H (L) : H L
 | | | |
 ukut $\emptyset$ swe by DS insertion

iv) L H : H L
 | | | |
 ukut $\emptyset$ swe by floating L deletion
 [ùkú:téwè]

The question of phonological representation of downdrift is discussed together with Question Intonation in section (6.5).

6.3 Lexical Tone Patterns6.3.1 Nouns

Three tonal combinations are possible in bisyllabic nouns. They are HL, LH, and LL. These are illustrated below:

17	HL		LH
	a) /úzá/ 'tsetsefly'		d) /ǎgǎ/ 'bottle'
	b) /óbb/ 'hand'		e) /ǎgá/ 'chair'
	c) /óà/ 'home'		f) /ǎzǎ/ 'bronze anklet'
			LL
			g) /ǎwǎ/ 'legs'
			h) /ǎdǎ/ 'heart'
			i) /ǎkǎ/ 'inheritance'

There is no single example of a MH bisyllabic noun in Emai. Although we have H!H, this is to be derived from underlying H(L)H sequence.

The following six tonal patterns occur in trisyllabic nouns; LHH, LLL, LHL, HLL, HLH, HHL.

18

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|----------------------|
| LHL | HHL |
| a) /itásà/ 'plate' | j) /égbíà/ 'morning' |
| b) /ìgbégbè/ 'velvet' | k) /ódíò/ 'elder' |
| c) /ámágò/ 'mango' | l) /ékéì/ 'belly' |
| LLH | HLH |
| d) /ádògá/ 'tripod
hearth' | m) /ódùdú/ 'shadow' |
| e) /ìjèké/ 'sugar
cane' | n) /íkió/ 'mascara' |
| f) /ètóké/ 'stump of
firewood' | o) /ákògá/ 'bat' |

- | | |
|------------------------------------|-------------------------|
| HLL | LHH |
| g) /ìgbògbè/ 'pall
bearers' | p) /ègús/ 'hoe' |
| h) /úgògò/ 'piece of
something' | q) /ìvíé/ 'beads' |
| i) /ágèlè/ 'young man' | r) /èhús/ 'boiled yams' |

Examples of HHL and LHH sequences presented above represent the entire set in our data. Trisyllabic nouns with all high tones are not attested in Emai. The only instances of high sequence on trisyllabic morphemes in Emai is presented by adverbial ideophones of degree. The high sequence is created by triplication of the adverbial structures.

- e) /áúúúú/ '(of colour), very dark'
- t) /gbígbígbí/ '(of temperature), very high'
- u) /bóbóbó/ '(of speed), very fast'

H- sequences are commonplace in both bisyllabic and trisyllabic nouns as a result of various rules that spread high tones on these units in grammatical context (see section 6.4).

6.3.2 Verbs and Adjunctives

Whereas verbs have low tones when pronounced in isolation, adjunctives have high tones. However, in constructions, the tone on verbs is determined by the tense and/or aspect of the construction.

19 Verbs

- a) /á/ 'die'
- b) /tà/ 'say'
- c) /dè/ 'fall'
- d) /áyà/ 'stroll'
- e) /kòkò/ 'gather'
- f) /kàkà/ 'hard'

Adjunctives

- g) /kéré/ 'be small'
- h) /kpúúú/ 'pellet-like'
- i) /kpéké/ 'petite'
- j) /dúgbú/ 'pod-like'
- k) /kísí/ 'diminutive'

6.3.3 Numerals

Numerals (the basic ones) have LH(L) tonal combination, excluding the numeral /ìhíó/ 'seven' which has a final high tone and /ógbà/ 'thirty' which has a H-L combination.

- | | |
|--------------------|-------------------|
| 20 a) /òkpá/ 'one' | f) /èéhà/ 'six' |
| b) /èvá/ 'two' | g) /èé/ 'eight' |
| c) /èéà/ 'three' | h) /ìsí/ 'nine' |
| d) /èéélé/ 'four' | i) /ìgbé/ 'ten' |
| e) /ìínc/ 'five' | j) /ùúé/ 'twenty' |

6.3.4 Deictics

The personal pronouns of Emai behave like verbs tonally. When pronounced alone they are all realised on low tones, but may manifest different tonal structures in different constructions. As for other deictics, one may recognise only three tonal structures. They are LL, HHL, and LH. The last structure is for comparative adverbs. LL is realised on the first dimension of place adverb and demonstrative pronoun, while the second and third dimensions (excluding /ewo/ 'yonder') carry the HHL pattern (see section 3.4).

A few examples are repeated below:

- 21 a) /ɔ̌lã̌/ 'this'
 b) /ɛ̌lã̌/ 'these'
 c) /šã̌i/ 'that'
 d) /é̌ã̌i/ 'those'
 e) /šľši/ 'the other'
 f) /é̌ľši/ 'the others'

One thing comes out clearly from our exposition of the tonal patterns in Emai lexical categories, i.e., that a highly restricted set of combinations is allowed in the language. Two lexical categories, the personal pronoun and the verb, are found to have lost lexical tone contrast (assuming that such contrast once existed). The noun category on the other hand retains this contrast. The complete absence of H-sequences in nouns is suggestive of a change from a purely tonal system to a pitch accent system. One important evidence of such a change in a two tone language (like Emai) is the loss of tonal contrast in verbs (see Clements and Goldsmith 1984:7). In spite of the plausibility of such^a possibility, we do not intend to

pursue a pitch accent analysis of Emai at this point. For one reason, in the language, morphemes still require underlying forms in which each syllable must be specified for an underlying tone. In a pitch accent language, 'the underlying form of each morpheme requires, at most, the specification of the location of a high pitch or a drop in pitch' (see McCawley 1964, 1970).

6.4 Tone and Syntax

In this section we are going to examine various tonal changes that take place in various syntactic units in Emai and account for the changes in a principled way within the framework of our chosen theory.

6.4.1 Tonal Alternations in the Simple Noun Phrase

All noun phrase types in Emai (excluding the numeral construction) manifest the same types of tonal changes. Usually, all low tones on the head of the phrase become high if there is no interposing high tone.

Possessive Associative Construction

(Alienable)

- 22 a) àwè ísì ófè --> áwé!áófè
 leg AM rat 'rat's legs'
- b) óvèxà ísì òí --> óvèxàsòí
 child his 'his child'

Inalienable Possession

- c) ùbèlè àwè --> úbélámè
 gourd water 'a gourd of water'
- d) èkpà ìvì --> ékpìvì
 bag kernel 'a bag of kernels'

Descriptive Associative Construction

- e) ògbèlè ílì òfùá --> ógbélé lòfùá
 belt AM white 'white belt'
- f) íkúkù élì ògbèré --> íkúkú lògbèré
 bullets AM surplus 'surplus bullets'

Demonstrative Construction

- g) ìkpèxiè òlá --> íkpéjé nà
 beans this 'this beans'
- h) íbàtà èlá --> íbátá nà
 shoe these 'these shoes'

- g) ̀igbégbè ́sáì --> ̀igbégbé ́áì
 velvet that 'that velvet'
- h) ̀íkèké ̀lǎ --> ̀íkèké ́nǎ
 bicycle this 'this bicycle'
- i) ̀ògídìgá ́ólì ̀òdè --> ̀ògídìgá ̀lòdè
 a type of AM yesterday 'the cutlass of yesterday'
 cutlass

The change observed in examples 22 and 23 is not peculiar to Emai; it seems to us a general feature of Edoid languages. Elimelech (1976) and Amayo (1976) account for similar changes in Etsakq (Yekhee) and ̀do (Bini) respectively by postulating floating tones (in the phonological representation) for each noun phrase type identified. Such floating tones were sometimes derived historically as remnants of a deleted construction marker. This is particularly the case in the associative construction in Edo (Amayo 1976). The tonal change in the head noun in Emai is completely identical with the changes reported in Yekhee by Elimelech. In his analysis, a floating high tone was postulated between the head noun and qualifier for each of the noun phrase constructions

he identified in the language. He made no attempt to derive these floating high tones either historically or synchronically. Whatever solution we advance to explain this change must be able to avoid proliferating floating tones since the consistency exhibited by the change in all noun phrase types is suggestive of a uniform cause. In the following paragraphs we shall argue that the change is caused by the spreading of initial high tone of construction markers or qualifiers. This argument is particularly strengthened by the fact that for each of these constructions a high tone prefix of construction markers or qualifiers may be postulated after the head noun.

Tonal change in the head noun of an associative noun phrase (alienable or inalienable) may be traced to the high tone concord prefix of the associative markers (*ísi/ési* and *íli/éli*). In Chapter Three (section 3.6) we mentioned that the initial vowel of the associative marker (*ísi/ési*) is a concord prefix which agrees with the head noun in locative and non-locative association. This vowel has a high tone. The descriptive associative phrase marker, it was observed,

is indistinct from the definite article (óli/éli) even though on the surface only the li form is realised. The initial vowel of this morpheme is a concord prefix which agrees in number with the head noun. We also mentioned that the inalienable associative construction is derived from its alienable counterpart by deleting the associative marker (see appendix 1.2.3). Thus, at the underlying level, the distinction between alienable and inalienable associative construction is nonexistent.

With the above background information in mind, we may simply account for the change in the possessive and descriptive associative constructions in terms of the spreading of the high tone of the concord prefix of the construction marker. This is followed by the deletion of the vowels of the associative marker in the descriptive and alienable associative constructions and the deletion of the whole associative marker in the inalienable construction. A few sample derivations of some of the examples in (22) are supplied below:

24

a i) L L L H L H L
 | | | | | | |
 akaka isi ofe
 grasshopper AM rat
 'rat's grasshopper'

ii) by CPTS (Concord Prefix Tone Spread)

 H L H L
 | | | |
 akaka isi ofe

iii) by vowel Elision

 H (L) H L
 | | |
 akaka ósó ofe

iv) by DS Insertion

 H (L) | H L
 | | |
 akaka ósó ofe

v) by floating low Deletion

b i)

H L L	H L	L LL
ovexá	isi	ogie
child	AM	king
'king's child'		

ii) by OPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

iv) by DS Insertion

v) by floating low Deletion

Inalienable Associative Construction

- c i) L L L H L L L
 | | | | | | |
 ubele isi ané
 gourd AM water
 'a gourd of water'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by am Deletion

[úbéla^hmē]

i) $\begin{array}{ccc} \text{L} & \text{L} & \text{L} \\ | & | & | \\ \text{akaka} & & \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{cc} \text{H} & \text{L} \\ | & | \\ \text{isi} & & \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \text{HL} & & \text{L} \\ | & | & | \\ \text{eimi} & & \end{array}$

grass-

hopper AM heaven

'a species of grasshopper'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by am Deletion

Descriptive Associative Construction

- e i) L L L H L L L
 | | | | | | |
 íxuví òli obe
 charm AM bad
 'bad charm'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

f i) $\begin{array}{ccc} L & L & L \\ | & | & | \\ ibele & eli & ebi \end{array}$ $\begin{array}{cc} H & L \\ | & | \\ eli & ebi \end{array}$ $\begin{array}{cc} H & | & H \\ | & & | \\ ebi & & ebi \end{array}$

gourds AM black

'black gourds'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

The difference between the derivation of the alienable and inalienable possessive associations is that after spreading the associative morpheme is deleted in the former whereas only its vowels are deleted in the latter. This difference is reflected in the fact that in the alienable construction the tone of the initial vowel of a qualifier is downstepped following the deletion of final low tone vowel of *am*. In the inalienable construction, this does not happen because the whole morpheme (with its tones) is deleted.

We would observe that although the derivation involving the descriptive associative construction follows the same procedure as the alienable possessive counterpart, it does not create tonal downstep. In other words, even though its final low tone vowel is deleted, the following tone of the qualifier is not downstepped (see examples 24e and f). This behaviour is consistent with the definite article (here functioning as *am*) in *Emai*. Although the definite article has a final low tone when it is pronounced in isolation, we find that unlike other morphemes in *Emai*, the deletion

of this low tone vowel in construction does not result in downstepped tones.

- 25 a) /óli údò/ --> [óluúdò]
 'the stone'
- b) /éli àwè/ --> [élaàwè]
 'the legs'
- c) /óli ófè/ --> [óluófè]
 'the rat'
- d) /éli èkpà/ --> [élaèkpà]
 'the bags'

We cannot postulate a high tone on this vowel because its deletion does not result in the formation of a falling contour (i.e. HL) as one would expect. We conclude therefore that the low tone gets deleted with the vowel.

In the demonstrative construction the derivation is essentially the same since demonstratives like other qualifiers have initial concord prefixes. Whereas the second and third dimension demonstratives (/óáì 'that', /éáì 'those', /ólóì 'the other', /élóì 'the others') have high tone concord prefixes, the first dimension demonstratives (/òlá/ 'this', /èlá/ 'these') have low

tone concord prefixes when rendered in isolation.

However, their emphatic counterparts have high tone prefixes (/ʒlálá/ 'this very one', /élálá/ 'these very ones'). In the light of this one may ignore the low tones on the prefixes of unemphatic first dimension demonstratives and postulate a high tone concord prefix for all demonstratives in Emai. Thus, the derivation would be as shown below:

ii) by CPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

- b i) L L H HL
 | | | ||
 ckpa elõi

 bag the others
 'the other bags'

- ii) by CPTS

- iii) by Vowel Elision

- c i) L L HHL
 | | |||
 ota oai

 squirrel that
 'that squirrel'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

d i) L L L H L
 | | | | |
 urukpa eā

la tern these
 'these latterns'

ii) by CPTS

iii) by Vowel Elision

There is a strong phonological motivation for treating the first dimension demonstratives as having high tone concord prefixes. For one reason, the deletion of their concord prefixes does not result in downstepping of succeeding tones as would be expected (see examples 26a and d above). These demonstratives also behave abberantly with regard to changes affecting pronominal qualifiers of noun phrase. All other pronouns LH patterns as qualifiers of NP in alienable associative construction; only /òlā/ 'this' and /èlā/ 'these' maintain their tones.

- 27 a) óbò ísì òlā --> óbó!sòná
 hand am this one 'this one's hand'
- b) àwè ísì èlā --> áwé!sèná
 legs am these ones 'these ones' legs'
- c) òkpà ísì ólò --> ókpá!sòńí
 bag am the other one 'the other one's bag'

- d) ébè ísì éáí --> ébé!sèáí
 book AM those 'those ones' books'
- e) àvè ísì óí --> ámé!sòí
 water AM his/hers 'his/her water'
- f) ábò ísì àvà --> ábó!sàvá
 hands AM yours(pl) 'your hands'
- g) éwè ísì èvè --> éwé!sèmé
 goat AM mine 'my goat'

Following from the above, one may conclude that the demonstrative category is undergoing change as part of the tonal changes which have eliminated the high tone from verbs and personal pronouns. This change it seems is starting with the first dimension demonstratives; hence the realisation of low tones on them when they occur in isolation.

Generally, in support of the analysis of the tonal change in head nouns which we have put forward is the fact that the change does not apply in the numeral construction - the only noun phrase construction in Emai where morphological concord is not expressed. A few examples are presented below:

- 28 a) ògbèlè òkpá → ògbèlè òkpá
 belt one 'one belt'
- b) àkàkà ìgbé → àkàkà ìgbé
 grass- hopper ten 'ten grasshoppers'
- c) ìxùvì ógbà → ìxùmí ógbà
 charm thirty 'thirty charms'

Thus, it would seem as if there is a definite link between the occurrence of a concord prefix and the change on the head noun.

An alternative approach to our account above is to postulate a floating high tone (i.e. (H)) between the head and qualifier in the inalienable possessive and demonstrative constructions, and between the head and sm in the descriptive and alienable associative constructions (quite apart from the high tone of the initial vowel of construction marker and qualifier). This floating tone would spread onto preceding low tone syllables. A few examples are presented below:

29 a (2 2a)

ii) by $\textcircled{H}$ Spreading

iii) by Vowel Elision

iv) by DS Insertion

v) by floating low Deletion

[áwé:sófè]

'rat's legs'

11) by (H) Spreading

111) by Vowel Elision

11) by (H) Spreading

iii) by Vowel Elision

The derivations above represent the alienable and inalienable associative constructions, the descriptive associative construction and the demonstrative construction in that order. As the derivations show, the floating high tone (H) occurs as part of the underlying representation. This tone rather than the high tone on concord prefixes of construction markers and qualifiers spreads onto the preceding low tone syllables. This a conveniently simple approach since we do not have to postulate an associative marker which is deleted in the inalienable construction. The problem with this approach is that it undermines the underlying relationship between the alienable and inalienable constructions. It tells us nothing about the source of the floating high tone. Thus, it reduces the floating tone to a mere descriptive artefact. Having a floating tone marking constructions

that already have grammatical markers is rather superfluous.

In all noun phrase constructions in Emai, the spreading of the high tone of the concord prefix is blocked by a high tone. Thus in a sequence of low tones interposed by a high tone, the lows following the high are raised to high whereas all lows preceding the high are unchanged. This blocking phenomenon is exemplified in (23a-1) above.

Following our framework, we may represent the change in the head noun as in Fig. 43 below:

Fig. 43

This diagram states that the high tone of a concord prefix spreads across boundary onto a sequence of vowels of a preceding morpheme specified as [-High] tone (i.e. low tones) in Emai.

- c) úkpódè ísì ígúè ísì òkè → úkpódé: sígúé: sòkè
 road AM camp AM oke
 'the road to Oke's camp'
- d) àwè ísì ígbàláká ísì òkiè ísì òkè → áwé: sígbáláká: sòd₃é: sòkè
 legs AM ladder AM king AM oke
 'the legs of the king of Oke's ladder'
- e) èkpà ísì ikéké òlā → èkpá: síkéké nā
 bag AM bicycle, this
 'this bicycle's bag'
- f) èkpà ísì òúú ísì èkpè → èkpá: sòúú: sèkpè
 bag AM pear AM leopard
 'the leopard's bag of pear'
- g) àwè ísì àdògá òlólí → áwé: sàdògá nólí
 legs AM tripod hearth the other
 'the legs of the other tripod hearth'

- h) óbò ísì úxùèdè ísì ímátò ísì òkpòsò òlà → óbò:sùxwédé:símátó:sòkpósó nà
 hand AM door AM car AM woman this
 'the handle of the door of this woman's car'
- 1) éhò ísì úkpò ísì úxùèdè òlà → éhò:sùkpú:sùxwédé nà
 edge AM cloth AM door this
 'the edge of this door blind'
- 3) àkpótí ísì éiyó ísì òní → àkpótí:sé: ó:sòní
 box AM money AM ohí
 'Chi's box of money'

We are only concerned here with the tonal changes in the heads of the qualifier phrase. We are already aware that the tonal change in the head noun of a noun phrase is caused by the spreading of the high tone of the concord prefixes of the associative marker or qualifier. We also know that a downstep in the qualifier is caused by the low tone of deleted final vowel of the associative marker (see section (6.1.1)). Thus, one observes that only head nouns of embedded NPs undergo tonal change. The change involves the conversion of the tonal patterns on the left to the patterns on the right of the arrow:

LL(L)	→	LH(H)	(e.g. 31a)
HL(L)	→	LH(H)	(" b)
HHL	→	LHH	(" c)
HLH	→	HLH	(" d)
LHL	→	LHH	(" e)
LLH	→	LLH	(" f)
H!H	→	H!H	(" j)

There are two possible ways of accounting for this change. The first is to assume that a LH(H) tone melody is assigned to the nominal heads of a qualifier

phrase. These tones link from left to right. The melody is blocked if a final high tone occurs in a morpheme (as in 31 e-g and j).

A better analysis is simply to account for the change in terms of the insertion of a low tone on the first syllable of nominal heads of qualifier phrases. This insertion takes place after CPTS and vowel elision have applied in each of the simple NP components hence we have a LH(H) pattern. The low tone is an index of the internal bracketing of the complex NP. It shows that the relevant morpheme belongs logically to two NPs. Below are sample derivations of some examples in (31).

32 a 1)

L	L	H	L	H	L	L	H	L	L	LL
iwe	isi	cuexã	isi	ogie						

11) by CPTS, and vowel elision

H	(L)	H	H	(L)	L	L
iwe	øøø	cuexã	øøø	od ₃ e		

111) by low tone insertion

[íwé:sòvèxá:sòd₃è]

'the king's child's house'

11) by CPTS, and vowel elision

111) by low tone insertion

[ùkpòdè:sìguè:sòkè]

'the road to Oke's camp'

11) by CPTS and vowel elision

111) by low tone insertion (links vacuously)

[ékpa:sòúmú:sèkpè]

'the leopard's bag of pear'

We have postulated low tone insertion rather than linking the low tone of the deleted final vowel of the associative marker onto the following vowel of the head of the qualifier phrase because if we did that we would have no way of accounting for the occurrence of DS in the output.

Finally, since a lexical high tone blocks spreading, and since low tone insertion in complex NP is ordered after spreading,

it follows that if spreading fails to apply low tone insertion would also not apply. This explains why no change takes place on heads of qualifier phrases that have final high tones (see 31e, g and j).

6.4.3 Tone and Tense/Aspect

In this section we are only interested in those tense and aspectual constructions that are differentiated by tone alone. Consequently, the following pairs of tense and aspectual constructions come under focus: completive present (CPE) and completive past constructions (CPA); remote future (RPUT) and immediate future (IFUT); habitual (HAB) and continuous (CONT).

Tone performs a grammatical function in Emai - drawing a distinction between the pairs of tense/aspectual constructions listed in the first paragraph of this section. But for their tonal structures, each of the pairs of constructions above are undifferentiated 'segmentally'.

6.4.3.1 The Completive Constructions

The completive present is defined by the fall of a final high tone on a nominal subject (see e.g.s 3-j

below), and high tones on the verb and its suffix. Tones on subsequent morphemes are realised as downstep high or low depending on their lexical tones. In the completive past, low tones on nominal subject become high provided there is no intervening high tone (see e.g.s a-i below). Low tones preceding a high tone are unchanged. Downstep high tones occur on the verb and its suffix while subsequent verbal morphemes (factative, second member of a serial verb) have a downstep low tone.

In addition, the fall phase of a nominal subject displaying a final HL is eliminated (see e.g.s. (k) and (l). Data is presented below showing the situation in the CPE and CPA constructions.

33 Completive Construction

	<u>Input</u>	<u>Present</u>	<u>Past</u>
a)	òd ₃ è mēfē ì king sleep Fac.	òd ₃ è mēfē ì ì 'the king has slept'	ód ₃ é ì mēfē ì ì 'the king slept'
b)	àgbò là lé ram run away	àgbò là ì lé 'the ram has run away'	àgbó ì lá ì lé 'the ram ran away'
c)	àkàkà ù ì ì grasshopper die Fac.	àkàkà ú ì ì 'the grasshopper has died'	ákáká ì ú ì ì 'the grasshopper died'
d)	òkpòsò wà ré woman come G	òkpòsò wá ì ré 'the woman has come'	ókpósó ì wá ì ré 'the woman came'
e)	íwèxà ù-lò ì children die It. Fac.	íwèxà ú-ló ì ì 'children have died'	íwéxá ì ú-ló ì ì 'children died'
f)	ításà ùwé ì plate lost Fac.	ításà úwé ì ì 'the plate has been lost'	ításá ì úwé ì ì 'the plate is lost'
g)	ùgí dè ré basket fall G	ùgí dé ì ré 'the basket has fallen'	ùgí ì dé ì ré 'the basket fell'

h) `ètòkɛ́` firewood	dè ré fall G	`ètòkɛ́` 'the firewood has fallen'	dé : ré 'the firewood fell'
i) `íkèkɛ́` bicycle	dè l fall Fac.	`íkèkɛ́` 'the bicycle has fallen'	dé : l 'the bicycle fell'
j) `íxwǎ` tick	dè ré fall G	`íxwǎ` 'the tick has fallen'	dé : ré 'the tick fell'
k) `édjò` elders	[`édjò́]` stand G	`édjò` 'the elders have got up'	[`édjò́`] 'the elders got up'
l) `égbjà` morning	[`égbjà`] arrive TER	`égbjà` 'morning has arrived already'	[`égbjà`] 'morning arrived ...'

Perhaps to account for these tonal changes one may postulate rules which take as input the lexical tones and express the tonal patterns in terms of grammatically conditioned tonal changes. Apart from the fact that one would need extremely complex and 'unnatural' rules to account for the supposed change from the underlying to surface representation, the occurrence of tonal downstep in these constructions suggests a situation where linked melodies set lexical tones afloat. Downstep is inserted after the floating low tone before it disappears. Downstep in these constructions could not obviously have resulted from simple tonal changes of assimilatory or dissimilatory types.

The success of a purely tonal analysis of Emai would depend partly on the recognition of tonal morphemes (tomorph: Elugbe 1982) as an essential part of the grammar of Emai. These tomorphs which may be single tone units or tonal melodies (fixed tonal pattern) are grammatically significant tones which are construed as existing independently of 'segmental' phonological string (i.e. distinct from

the lexical tones) and thus must be mapped onto specific constructions. Before we set out to propose melodies for the completive constructions, we must first account for a more general change that affects subject nominals irrespective of the tense/aspect of the sentence in which they occur. For lack of a better term, we simply refer to it as the 'Prepausal (High Tone) Fall (PHF)'. The rule inserts a low tone onto a final high tone syllable of subject nominals and focussed nominals thereby creating a HL on the syllable. This rule which accounts for the fall of the final high tones of nominal subjects applies before the assignment of tense/aspectual tones (see examples 33g-i, 34, 37e-g and 39). Although the rule applies also in completive past, habitual and remote future constructions, the assignment of tone melodies in the completive past and the application of high tone spreading in the habitual and remote future constructions obliterate the fall phase from the surface representation of these constructions. Later on we shall see how this happens when we deal with these constructions. Meanwhile, below are a few examples showing this change in Focus construction:

- 34 a) ògìè dè ògò --> ògò ód₃é ! dè ! ì
king buy bottle 'it is a bottle that the king bought'
- b) ófè ò vî ùgí -> ùgí ófé ! ó ! ì
rat enter at basket 'it is basket that rat entered'
- c) ò è ìjèké -> ìjèké ó ! é ! ì
he/she eat sugarcane 'it is sugarcane that he/she ate'.

The completive present construction assigns a high tomorph to the rightmost syllable of a verb. This high tone spreads backward if a verb is bisyllabic. As a result of the linking of this high tomorph, the low tone of the verb is set afloat after which downstep is inserted and floating low is deleted; hence subsequent tones (i.e. of factative morpheme, second member of a serial verb or verbal sequence etc.) are downstepped.

35 a) (- 33e)

[i v̄ ē x̄ ā ú l̄ ó ! ī]
'children have died'

b (- 33i)

It should be mentioned at this point that once a tone is delinked it is assumed to float. This explains why the derivation above does not reflect a stage at which the low tone floats.

by high tomorph linking and
tone delinking.

by tomorph spreading

by DS insertion and floating
low deletion.

e)

input

by PHF

by high tomorph linking and
tone delinking.

by DS insertion and floating
low deletion.

[éñjẽ^H dé : ré]

'the finger/toe nail has fallen'

The completive past construction carries a H-H-L melody for a sentence. The initial H links to the subject, the second H links to the verb (and its suffix). The final low tone of the melody links to subsequent verbal morphemes (see derivations in (36) below).

The high tone assigned to the subject links to the rightmost syllable thereby delinking the tone of such a syllable. Since the subject must necessarily end in a low tone as a result of PHF rule, the linked H delinks the low of the syllable to which it attaches. The consequence is the downstepping of the following tone of the verb. In addition, this high tone spreads leftward onto low tone syllables. Spreading is blocked by a lexical high tone (see e.g. 33 f-j above). Similarly, the second H of the melody delinks the low tone of the verb and this in turn causes succeeding tones to be downstepped. Like its completive present

counterpart, only one H tone unit is assigned to a verb and its suffix. This tone is linked to the rightmost syllable and spreads leftward to the remaining syllables. Finally, the low tone of the melody is linked to the verbal morpheme after the verb, otherwise it is left unlinked where only one verbal morpheme occurs in the sentence. Below are sample derivations.

36 a (- 33e)

b (-33 f)

input

by melody linking and
tone delinking

by spreading

by DS insertion and float-
ing low deletion.

[itása! úwé!i]

'the plate is lost'

c (- 33 i)

input

by PHF

by melody assignment
and tone delinkingby DS insertion and
floating low deletion

[fkkksé : é :]
 'the bicycle fall'

d

input

by PHF

by melody linking and
tone delinking

by spreading

by DS insertion and
floating low deletion.

[igi : déls : i]

'the baskets fell'

e (-33 1)

input

by melody assignment and
tone delinking

iii) H H !H ! L
 | | | |
 egbja re le
 [égbjá ! ré ! le]
 'morning arrived'

by DS insertion and floating
 low deletion.

In examples (b), (c) and (d) above, we would observe that the melodic high of subject nominals does not spread onto the low tones preceding a high. This is because, as we mentioned earlier on, a lexical high tone blocks the spread of melodic tones. Examples (c), (d) and (e) show the delinking of the fall phase of a final $\bar{H}L$ tone as a result of the linking of the melodic high of the subject. The delinked L stays afloat and is deleted after the insertion of DS.

An alternative analysis to the one we have proposed above is to ascribe the changes on the nominal subject to remnant tones of deleted subject concord marker (SCM) which occurs between NP and VP. The verbs on the other hand could be regarded as toneless, only picking up their tones in different tense/aspectual environments.

The PHF may then be traced to a remnant low tone SCM which links to a final tone of subject in completive

present construction. Hence a final H becomes HL.

While this may account for tonal change on nominal subject in the CPE, it fails to account for the change of low tones to high in CPA. To account for this, we may postulate a remnant H SCM in CPA construction. This tone links onto the last syllable of nominal subject and spreads backward onto low tone syllables. There are a couple of problems with this analysis. First, the SCM itself, even in the habitual and continuous construction where it is still elicited, depends on tense/aspect for its tone (see e.g. 29 below). Moreover, the fall of a final high tone could not have been caused by a low tone SCM since such a fall also occurs in environments where SCM cannot be postulated (e.g. final high tone of a focussed nominal falls as in example 34 above). Also, if one were to postulate a remnant high tone SCM to account for the high tones on nominal subject in CPA, one would be unable to explain the downstepping of the high tone of a verb in situations where the subject terminates in a final high tone (as in examples 33 h-j above). In other words, it is not possible for a H (H) H sequence to become H ! H.

Treating the verbs as toneless before they enter into construction does not allow us to explain the downstepping of the factative morpheme or the second member of a verbal sequence in the completive constructions (see example 33). This is because as toneless morphemes the assignment of aspectual tones cannot result in the introduction of floating (Low) tone segments and consequently DS into the phonetic representation.

6.4.3.2 Immediate and Remote Future Construction

Unlike the completive constructions, the future tense constructions have a marker in /lɔ/. The distinction between the immediate and remote future is created by the spreading of the high tone of the future morpheme onto preceding nominal subject in the latter. Like in other constructions a final high tone on nominal subjects falls (as in examples 37e-g below) although this fall is not observed in the remote future environment as a result of the leftward spread of the high tone of the future tense marker. Spreading also accounts for the absence of the fall

phase of lexically derived final HL tones of subjects in the remote future environment as in exemple (37 h) below. The changes which take place in the future tense constructions are illustrated below:

37 Input

a) ód₃é ló gbè
king Fut. dance

b) ákáká ló ù
Grass
hopper Fut die

c) ó èxáuló là lé
child Fut run away

d) ításá ló ùwè
plate Fut lost

e) ògú ló gbè á
bottle Fut break CS

f) íbàbá ló là lé
father Fut run away

Immediate

òd₃è ló gbè
'the king is about to
dance

ákáká ló ù
'the Grasshopper is about
to die'

òwèxá ló là lé
'the child is about run
away'

ításá ló ùwè
'the plate is about to be
lost'

ògú ló gbè á
'the bottle is about to
be broken'

íbàbá ló là lé
'father is about to run
away'

Remote

òd₃é ló gbè
'the king will dance'

ákáká ló ù
'the Grasshopper will die'

òwèxá ló là lé
'the child will run away'

ításá ló ùwè
'the plate will be lost'

ògú ló gbè á
'the bottle will be ro
broken'

íbàbá ló là lé
'father will run away'

	<u>Input</u>	<u>Immediate</u>	<u>Remote</u>
e)	éhié[é ^h jié] ló tò á finger/toe nail	é ^h jié ló tò á 'the finger/toe nail is is about to be burnt'	é ^h jié ló tò á 'the finger/toe nail will burn'.
h)	égbá [égbá] ló rè morning Put arrive	égbá ló rè 'it is almost morning'	égbá ló rè 'morning will arrive'

No tonal melodies are linked in these constructions, so downstepped tones are absent. Below are derivations of (37a,b,d,f,h).

38 Remote Future

input

by spreading

[ód₃é ló gbè]
 'the king will dance'

input

by spreading

[ákáká ló ù]
 'the grasshopper will die'

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 Public Health
 Chong Piper*

c 1) L H L H L L
 | | | | | |
 itasa lo uwe

input

11) L H H L L
 | | / | |
 itasa lo uwe

by spreading

[ításá ló ùwè]

'the plate will be lost'

d 1) L L H H L H
 | | | | | |
 ibaba lo la le

input

11) L L H (D) H L H
 | | | / | |
 ibaba lo la le

by PHF

111) L L H H L H
 | | | / | |
 ibabá lo la le

by spreading

[íbàbá ló là lé]

'father will run away'

Examples (c) and (d) above show that a lexical high tone blocks the spreading of the high tone of the future tense marker. In all the examples, we find that the high tones of the subject and the high tone on the future tense marker are realised phonetically on the same pitch level. This confirms our derivation of the high tones on subject nominals through spreading of the high tone of the future morpheme.

The PHF rule applies before spreading takes place (see example (d) above), hence the absence of the fall in the surface representation. In the immediate future environment the fall is realised because the high tone of the future morpheme does not spread. We have not included derivations of the immediate future

in our examples because except for the PHF no other change applies in that environment.

6.4.3.3 The Habitual and Continuous Constructions

The habitual and continuous aspects are undifferentiated 'segmentally'. The distinction between both constructions is in the H-L-H melody associated with the former and L-H-H melody associated with the latter. Below is data showing changes in both constructions.

<u>Input</u>	<u>Continuous</u>	<u>Habitual</u>
a) òkpòsò c a là woman SCM ASP run	òkpòsò ò ó lá 'the woman is running'	òkpòsò ó ò lá 'woman runs'
b) ígbáláká c a yáé ladder SCM ASP expensive	ígbáláká ò ó yáé 'ladder is becoming expensive'	ígbáláká ó ò yáé 'ladder is expensive'
c) ékpè c a là já leopard SCM ASP run about	ékpè ò ó lá:jà 'the leopard is running about'	ékpè ó ò lá:jà 'the leopard runs about'
d) ígbégbè c a tò velvet SCM ASP burn	ígbégbè ò ó tò 'the velvet is bruning'	ígbégbè ó ò tò 'a velvet burns'
e) émèlá c a hámá/èyè cow SCM ASP tasty pregnant	émèlá ò ó hámá 'the cow is pregnant'	émèlá ó ò èyè 'beef is tasty'
f) ògó c a àá bottle SCM ASP leak	ògó ò ó àá 'the bottle is leaking'	ògó ó ò àá 'a bottle leaks'

The melodic tones of the continuous and habitual constructions are shared among the SCM, the aspect morpheme and the verb respectively. In the continuous construction the first L is assigned to the SCM while the two H melodic tones are assigned to the aspect morpheme and verb respectively. Similarly, in the habitual construction, the first H is assigned to the SCM. This H spreads leftward onto low tone syllables of the subject. The L is assigned to the aspectual morpheme while the final H is assigned to the verb. In both constructions the last melodic H is assigned to the rightmost syllable of the verb (plus its suffix). However, unlike in completive constructions, it does not spread to the remaining syllables of the verb. The derivations below show how the assignment of melodic tones is implemented as well as other tonal changes that take place in these constructions.

[igbalàkà ò óyáé]

'ladder is becoming
expensive'

[igbáláká ò ò yáé]

'ladder is expensive'

Continuous

a 1) L L L L L~H~H input
 | | | | |
 okposò c a lá

11) L L L (L) (H) L
 | | | | |
 okposò c a lá

by melody linking
and tone delinking

111) -

by spreading

[òkposò ò ó lá]

'the woman is running'

Habitual

L L L L L H~L~H
 | | | | |
 okposò c a lá

L L L (H) (L) L
 | | | | |
 okposò c a lá

H L L H L
 | | | | |
 okposò c a lá

[òkposò ó ò lá]

'a woman runs'

iv) by DS insertion
and tone deletion

input

by melody linking and
 tone delinking

111) -

by spreading

[igbégbè ó ó tó]

'the velvet is burning'

[igbégbé ó ó tó]

'velvet burns'

input

- 11) LL L~H~H
by PHF
- 111) L HL (L) H
by melody linking
and tone delinking
- 1v) - L H H L LH (L)
by spreading
- [ògò ó ó àá]
'the bottle is leaking'
- [ògò ó ó àá]
'a bottle leaks'

It would be observed that at an underlying level, the SCM and the aspect morphemes are postulated as toneless. This is informed by the fact that these morphemes depend on the aspect constructions for their tones, and the behaviour of succeeding tones does not suggest that these morphemes have any underlying tones.

That spreading rather than melody tones account for the high tones on subject nominals in habitual construction is observable from the fact that these tones are realised on the same level as the high melodic tone of the SCM. Where melodies are involved lexical tones would be displaced - leading to the downstepping of subsequent tones if the displaced tones are low.

Finally (d) above shows that a lexical high tone blocks the spread of the melodic H of the SCM in the habitual construction (see also (e)). Like in other constructions a final high tone on subject falls. This fall is obliterated in the habitual construction as a result of the spread of the melodic H of SCM (see the derivation in 40 e above).

6.2.2 Tonal Changes in Objects

Apart from the changes discussed above, some other changes take place in the sentence. Non-final nominals occurring as objects of a verb or preposition may undergo tonal changes. These changes occur after tense/aspectual tones have been assigned to the sentence and syllable structure processes have applied. In the following paragraphs we shall attempt to present the picture and proceed to analyse the changes in a simple way.

There is a way in which tense/aspect determine the pattern of change. In simple completive constructions, non-final nominal object simply realise high tones. However, LH pattern is realised on non-final qualifier of an associative phrase. Below are some examples:

41	<u>Input</u>		<u>Output</u>
a)	ò gbé ófè	→	ò gbófè
	he/she kill rat		'he/she has killed a rat'
b)	ò gbé ófè òdè	→	ò gbófé òdè
	he/she kill rat yester- day		'he/she killed a rat yesterday'.

Input

c) ò gbé ófè ví ìmè →
he/she kill rat at farm

d) ò gbé ófè ví ìmè òdè →
he/she kill rat at farm yesterday

e) ò fi òd₃è émì →
he/she hit king thing

f) ò gbé ófè ísì òd₃è òdè →
he/she kill rat am king yesterday

Output

ò gbófé vímè
'he/she has killed a rat on the farm'

ò gbófé vímè òdè
'he/she killed a rat on the farm yesterday'

ò f₃jód₃é émì
'he/she has hit the king'

ò gbófé sòd₃é òdè
'he/she killed the king's rat yesterday'

Where the sentence contains an indirect object no change is recorded on the direct object as shown by examples (g) and (h) below.

g) ò gbé ófè jé òd₃è →
he/she kill rat to king

ò gbófè jód₃è
'he/she has killed a rat for the king'

Input

e) ó à gbé ófè jè òd₃è
he/she HAB kill rat to king

f) ó à gbé ófè jè òd₃è vi ímè èpáá
he/she CONT kill rat to king at farm now

g) ó à gbé ófè ísì òd₃è sáá
he/she HAB kill rat am king always

Output

→ ó ǝ gbòfè jòd₃è
'he/she kills rat for the king'

→ ó ǝ gbòfè jòd₃è vímè èpáá
'he/she is killing a rat to the king at the farm at the moment'

→ ó ǝ gbòfè sòd₃è sáá
'he/she kills the king's rat always'

The future tense constructions behave like the habitual/continuous constructions except that like the completive constructions, no change takes place on the direct object if the sentence also contains an indirect object. The indirect objects have high tones.

InputOutput

- a) ó ló gbè ófè → ó ló : gbófè
 he/she FUT kill rat → 'he/she will kill a rat'
- b) ó ló gbè ófè áxò → ó ló gbòfè áxò
 he/she FUT kill rat tomorrow → 'he/she will kill a rat tomorrow'
- c) ó ló gbè ófè ví ímè → ó ló gbòfè vímè
 he/she FUT kill rat at farm → 'he/she will kill a rat at the farm'
- d) ó ló gbè ófè ví ímè áxò → ó ló gbòfè vímè áxò
 he/she FUT kill rat at farm tomorrow → 'he/she will kill a rat at the farm tomorrow'
- e) ò ló gbè ófè jé òd₃è → ò ló:gbófè jòd₃è
 he/she FUT kill rat to king → 'he/she is about to kill a rat to the king'
- f) ò ló gbè ófè jé òd₃è ví ímè ènáà → ò ló:gbófè jód₃é vímè ènáà
 he/she FUT kill rat to king at farm now → 'he/she is about to kill a rat to the king at the farm'
- g) ó ló gbè ófè ísí òd₃è → ó ló gbòfè sòd₃è
 he/she FUT kill rat am king → 'he/she will kill the king's rat'
- h) ó ló gbè ófè ísí òd₃è áxò → ó ló gbòfè sòd₃è áxò
 he/she FUT kill rat am king tomorrow → 'he/she will kill the king's rat tomorrow'

The incidence of DS observed in examples (43 a, e, and f above) is caused by the deletion of low tone vowels and ^{is} not a result of the tonal change which we are discussing here.

From the data above (examples A1, A2 and A3) it would be observed that apart from the requirement that a nominal should occur non-finally, whether or not change occurs, and the nature of change depend upon the tense/aspect expressed as well as the structure of the object.

To account for these changes, we postulate a floating high tone (H) and a floating low tone (L). The floating (H) occurs at every boundary between a non-final object nominal and a following morpheme, except between a direct and an indirect object in completive and future constructions. This floating (H) spreads leftward onto preceding object nominals. But in completive aspect and future tense constructions the spread does not extend to the direct object if the sentence also contains an indirect object (as in examples 41h and 43 f above). The floating (L) is linked only after the floating (H) spread has applied.

[ò gbófé vímé òdè]

'he/she killed a rat at the farm yesterday'

c (-41g)

[ò gbófè jód₃é vímé òdè]

'he/she killed a rat to the king at the farm'

d (-42 f)

[ò ó gbòfé jòd₃é vímé èɲāā]

'he/she is killing a rat to the king at the moment'

e (- ʌ3d)

[ó ló gbòfé vímé áxò]

'he/she will kill a rat at the farm tomorrow'

f (- 43 f)

[ò ló !gbófè jód₃é vime ɛnāā]

'he/she is about to kill a rat to the king at the farm'

[ò ló dɔgbɛlé vekí ɛnāā]

'he/she is about to buy a belt at the market'

[ó ò gbakaká jomémé vimeúsáá]

'he/she kills grasshopper to the lunatic at the farm always'

[ò ó kēnògóló lí éḡá óké sḡnāá]

'he/she is sharing praying mantis for children
at Oke now'

(L̄) insertion does not apply in the future tense construction if the sentence contains both direct and indirect objects. Similarly, spreading of (H) is restricted to the indirect object only.

Whether or not a nominal object will undergo tonal change may also depend on its lexical tone pattern. No change takes place if a nominal has a final high tone. Thus in the examples below no change is recorded.

45 a) ́́ á dé ódòdó sáá → ́́ ó dódòdó sáá
he/she HAB buy flower always 'he/she buys flowers always'

b) ́́ á é Ijèké ́́nǎá → ́́ ó Ijèké ́́nǎá
he/she CONT eat sugarcane now 'he/she is eating sugarcane now'

c) ́́ ́́ ló dé Ikòkó áxò → ́́ ́́ ́́ Ikòkó áxò
he/she FUT buy cocoa tomorrow 'he/she will buy cocoa tomorrow'

d) ́́ ́́ gbé é:ǎó òdè → ́́ gbé:ǎó òdè
he/she make money yesterday 'he/she made money yesterday'

e) ́́ ́́ dé ògídíǎá èdèdè → ́́ dògídíǎá èdèdè
he/she buy cutlass(type) moments ago 'he/she bought a cutlass moments ago'

One would expect the nominal objects above to display either a LHa or an all H pattern in line with the general pattern. The reason why this does not happen is that in Emai, a lexical high tone blocks the spread of a high tomorph or floating tone (see section 6.4.3). Thus, since a final high tone makes it impossible for (H) spread to apply, (L) insertion which is ordered after it does not apply. Finally, one would like to mention at this point that these tonal changes seem to reflect certain complexities in the structure of the sentence, presumably at the discourse level. We are as yet unable to determine the nature of these complexities.

6.5 Intonation

In this section we shall attempt to account autosegmentally for intonational phenomena in Emai. These are the question intonation and DD. These two phenomena are found to interact in interesting ways in the language. Our analysis is based essentially on Inkelas, Leben and Cobler (1987) (henceforth ILC). They accounted for intonational phenomena in Hausa by postulating a second

tonal tier - the Register tier. "A register tone shifts the register, so that it affects not only the tone it is associated with but all remaining tones in the phrase as well" (p. 4).

Very simply, intonation refers to the pattern of fluctuation in pitch realised under different grammatical conditions or mood. Declarative sentences in Emai are differentiated from their yes-no question counterparts only by different FO contour graphs in both sentence types. There are two types of yes-no questions in Emai - the simple yes-no and the yes-no plus surprise.

6.5.1 Simple Yes-no

The yes-no question in Emai bears some similarity to yes-no questions in Hausa. According to ILC (1987:2), Hausa yes/no questions combine three factors. These are the total or partial suspension of DD, the change of phrase final lexical High to extra- High and the realisation of a following boundary low as raised low. In Emai, question intonation also involves the suspension of DD and the change of sentence final (not phrase final as in Hausa) lexical High to extra-High. All High and Low tones

- c) ófè ló vǎré ǎǎǎ
 'rat will come now'

- d) ébò jêdó
 'doctors have gone to Benin'

6.5.2 Yes-no question plus Surprise

The yes-no plus surprise question is like the simple yes-no in terms of global raising and the suspension of DB. It is defined by a final rising contour. The contour begins from the level of a low and rises to an extra-High level.

Final high tones (of declarative sentences) first

fall to low before rising to the extra-High level (in yes-no plus surprise question). Below are examples:

47 (46a-d)

Following ILC (1987) we postulate a register tier for Emsi. This tier has a rising and a low register tone. The former accounts for question intonation while the latter accounts for DD. "Register tones are linked to lexical tones and by virtue of this linking alter

the realizations of these tones". The register tone affects all tones within its domain by resetting the register either upward or downward depending on whether we are dealing with a high or low register. Figure (44) shows a representation of the two tiers:

The two yes-no question types in Emai can be accounted for by postulating a rising register tone which anchors to the last high tone in simple yes-no and the last tone in the yes-no plus surprise mood. The surprise element is captured by the fact that the rise starts at a lower level than the anchoring tone in the latter but at the same level as the anchoring tone in the former. The rise in the pitch of preceding tones is the result of the spread of the register tone unto preceding lexical tones. This is schematised below:

A register low accounts for the occurrence of DD. Down-drift is a process whereby a low tone induces a downward register shift which persists across the tone phrase.

Fig ('6) below captures the DD rule in Emai.

(a) shows the association of a register Low with a Low on the lexical tier. (b) shows this Low register linking to the succeeding lexical High.

The suspension of DD in question intonation is because the register High and register Low occur in complementary distribution. Looking at it from a phonetic perspective, one would observe that

if we interpret each register tone literally as setting up a new register for subsequent tones, and if we interpret High register as the instruction

to go up in FO by a certain amount and Low register as the instruction to go down by a similar amount, then we should expect that in a sequence of alternating H and L register tones, each successive register High tone will cancel out the lowering effect of the preceding Low tone ... We should expect that the value of High should remain relatively constant across the phrase, despite intervening low tones. (ILC 1987: 7).

Finally, we would like to mention that the analysis presented above is based purely on auditory impressions. Although the change in FO level is perceivable, instrumental study is still required to determine the exact nature of the FO curve in questions, the level of fall and rise of the register and the frequency of the extra-High vis-a-vis the lexical High. We are unable to carry out these investigations because at the time of this work, relevant equipment for carrying out the investigations was not available.

to go up in FO by a certain amount and Low register as the instruction to go down by a similar amount, then we should expect that in a sequence of alternating H and L register tones, each successive register High tone will cancel out the lowering effect of the preceding Low tone ... We should expect that the value of High should remain relatively constant across the phrase, despite intervening low tones. (ILC 1987: 7).

Finally, we would like to mention that the analysis presented above is based purely on auditory impressions. Although the change in FO level is perceivable, instrumental study is still required to determine the exact nature of the FO curve in questions, the level of fall and rise of the register and the frequency of the extra-High vis-a-vis the lexical High. We are unable to carry out these investigations because at the time of this work, relevant equipment for carrying out the investigations was not available.

preceding the extra-High are raised above their normal level although not to the level of the extra-High (Global raising). Below are a few examples illustrating simple yes/no question intonation.

16 a) ɔ̀d₃é ló : gbófè

'the king is about to kill a rat'

b) ɔ̀d₃é ló : gbófè

'the king will kill a rat'

APPENDIX

1.0 SENTENCE STRUCTURE

This section is intended to provide much of the syntactic background information to Chapters A-6. The concern is primarily with the surface structure since it provides the information relevant to the application of phonological rules (SPE).

1.1 The Structure of the sentence in Emai

The structure of Emai sentence is perhaps best captured by the following tree diagram.

Fig. *7

We shall now discuss the structures of the sentence components starting with the NP.

1.2 The Noun Phrase

The noun phrase in Emai is made up of an optional pre-modifier, a head nominal and one or more optional post-modifiers. The post-modifier may be a noun, a demonstrative, a possessive pronoun, a numeral or a noun phrase.

1.2.1 Premodification

Premodification involves the definite article, the augmentative marker, the diminutive marker, individuator, etc. Below are some examples.

- | | |
|--------------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| 1a1) élí éwè
'the goat' | 1i) élí éwè
'the goats' |
| b1) úl ékpà
'small bag' | 1i) íl ékpà
'small bags' |
| c1) údù éèxò
'big garden egg' | 1i) ídù éèxò
'big garden eggs' |
| d1) úkpà éwèè
'a lobe of kolanut' | 1i) íkpà éwèè
'lobes of kolanuts' |

The premodifiers agree with their head nouns in number by varying their initial vowel prefixes.

1.2.2 Postmodification

It is postmodification that presents interesting phonological consequences in Emai. Usually, noun phrases are identified on the basis of the type of modifier or qualifier in the phrase. The following noun phrases have been identified in Emai.

1.2.3 The Demonstrative Construction

The demonstrative construction is made up of a noun or numeral plus a demonstrative qualifier. Like the premodifiers, demonstratives also agree with their head nominal in number by altering their initial vowel prefixes.

2ai) óuèxa òlá
child this
'this child'

ii) íuèxa èlá
children these
'these children'

bi) ófè sáí
rat this
'this rat'

ii) éfè éáí
rat those
'those rats'

di) òkpòsò ólǎí
woman the other
'the other woman'

ii) íkpòsò élǎí
women the others
'the other women'

41) ǫkpá ǫlǎ
 one this
 'this one'

42) ǫvǎ ǫlǎ
 two these
 'these two'

1.2.0 Associative Construction

The term associative construction is used narrowly in this work to include only the types of constructions discussed in this subsection. We have identified two types of associative constructions in Emsi based on the semantic content of the phrases. The types are the 'Descriptive Associative Construction' and the 'Possessive Associative Construction'.

1.2.0.1 Descriptive Associative Construction

This construction is made up of a head noun, a definite article (functioning as the associative marker) an adjectival, noun, adverbial or numeral qualifier.

Below are some examples:

3 a) ǎrà ǫlǎ ǫgbégbè
 woodpecker Am velvet
 'velvet coloured woodpecker'

b) ǫwǎ (ǫlǎ) ǫgbè
 child Am new
 'newborn baby'

- c) ǫvèxǎ́ (ǫlǐ) ǫbè
 child AM bad
 'bad child'
- d) ébè ǫlǐ ǫdè
 book AM/yesterday
 'the book of yesterday'
- e) ǫvèxǎ́ ǫlǐ ǫvǎ
 children em two
 'the two children'
- f) úgbáí (ǫlǐ) ǫzèèà
 round AM third
 'third round/instance'
- g) ǫvèxǎ́ (ǫlǐ) ǫgbèrè
 children AM surplus
 'children who are surplus'

The Associative marker is optional when we have a numeral (ordinal) or adjectival qualifier.

1.2."2 Possessive Associative Construction

This construction is made up of an optional premodifier, the head noun, an associative marker (ǫlǐ or ǫsǐ) and a noun, pronoun, or demonstrative qualifier.

Below are examples illustrating this construction.

- a) ébè ísì ògìè
 book AM king
 'the king's book'
- b) (óìí) ókà (ísì) òvè
 the maize AM mine
 'my maize'
- c) èkpà ísì òlǎ
 bag AM this
 'this one's bag'
- d) (úvì) íwè ési ófè
 small house AM rat
 'rat's small house'

1.2.5 Alienable and Inalienable Possession

A distinction is drawn between the alienable and inalienable possession. This distinction is marked formally by the obligatory presence of the associative marker in the former and its absence in the latter. The difference is best explained by the following examples:

- 5 a1) úhuví ísì évá
 head AM yam
 'top portion of yam (as opposed to tail)'

11) óhùvǐ ∅ éuǎ
 'head of yam - cut off portion'

b 1) èkpà ísǐ ókà
 bag AM maize
 'bag for maize'

11) èkpà ∅ ókà
 'a bag of maize'

c 1) ùbèlè ísǐ ámé!yó
 gourd AM cowry
 'gourd for cowry'

11) ùbèlè ∅ ámé!yó
 'gourd of cowry'

d 1) íwè ésí àvǎ
 house AM yours(pl.)
 'your house (residence)'

11) íwè ∅ àvǎ
 'your house (ownership)'

When we have the associative marker the two nominals involved are related loosely whereas the relationship is stronger when it is absent. Above this is the fact that one referent is involved when the am is absent. Two

referents are normally maintained and related by the am.

1.2.6 Recursive Associative Construction

The difference between the simple associative construction and the recursive associative construction is that the qualifier is an NP in the latter. In the former it is a simple noun. Below are examples:

- 6 a) [iwè ési [óli ó ʒ]]
 NP₁ NP₂ NP₂ NP₁
 house AM the child
 'the child's house'
- b) [ébé ísi [ògiè ísi òkèl]]
 NP₁ NP₂ NP₂ NP₁
 book AM king AM oke
 'book belonging to the king of Oke'
- c) [ításà ísi [ófè (ísi) à ʒ]]
 NP₁ NP₂ NP₂ NP₁
 plate AM rat (AN) nine
 'my rat's plate'

d) [íbè ísì [órè síí òfúà]]
 NP₁ NP₂ NP₂ NP₁

band AM rat AM white

'the white rat's band'

e) [óbò ísì [óvèxa òlǎ]]
 NP₁ NP₂ NP₂ NP₁

hand AM child this

'this child's hand'

1.2.7 Quantifier and Numeral Constructions

Finally, there are the quantifier and numeral constructions which consist of a head noun plus a quantifier or numeral qualifiers respectively. Like the demonstrative construction, these constructions have no markers. Below are some examples:

7 a) ìkpòsò èvá
 women two

'two women'

b) àkàkà òkpá
 grasshopper one

'one grasshopper'

c) ópià ósò
 cutlass one
 'a certain cutlass'

d) ébè éso
 books some
 'some books'

1.3 The Auxiliary Phrase

Our treatment of the syntax of Emai, especially with reference to the auxiliary phrase, is at best cursory. The structure of the auxiliary node in Emai can be captured by the following rewrite rule:

Fig. 28 AUX → (SCM) (NEG) TENSE/ASPECT (PREVERBAL)

The rule states that only the tense/aspect marker is obligatory. Subject Concord Marker (SCM), negator and preverbal elements are optional.

1.3.1 The Subject Concord Marker

Amayo (1976) observes that in most Edo (Bini) sentences there is a marker occurring between a nominal subject and a following auxiliary marker or verb stem. This marker is the subject concord marker (SCM). The

SCM relates the NP subject to the predicate or verb phrase. In Emai the SCM shows up in all negative sentences. In positive sentences it shows up only in the habitual and continuous aspect constructions. In addition, the SCM is absent in sentences (positive or negative) with pronominal subjects. Examples below show only environments where the SCM occurs.

- 8 a) ògiè ò á .lá
king SCM CONT run
'the king is running'
- b) iuèxá ò á gbé
children SCM CONT dance
'children are dancing'
- c) ófè ò í là
rat SCM NEG run
'rat didn't run'
- d) éwè ó í à là
goat SCM NEG HAB run
'a goat never runs'
- e) èdó ó à víé
Edo SCM HAB cry
'Edo cries'

- b) $\text{fu} \acute{\text{e}} \text{x} \grave{\text{a}} \text{ gb} \grave{\text{e}} \text{ óf} \grave{\text{e}}$ → $\text{f} \acute{\text{e}} \text{x} \acute{\text{a}} \text{ é} : \text{gb} \acute{\text{o}} \text{f} \acute{\text{e}}$
 children kill rat children RP kill rat
 'it is the children who killed a rat'
- c) $\text{íj} \acute{\text{a}} \text{í gb} \grave{\text{e}} \text{ óf} \grave{\text{e}}$ → $\text{íj} \acute{\text{a}} \text{í j} \acute{\text{a}} : \text{gb} \acute{\text{o}} \text{f} \acute{\text{e}}$
 they kill rat they RP kill rat
 'it is they who killed a rat'
- d) $\text{ù gb} \grave{\text{e}} \text{ óf} \grave{\text{e}}$ → $\text{w} \acute{\text{e}} \text{w} \acute{\text{e}} \text{ ú} : \text{gb} \acute{\text{o}} \text{f} \acute{\text{e}}$
 you kill rat you(emph) RP kill rat
 'you killed a rat'
- e) $\text{à gb} \grave{\text{e}} \text{ óf} \grave{\text{e}}$ → $\text{m} \acute{\text{a}} \text{m} \acute{\text{a}} \text{í} \text{ ná} : \text{gb} \acute{\text{o}} \text{f} \acute{\text{e}}$
 we kill rat we(emph) RP kill rat
 'we killed a rat'

The replacive pronouns agree in number with a noun subject; but the SCM does not. They also agree in number and person with a pronoun subject. The SCM is placed under the Aux. node rather than the NP (subject) because it displays a close affinity with other members of the Aux as regards the phonological processes it undergoes. Vowel elision, glide formation and assimilation/contraction all apply in Emai - affecting only morphemes that fall within the same primary constituent boundaries. The SCM is assimilated and undergoes contraction with other members of the Aux (precisely the

HAB /CONT and NEG markers); but never with a preceding nominal subject. We see this as an indication that it belongs with other Aux elements. In addition, since the SCM expresses concord between the subject and predicate, it is logical to have it on the auxiliary node.

1.3.2 Tense and Aspect

Emai expresses a wide range of tense/aspectual meanings but the only ones that are of interest to us in this work are the completive past and present aspects, the habitual (HAB.) and the continuous (CONT.) aspects, and the immediate and remote future tenses (IFUT, RFUT). The differences between these pairs of tense/aspectual forms is implemented by tonal changes/alternatives. Detailed discussions of these pitch contrasts is presented in Chapter 6 (6.3.4-6.3.7). Meanwhile, we present some examples of these tense/aspectual types.

Completive (past)

- 10 a) [áwé : lá : lǎ]
 goat run away
 'the goat ran away'

Present

- b) [éwè lá : lɛ]
 'the goat has run away'

Non-Completive
Continuous

- c) [ófè ò ó gbé]
 rat SCM CONT dance
 'the rat is dancing'

Habitual

- d) [ófé ó ò gbé]
 rat SCM HAB. dance
 'a rat dances'

Future

- e) [ɛmò̃ ló ù]
 child IFUT die
 'the child is about to die'

- f) [ɛmò̃́ ló ù]
 child RFUT die
 'the child will die'

1.3.3 Preverbals

The preverbal class includes elements that modify the verb in other ways that are not strictly speaking

temporal or durative. They precede the verb. Examples of such words in Emai are:

- 11 a) dóbò 'accidentally'
 b) dábò 'deliberately'
 c) blà[bjà] 'dubitive'
 d) kiè [tjè] 'repetitive'
 e) méti 'able'
 f) zèzè 'a bit'
 g) zéni 'greatly'
 h) etc.

These elements are not verbs, neither can they function as verbs.

- 1) ò zéni é lùgò
 he/she greatly eat bean(species)
 'he/she ate a lot of beans'
- 2) ò dóbò gbé sí
 he/she accidentally kill it
 'he/she killed it accidentally'
- 3) ò bíá vâré?
 he/she Dub. come
 'did he/she come? - I wonder?'

1.3.4 The Verb Phrase

The structure of the VP in Emai can be captured by the following rewrite rule:

The rule above accounts for two types of VP. The first which we tag a simple VP has an obligatory V and optional NP, PP or LP. The second type which we refer to as complex VP dominates a VP.

1.3.4.1 Simple VP

A simple VP has only one verb and its derivation does not involve any kind of subordination or coordination. A fully specified simple VP can be illustrated by the structure below:

Fig. 50

[ò gbé ófè ó uí òtòí]

he/she kill rat onto at ground

'he/she has killed a rat (onto) on the ground'

1.3.4.2 Complex VP

The complex VP accounts for the serial verb construction. A number of writers dealing with serialisation in various languages have proposed various syntactic sources and derivation for serial verbs. They propose that serial verbs are derived from coordinate sentences, modifying sources, embedding sources or a combination of any of them (see Awobuluyi 1967, 1973; Boadi 1968;

Williams 1971; Bamgboṣe 1973, 197^b; Van Leynseele 1975, etc.). We believe that serials in Emai are derived from coordinate structures which then undergo subordination and deletion to arrive at the surface structure. These stages are illustrated below:

Input Structures

Fig. 51

By Subordination

Fig. 52

By Equi-NP deletion

Fig. 53

[ò dé fi ó uí òtòí]

it has fallen onto the ground'

It is beyond the scope of this work to attempt to justify these structures, but it is clear that whatever the input or stages of derivation are, at the surface structure level, VP_1 dominates two VPs. It is also clear that at an underlying level the two verbs in series belong logically to different sentences.

1.4 Sentence Types

One can identify three sentence types in Emai. These are the simple, the complex and the compound sentence types.

1.4.1 The Simple Sentence

A simple sentence contains one main verb.

- 12 a) ̀̀̀kpě gbé ófè
leopard kill rat
'the leopard has killed a rat'
- b) ófè é ókà
rat eat maize
'the rat has eaten maize'

1.4.2 Complex Sentence

A complex sentence contains two simple sentences one embedded in the other.

- 13 a) [ófè [ólí í dè : ì] ú : ì]
s₁ s₂
rat Def I buy Fac. die Fac.
'the rat which I bought has died'
- b) [í gbé [ófè ólí ó : é ókà]]
s₁ s₂
I kill rat Def it eat maize
'I have killed the rat which ate maize'

1.4.3 Compound Sentence

A compound sentence contains two or more conjoined simple sentences. The conjunctions are underlined in the examples below:

14 a) éwè bí ófè vá : rè
 goat and rat come
 'the goat and the rat have come'

b) xì éwé xì òfé váré òdè
 Comp. goat Comp. rat come yesterday
 'both goat and rat came yesterday'

Only the simple sentence is of primary interest in this work. A simple sentence may be declarative or interrogative. Both sentence types may be positive, negative or focussed.

1.5 Declarative and Interrogative sentences in Emai.

These are the wh-question and the Yes-no question. The former type is differentiated from the declarative sentence by the presence of a Wh-morpheme as the object of the sentence. The Wh-morpheme has a final rising tone.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>15 a) áwà gbé : émé
 dog kill what
 'what did the dog kill?</p> | <p>ii) émé áwá gbé : í
 what dog kill Fac</p> |
| <p>b) éwè jé ébè
 goat go where
 where did the goat go?</p> | <p>ii) ébè éwé jé : í
 where goat go Fac</p> |
| <p>c) ù gbé óè
 you beat who
 who did you beat?</p> | <p>ii) óè ú !gbé : í
 who you beat Fac</p> |

The examples to the right are focussed variants of examples to the left.

A yes-no question is not different from the declarative sentence segmentally. Both sentence types only differ in pitch. Question is marked by a rising intonational tomorph which attaches to the last high tone and last tone in the sentence in the simple yes-no and yes-no plus surprise questions respectively. The FO level of the preceding tones is raised (See Chapter 6, section 6.5 for a discussion and exemplification).

1.6 Focus Construction

Two types of focus constructions are in existence in Emai. They are the sentence focus marked by éří occurring before the sentence and the word or phrase focus, marked by foregrounding a word or phrase (see examples (16) and (17) below for both types). The pronouns have independent focus forms (see section 3.5.2 for these).

16. Sentence Focus

a) éří ófé : é ókà
 Foc. rat eat maize
 'the rat ate the maize'

b) éří i : tó éđř
 Foc I roast palmnut
 'I roasted palmnut'

17. Word or Phrase Focus

a) ófè (lí) ó : é ókà
 rat Def. RP eat maize
 'it is the rat that ate the maize'

b) ókà (lí) ófé : é : í
 maize Def. rat eat Fac.
 'it is maize that the rat ate'

- c) $\acute{u}\acute{e}m\acute{f}$ (l $\acute{i}$) $\acute{o}f\acute{e}$: $\acute{e}$ $\acute{o}k\grave{a}$
 eating Def. rat eat maize
 'it is eating that the rat ate maize'

Note that the presence of the definite particle makes focussed word definite and consequently adds strength to the focus. It does not mark focus in itself hence its optional status. It is only the informational structure of the sentence that is changed by the word or phrase focus. The addition of l $\acute{i}$ adds definiteness by identifying the referent as the undisputed performer or object or action.

1.7 Negation

Negation is marked by the negative morpheme ($\acute{i}$) occurring after the subject concord marker in simple sentences (see 1.3 for the structure of the Auxiliary Phrase). In Focus sentences the negative focus form ($k\acute{i}$) occurs. This morpheme occurs immediately after ($\acute{e}r\acute{i}$) to express negative focus in sentences. In word or phrase focus it occurs after the focussed entity. Generally, the position of the negative morpheme depends upon what is negated - the sentence or phrase. It

immediately precedes the negated unit. Using the examples in (18) and (19), negation would be realized thus:

18. VP Negation

- a) ófè ó ì è ókà
 rat SCM NEG eat maize
 'the rat did not eat maize'

Sentence Focus Negation

- b) érí kí ófé : é ókà
 Foc NEG rat eat maize
 'it is not that the rat ate maize'

Word or Phrase Focus Negation

- c) ófè kí ó : é : ókà
 rat NEG RP eat maize
 'it is not the rat that ate maize'
- d) ókà kí ófé : é : ì
 maize NEG. rat eat Fac.
 'it is not maize that the rat ate'

We would want to note that all the examples presented in this appendix reflect stages before the application

of vowel elision, and glide formation across word boundary. This enables us to retain individual words.

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